

**Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in
China:**
Evidence from the Food Industry

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DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis is my original work which has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Yuxiao Zhou

Personal details withheld.

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ABSTRACT

Based on a content analysis of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) reports of top 100 food companies in China from 2011 to 2015, and a thematic analysis of in-depth interviews with four groups of participants, this thesis aims to study the current CSR disclosing level of China's food industry and to explore the motivations and obstacles to conduct CSR practice. The results obtained show that overall CSR information disclosure level of Chinese food companies is very low and incomplete. There is evidence to show many Chinese food companies use a 'Greenwash' to repair their brand reputation and improve their company's public image. They employ a decoupling strategy to only formally participate in CSR activities, rather than fully understand all their responsibilities in various aspects. This thesis adds to the extant knowledge of the Chinese harmony approach, revealing that companies in China carry out their CSR activities to show their concerns for nature and kindness to people. The findings explain the connection between the Harmonious approach and Shareholder, Legitimacy and Institutional Theory, which can also explain the motivations to carry out CSR practice and disclose CSR information. This thesis identifies that insufficient knowledge from each aspect of stakeholder, incomplete and inefficient legal system and underdeveloped CSR system under the coercion, imitation and regulation are main obstacles to conduct or disclose CSR information. Therefore, in order to improve the Chinese food companies' CSR performance and information disclosure level, this thesis recommends to introduce a mandatory disclosure requirement, perfect the content of CSR reports, strengthen supervision and increase the intensity of punishment, and strengthen education to raise awareness.

Chapter 1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to introduce the research issues and background, research aim and objectives, research design and the structures of this thesis. Section 1.1 introduces the research background, including the contents of understanding of CSR in China. Section 1.2 explains the literature review progress and identifies the research gap. Section 1.3 proposes the research aim and objectives. Section 1.4 explains the importance of this research. Section 1.5 describes the structures of this thesis.

1.1 Research background and motivations

The rapid economic rise in China has resulted in social and environmental problems that, if leave them unresolved, will undermine the country's ability to maintain economic growth and progress for decades (Wei, Shen, Zhou and Li, 2015). These problems include water resources shortage, pollution, working condition, product safety and governance and accountability. The role of companies in addressing these challenges is increasingly recognised and reflected in the appear and practice of CSR. According to the report of Corporate Responsibility and Sustainable Economic Development in China: Lessons for Enterprises (2012), the explanation of current challenges relating to this research are as below:

- Water resources shortage and quality;
- Industrial pollution and greenhouse gas emission;
- Working condition – although it has improved over the past years, the problem of excessive overtime is particularly hard to be sorted;

- Product safety – Product and food safety scandals and recalls have caused deaths, illnesses and injuries. It has damaged the reputation of Chinese brands abroad and caused unease at home country;
- Corruption – Widespread corruption is one of the most intense areas of public concern, and the communist party is increasingly aware that it is a major obstacle to the country's socio-economic development;

Since the 1990s, the concept of CSR has arisen increasing attention from different sectors of society (Tian, 2006). Also, CSR has become a core concept of responding to many issues, including the aspects of environmental and sustainable development of the society, human rights, health and safety, labour rights and stakeholder relationships (Hopkin, 2004; Tian, 2006). As Li and Zhang (2010) indicated, the public is taking an increasingly international view and growing awareness of the corporate social responsibility in recent years. As Wang and Juslin (2009) indicate that although China is becoming a crucial player in CSR, compared to its Western counterparts, its CSR awareness is still rather low. China is the biggest developing country and it has a different culture, political environment and economic strategy from the West. It is reasonable to assume that CSR in China is different from its Western counterparts. Therefore, the first research motivation is to identify the CSR relevant to China's particular social and cultural background by developing a measurement instrument. In other words, this research intends to explore the scale of the actual situation of CSR and its disclosure level reflected by relevant published information. Particularly, this thesis aims to identify the motivations or obstacles of a company to conduct or disclose its CSR activities by carrying out in-depth interviews with related shareholders.

This research focuses on the food industry with the concern for the exposed food safety

incidents, for example, Sanlu's Melamine-Tainted Milk Crisis (Lu and Tao, 2013), 'Sewer' oil (Foster, 2011) and other scandals raised recently. The public has started to pay increasing attention to the health and safety of the food. Although companies are increasingly disclosing CSR information under the public and government pressure afterward, it is worth to study whether the current annual stand-alone CSR or other format reports (e.g. environment report and integrated financial reports) can satisfy the increasing requirement for accountability. This is the third motivation to access the current disclosing level of CSR information of food companies in China, then to identify the reasons they choose to or not to disclose CSR information, and finally to offer practical suggestions to improve the CSR practices in China and to increase the food industry's CSR disclosure level. With the above research motivations and researcher's intentions, literature have been reviewed to identify the research gap discussed below, and the research aim and objectives are as summarized following.

1.2 Literature Review and Research Gap

Firstly, an extensive literature review method is employed. In order to carry out the extensive review, 554 articles, which are related to CSR, CSRD, CSRD in China, CSR in food industry are searched and downloaded (Excel file is available upon request and evidence is shown as figure 1.1). Then, the Systematic Review approach is employed. By intensively reviewing the top ten journals, relevant articles about CSR are searched, then to record key information in an Excel form including Author, Publish Year, Title, Key Words, Journal Code, Research Country, Research Method, Research Instrument, Data Analysis, Content Analysis, Research Sample, Findings, Limitations, Disclosure/Reports, Research Area, Motivation and Obstacle. The intensively reviewing focused on top ten journals because the articles from the top ten are high quality and standard to be academic guidance and reference.

The above information is the data bank. It summarizes and records valuable information which enables me to recall any information I need accurately and rapidly in the future.

Through this process, it is found that there are only numbered journals contain the topic about CSR in China. In addition, there is no article about CSR in China’s food industry from the top ten journals (see table 1.1). This is a research gap identified.

The research gap identified is worth to be investigated. After the reform and opening up, China’s food industry has developed rapidly, and its contribution to economic growth has increased year by year. However, due to the low barriers to entry the food industry, the number is large but scale is small and scattered. According to Li, Khalili and Cheng (2018) state, the company and social actions with regard to national conditions and global changes. In the past period, food companies in China have their own problems including low level of management skills, and business ethic consciousness, and lack of effective supervision of regulatory authorities. This results in little research on the CSR of China’s food industry.

Table 1. 1 Number of articles about CSR in China from the top ten journals

Journal Code	AOS	BAR	ABR	JBFA	CPA	AAAJ	CAR	AF	JBE	SEAJ
Number of articles	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	15	2

1

1. AOS: Accounting, Organizations and Society; BAR: British Accounting Review; ABR: Accounting and Business Research; JBFA: Journal of Business Finance and Accounting; CPA: Critical Perspectives on Accounting; AAAJ: Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal; CAR: Contemporary Accounting Research; AF: Accounting Forum; JBE: Journal of Business Ethics; SEAJ: Social and Environmental Accountability Journal.

1.3 Research Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to study the current CSR disclosing level of China's food industry and to explore the motivations and obstacles to conduct CSR practice. In consequence, the research aim to achieve the following three objectives:

1. To undertake a quantitative study by developing a measurement instrument – Scorecard (content analysis) to explore the scale of the current level and situation of CSR of China's food industry;
2. To undertake a qualitative study by in-depth interviews to explore the motivations and challenges to carry out CSR practice and disclose CSR information.
3. To offer practical improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and comprehension of CSR in China's food industry.

1.4 Importance of this research

After the reform and opening-up, it can be seen that the China's food industry are developing rapidly. The development of China's food industry also contribute to the economic growth which is increasing year by year. However, as food companies are in large numbers, small scale, dispersed and less intensive, it is concerned that their quality and safety management ability is relatively low. The lack of ethical standards of merchants, the ineffective supervision from the government departments, the continuous food safety scandals happened in China, have resulted in the loss of public confidence in food companies, and damage of the international reputation in China's food industry. Therefore, the understanding, discussion, study, promotion and development of CSR in China's food industry are of great significance in terms of caring for people's well-being and rights, and the progress of society as a whole (Zhang et al., 2014). Based on this background, this thesis studies the influencing factors of CSR in China's food

industry by following the general idea of finding problems, analysing problems and solving problems. This thesis combines qualitative and quantitative analysis methods, with respect to the theory of stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory and institutional theory, from the perspective of business, government and social analysis to explore the reasons for the lack of CSR and provide practical recommendation to improve the CSR performance in China's food industry (Zuo et al., 2017).

The originality of this research is as below:

1. Applying known research instrument in a new area.

A scorecard used to be applied by managers to measure employee performance, to assess customers for creditworthiness, and to record or summary a sport player's details or statistics (Lawrie and Cobbold, 2004). In this research, the scorecard is the first time to be applied to assess a food company's CSR performance. The approach of scorecard used in this research is consistent as it is used to be. The selection of scorecard items is according to the related CSR reference and regulations. Then the designed scorecard used to assess food companies' CSR reports to receive scores. By analysing the scores from different angles to obtain results. The scorecard design and application will be explained in the chapter of research method.

2. Adding to previously original work

One objective of this thesis is to explore the motivation and challenges by employing in-depth interviews. By interviewing the participants (the interview selections are explained in the chapter of research method), who are Chinese nationalities with different positions can provide ideas from their own visions, while combining with their Chinese culture background. Therefore, the results of CSR behaviour in China's food companies with Chinese

characteristics can be added to previous work.

3. Theoretical significance

Western scholars have carried on the extensive and profound study on the CSR (Moon and Shen, 2010), on this basis, Chinese scholars study combined with the actual situation in China, the meaning of corporate social responsibility accounting information in China's definition, evaluation system and disclosure conducted extensive research and achieved some results, but in view of the enterprise in the industry, the social responsibility accounting measurement, accounting and disclosure content. Especially the present food safety situation is urgent. Chinese people are aware of the social responsibilities a food company need to fulfil. The questions are to identify the weakness of food companies' performance and find the suitable theory and policy to improve the situation. Therefore, through the research on the disclosure level of food companies' social responsibility accounting information, this study aims to make up for the deficiency of relevant theoretical research and provide a theoretical basis for standardizing the disclosure of food company's social responsibility accounting information.

The research on the CSR information disclosure of China's food companies can help food companies to objectively and impartially publicize their social responsibilities in the process of production and operation, to achieve the balance of rights and obligations, and effective in relieving malignant food safety events occurring due to the continuous crisis of confidence caused by food companies, set up the enterprise good social image, improve enterprise's market share and consolidate the status of enterprise in the market, realize win-win situation of the enterprise economic benefit and social benefit. For consumers, it can make consumers effectively evaluate the fulfilment of social responsibility by food companies, which is conducive to better protect the legitimate rights and interests of consumers. Meanwhile, it is

also a useful constraint for enterprises to assume social responsibility. For the government, it can help the government to formulate more targeted macro measures, guide the healthy development of the food industry, establish a fair, reasonable and effective new order of socialist market economy, comply with the requirements of sustainable development in China, and promote the construction of a harmonious society in China.

1.5 Structure of the thesis

The structures and chapters of this thesis are as below.

Chapter 1 introduces the research background and motivations, aims and objectives, methods, the importance of this research and the structure of this thesis.

Chapter 2 reviews the literature in the areas of: (1) definition and introduction of traditional CSR and SCSR; (2) introduction of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSRD); (3) Research context – China; and (4) introduction of food industry and the food industry situation in China; (5) describes the theoretical framework, including Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory and Institutional Theory; (6) a summary of current literature review; and (7) explain the hypotheses development.

Chapter 3 describes the research framework of this study and explains the research methods employed, including (1) Quantitative study– Scorecard (Content analysis); and (2) Qualitative study – In-depth interview (Thematic analysis).

Chapter 4 reports the data analysis results of content analysis – Scorecard from the angles of: 1) company size; 2) disclosure category; 3) comparison of different categories of Food

Company; and 4) report format.

Chapter 5 reports the data analysis results of in-depth interview from the following groups of participants: managers, general employees, government staff and consumers.

Chapter 6 discuss the study findings in the light of research objectives and theoretical framework. In addition, this chapter conclude and summary this thesis. The suggestions of future study are also considered in this chapter.

Chapter 2 – Literature Review

This chapter introduces the literature reviewed to determine the research aims through the following three aspects. Section 2.1 provides definitions of traditional CSR, including its contents and classification and strategic corporate social responsibility (SCSR). Section 2.2 describes corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR D). Section 2.3 explains the research context, China, including the CSR development history in China and the culture with Chinese characteristics. Section 2.4 discusses the research industry, the food industry, including the history of its development and the current situation and challenges of the food industry in China. Section 2.5 describes the theoretical framework, including Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory and Institutional Theory. Section 2.6 includes four hypotheses. Section 2.7 is a summary of this chapter.

2.1 CSR definitions and concepts

This section has three parts. The first part provides the CSR definition – Carroll’s CSR Pyramid – and discusses other CSR concepts. The second part describes the contents of CSR. The third part outlines the CSR contents standards.

2.1.1 Traditional CSR

Refer to Chaffee (2017) and Latapí Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir (2019), the origins of the social component in corporate behaviour can be traced back to the ancient Roman Laws and can CSR originated in the West and was held ethically and also socially accountable by stakeholders including managers, employees, the public, customers, social medias, investors, suppliers, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and many others (Maloni and Brown, 2006). Carroll (1979 and 1991) states that CSR refers to the responsibility of the companies to their stakeholders during their business operations. He proposed a comprehensive definition of CSR, which is known as Carroll's CSR Pyramid. In his view, CSR contains four parts: economic responsibilities, legal responsibilities, ethical responsibilities, and philanthropic responsibilities. The explanation of each responsibility is provided below. This pyramid model shows that the aim of firms are not only to create financial profits for shareholders, but also need to comply with the law, ethical responsibility and charitable responsibility and, in the end, turn into good corporate citizens.

Economic responsibility

It is well know that the primary motivation of a company is to make profit. The business of a company is to provide goods or services to society and the public. Therefore, to process the business, it is necessary to produce a consistent and acceptable profit. Carroll (1991, p.41) states that all other business social responsibilities are “predicated upon the economic responsibility of the firm, because without it the others become moot consideration”.

Legal responsibility

A company or organisation has to consistently act up to the laws and regulations implemented by various local administration and the state where the company or organisation operate its business. To be a successful company, it is essential to be a good corporate citizen and provide

goods and services in a manner that meets the minimal legal requirements.

Ethical responsibility

It is important to be a good corporate citizen and to embrace the standards and norms that can reflect the concern of consumers, employees, community, shareholders and other stakeholders. According to Carroll (1991, p.42), “Ethical responsibilities may be seen as embracing newly emerging values and norms society expects business to meet, even though such values and norms may reflect a higher standard of performance than that currently required by law”.

Philanthropic responsibility

This responsibility includes engaging in acts to promote goodwill or human wellbeing, for example, philanthropic activities to contribute to the local community, education aid or disaster rescue. There is a difference between ethical and philanthropic responsibilities. The philanthropic responsibilities are more voluntary and are not expected in a moral sense.

Many other scholars discuss the concept of CSR. For example, Coldwell (2001) states that at present, the concept of CSR includes all areas of business activities that have impacts on this society. Joyner, Payne and Raiborn (2002) argue that companies undertake different aspects of economic, legal and ethical activities to adjust the expectations and values of this society to protect the health and safety of the environment and living society. To summarise, Mohamed and Sawandi (2007) state that Corporate Social Responsibility is the consecutive work taken by companies and organisations to enhance their ethical cultivation and increase social activities in public, and then contribute to economic growth, sponsor charity events, and improve the employment environment and natural environment.

Anim and Cujoe (2015) note that CSR has traditionally been focused on the economic, legal

and ethical responsibilities but is now more focused on the issue as a strategic tool. The application of CSR is in line with the primary business objective to benefit the business while contributing to society (Lantos, 2001). Furthermore, a company with a good reputation for its CSR can improve its brand reputation and gain a brand image, which is valuable for a company to achieve more profits. Therefore, McWilliams and Siegel (2001) propose that CSR practice usually lead to long-term benefits and should be regarded as a long-term investment that produces financial returns.

The research on CSR in China started relatively late and is mostly based on the Western research. The basic representative points of view are outlined below. Lu (2002) proposes that the large part of a company's CSR activities reflects its moral responsibility. It includes various charitable donation activities to return the profits generated by the company's business activities to society. Chen (2007) states that CSR means that companies have a responsibility to shareholders in the process of production and operation. In the process of obtaining financial benefits, the employer should take the initiative to assume the responsibilities for employees' rights and interests, environment and social welfare. Li and Xiao (2008) put forward the CSR definition needed to meet four standards and to redefine and parse the concept of CSR. They believe that CSR refers to the behaviour of companies to pursue sustainable development of themselves and society; abide by laws and regulations, business rules and social standard; effectively control the company operations effect on stakeholders and the natural environment; and achieve the maximisation of the integrated value of economy, society and environment. From a dynamic perspective, Li (2007) proposes that CSR is the economic, legal, ethical, voluntary charity and other related responsibilities that companies should undertake to their stakeholders in a specific period of social development. In other words, the focus and contents of CSR will be changed depending on various periods with different economic and social

developments. On the basis of comprehensive consideration of China's national conditions and existing domestic and foreign literature, Guo (2011) defines CSR as the subjective action in the process of optimizing companies' own interests to improve social welfare, for example, to improve the quality of goods, increase labour income, improve and protect the natural environment, and distribute income reasonably. Zhou (2011) states that CSR refers to the comprehensive responsibility that companies should bear for stakeholders and the society as a whole to protect and promote the legal rights and interests of stakeholders and benefit the society. Zhang (2013) suggests that CSR is a company's responsibility for its shareholders and stakeholders while pursuing its own development. Companies and organisations voluntarily undertake the social responsibilities and this kind of responsibilities are regarded higher than the legal requirements. Carrying out CSR improves the competitiveness of a company and its long-term development.

2.1.1.1 CSR stakeholders

Cai et al. (2006) state that some people believe that after business companies pay taxes in line with regulations, if they have met their social responsibilities, there is no need to take on other social obligations. If companies are asked to undertake too many social responsibilities and morality, they will find it difficult to grow. This view is regarded as one of the characteristics of oriental companies due to their excessive sense of moral responsibility. They eventually realise that it is difficult to become large companies and they will not be able to afford to further social responsibilities when they reach a certain stage of development. Some people think that companies should first ensure profitable development and operation based on their own conditions, and then consider the social responsibilities to the society and public. There is some truth to these arguments; however, the way of thinking is incomplete. Is a company merely a

machine running mechanically? Is a company humanized? What social responsibilities do companies carry out in a market economy?

Chen (2008) and Zhou and Jiang (2009) state that, undoubtedly, the top priority of a company is innovation and production. A company should become the creator of social material wealth. The main aim of a company is to provide good products and services to the society. Every company is the basic economic pillar for the survival and development of human society. If a company does not show its innovation and production functions, it will lose the basic value of its existence. Therefore, the first duty of a company is to create market benefits and fulfil its economic responsibility to the society.

According to Freeman (1984), Wood (1991), Clarkson (1995), James (2003), Guo and Li (2007) and Zhang (2012), the responsibilities to different CSR stakeholders can be summarised as below:

- (1) Shareholders: to maximise business profit to optimise dividends; to meet the needs of the sustainability environment development.
- (2) Employees: to provide a good working environment and guarantee employee welfare;
- (3) Trade unions: to support the activities to improve employee well-being;
- (4) Supplier: to guarantee timely payment for goods;
- (5) Consumers and agents: to deliver satisfied goods and services;
- (7) Community: to protect local environment; develop local facilities; solve local social problems; contribute to local economic, environment protection and sustainable development;
- (8) Government: to comply with local policies and regulations; obey the law; minimising the impacts on the environment, availability of resources;
- (9) Competitors: to compete fairly and actively;

(10) Non-profit Organisation: to support the charitable activities by providing employment opportunities, financial support to help disabilities, the poor, and other vulnerable group of people, to supervise and promote environmental protection.

2.1.1.2 Classification CSR contents standards

In terms of different standards, the contents of CSR can be divided into different categories. The five broad categories proposed by Kotler and Lee (2005), Lepoutre and Heene (2006) and Banerjee (2007) are described below.

In the first category, subject to the form, CSR is classified into procedural CSR and substantive CSR. The procedural CSR apply to the procedure and process of a company's decision-making. It requires a company's decision-making process has the consideration and reflection of social interests and rights. However, the substantive CSR is the result of a company's decision-making. The company are required to be responsible for social interests and rights.

In the second category, subject to the relationship between a company and its business activities, CSR can be distinguished as relevant social responsibility and irrelevant social responsibility. The relevant social responsibility means that companies have clear attempt to improve the welfare of stakeholders affected by their business activities. The irrelevant social responsibility has nothing to do with the impact of its business activities, but is purely to solve the existing known problems and difficulties in the society

In the third category, subject to incentives and the constrained code of conduct, CSR can be classified into moral responsibility and legal responsibility. The moral responsibility apply to the company's social behaviour, which is supposed to meet the expectation of moral and ethical

values, while the legal responsibility refers to the legal actions that are enforced by law enforcement agencies.

In the fourth category, subject to the result of a company's CSR activities, CSR can be divided into the social responsibility of sacrificing profits and the social responsibility of promoting profits. In other words, it means that some companies conduct CSR activities to enhance their reputation and improve their business performance to generate more financial profits, while other companies achieve their CSR through the consumption of their financial profits.

In the fifth category, subject to the motivation behind the corporate behaviour, CSR can be classified as the social responsibility of the value-oriented attitude and the social responsibility of the instrumentalist attitude. This means that some companies conduct their social responsibilities in terms of their decision makers' attitude and values, while the other companies' decision makers decide on their CSR activities according to the current social need.

2.1.2 Strategic corporate social responsibility (SCSR)

SCSR is a new research area generated by the combination of CSR research and strategic management research. SCSR is a positive strategic behaviour that integrates social problems into the intrinsic core values of a company or an organisation.

The origin of the concept of SCSR can be traced back to Baron (2001), who, from the standpoint of behavioural motivation, uses the term 'strategic corporate social responsibility' to apply to the corporate strategic behaviour of carrying out social responsibility and maximizing profits. Baron (2001) created the phrase 'strategic CSR' and explains that companies link their socially responsible activities that contribute to the society to their product

sales performance. Porter and Kramer (2006) claim that the purpose of a company is not only to seek to create company value and social sharing opportunities by employing strategic CSR, but as social problems can also be solved to obtain the sustainable competitive advantage and satisfy stakeholders, including giving full play to social influences, making companies more integrated into society, and eventually developing companies into social enterprises. Husted and Allen (2007) conducted an analysis of traditional CSR, traditional corporate strategy and SCSR to compare the differences between them. They suggest that SCSR has the following characteristics: to enable stakeholders (e.g. consumers) build awareness of products they received have the value of CSR contained; manage the stakeholder relationship can enhance a company or an organisation's value; take an active part in social activities other than those required by law; and look for current market opportunities to solve social problems. Regarding the concept of SCSR, Yang (2007), a Chinese scholar, believes that SCSR is the strategic behaviour where enterprises take the initiative to assume CSR and influence corporate value from the strategic perspective. Based on the concept of sustainable development, Xu and Liu (2010) constructed a framework integrating CSR and corporate strategic goal management from the perspectives of analysis, design, implementation and control. From Slezak's paper (2020), he also discussed how to embed the CSR concept into strategy and proposed that it is significant to understand which conditions CSR may create value to develop SCSR. The new component of SCSR, the optimisation of value, reinforces Chandler (2016) updated perspective in which the maximisation of profit. Chandler (2016) proposed that companies should aim at optimising value over the long term by focusing on their areas of expertise and by doing so there would be a reorientation of efforts towards the creation of shared value instead of profit maximisation. In other words, SCSR is a new concept that is known to be different from traditional CSR. SCSR is an active strategic behaviour that raises the status of social problems in a company to a new sight and incorporate it into the core value of the company.

2.1.2.1 Research on the theoretical basis of SCSR

The development of Friedman's classical agency theory in economics in 1970 resulted in scholars starting to discuss the CSR theory, then stakeholder theory, organisational economics theory, strategic leadership theory, and many others. Furthermore, research perspectives of scholars on CSR developed from the original ethics opinion that simply serves social 'goodness' to the strategic management perspective that integrates with the corporate mission. SCSR emphasise the relationship between business strategy and social responsibility, and emphasises the function of social responsibility in creating the core competitiveness of enterprises. The theoretical basis is mainly divided into transaction cost theory, corporate resource theory, and strategic management theory.

Firstly, transaction cost theory highlights that the fundamental purpose of an enterprise's existence is to save transaction costs. It argues that in the consideration of short run, the practice of the enterprises to actively fulfil SCSR will result in the increase of transaction costs in the process of strategic decision-making and reduce corporate earnings, whereas in the long run, SCSR will strengthen the corporate reputation and increase the trust between buyers and sellers to reduce transaction costs (Siegel and Vitaliano, 2007). Transaction cost theory, which is based on stakeholder management, assumes that the ultimate target of an enterprise is to gain the satisfaction of its stakeholders. SCSR improves the common utility of the enterprise and stakeholders by saving transaction costs, thus demonstrating the positive impact of SCSR on enterprises and society from the perspective of economics.

The second theory is corporate resource theory. McWilliams and Siegel (2001) state that customers value companies' social feature through their social contribution. They established

the ‘profit maximization’ social responsibility model and suggest that for the benefit of winning in the market competition, companies invest in their CSR performance to gain the public and private good to attract and retain more customers, and stakeholders, including consumers, are willing to pay extra for the added ‘social’ attribute of products (Bagnoli and Watts, 2003). For example, nowadays, more and more food companies (e.g., Hipp, Organix, Ella’s Kitchen, Amy’s Kitchen, Whole Foods Market) produce and sell organic foods to satisfy customers’ demand, and consumers prefer to pay more to buy these organic products for their health. SCSR assumes that management determines the level of enterprise resources allocated to social activities based on cost–benefit analysis, and therefore SCSR has evolved into a resource for implementing product level, business level and enterprise level differentiation strategies. Chinese scholar Zhou (2005) believes that SCSR is the resource guarantee for enterprises to achieve excellent ethics and sustainable development. Modern enterprise contract theory treats enterprises as a collection of contracts with different resources and capabilities. Scarce, imitated and irreplaceable resources of enterprises are the source of enterprises’ competitive advantages. SCSR serves as the guarantee for enterprises’ sustainable development and the source of enterprises’ competitive advantages through the transmission intermediary of excellent ethics.

The third theory is strategic management theory. Moore (1993, p.76), an American scholar, introduced the ‘business ecosystem’ to explain strategic management theory, which considers the balance of the enterprise ecosystem and emphasizes that the enterprises in the system connect unrelated contributors to create a new business model through competition. Chinese scholar Li (2009) believes that CSR is strategic because of its five essential characteristics: visibility, voluntariness, foresight, consistency, and specificity. Scholars worldwide build a new business model through the global strategic perspective. By serving the society, SCSR builds

a bridge to connect different stakeholders, breaks the traditional narrow industry-based strategic design, and develops a new value chain circulation system to maximise profit.

2.1.2.2 Value creation approaches of SCSR

The first approach is that SCSR can generate new business opportunities. In 2006, Porter argues that SCSR should be regarded as far from a cost but is an origin of opportunity, innovation, creation, improvement and competitive advantage. Prahalad (2004) proposed the ‘bottom of the pyramid’ (BOP) market concept. He believes that the BOP market is a huge and neglected market and that enterprises can capture the demand of BOP consumers and create new commercial value while improving their quality of life. Shao and Meng (2011) agree that by means of market innovation, the SCSR can create new business opportunities. Wang et al. (2011) suggest that by way of communication with stakeholders in SCSR practice, enterprises are able to better understand market changes and then they are allowed to seize more business opportunities. Based on the strategic attribute of SCSR, the above studies highlight that while undertaking social responsibility to serve the society, enterprises are capable of meeting the unfulfilled needs of consumers by the means of technology and product innovation and other means and tap new business opportunities with the help of the competitive strategy of market development to obtain excess profits.

The second approach is that SCSR can reduce enterprise risk. SCSR shows that enterprises have realized that both enterprises and society need to flourish. Serving the society involves not only meet the demands and requirements of stakeholders, but also improving the reputation of enterprises, solidifying the relationship between stakeholders and enterprises, and reducing business risks. Donaldson and Preston (1995) argue that corporate social risk source of stakeholders measure the SCSR is regarded as the value of enterprise credibility and that the

practice of the enterprises to actively fulfil SCSR will establish an effective stakeholder communication mechanism and thus reduce corporate social risks. Heslin and Ochoa (2008) suggest that the positive response of consumers to SCSR can result in the increase of product premium and promotion of service sales. The dual effect of product sales and price will lead to the increase of the company's sales revenue, thereby reducing the company's market risk. Liu and Song (2011) state that the concept of fairness in an enterprise would affect the work enthusiasm of employees, and active implementation of SCSR would help enterprises to attract excellent employees, stimulate their sense of mission to achieve corporate goals, and reduce operational risks.

The third approach is that SCSR can reduce financing costs. Heslin and Ochoa (2008) state that financial analysts and investors pay close attention to CSR performance. The Western governments encourage enterprises to publish their CSR reports, which has led investors to invest in companies with a defined SCSR. Moreover, ShoreBank, the first for-profit community development and environmental bank in America, has hired a triple-bottom-line manager to assess the impact of green infrastructure lending from a human, ecological and profit perspective, highlighting the growing concern of human society about environmental management and the tilt of financiers towards socially responsible corporate lending.

2.1.3 Summary – the CSR literature

Carroll (1999) believes that Bowen (1953) initiated the concept of CSR in his book *Social Responsibilities of the Businessman*, while other scholars believe Sheldon (1924) was the first person to use the term 'corporate social responsibility' in his book *The Philosophy of Management*. Since the launch of the CSR concept, it has been discussed and changed with the changing times; the continuous progress of production technology and productivity; the

continuous evolution of social, economic and political structure; and the continuous consumption of natural resources and the deterioration of the natural ecological environment caused by worldwide production. Carroll (2015) called an era of “managing corporate social responsibility” which meant the term CSR become increasingly popular which resulted in its use under many different contexts and addressed to some extent, the responsibilities of businesses with regards to the social concerns of the time.

The concept of CSR is still growing in importance. It is caused by many factors, such as increased social expectations. Companies engage in such activities. Some companies do it voluntarily, some companies they do it for the purpose of increasing profit. There is no doubt, however, that the idea can be beneficial to everyone involved in these actions. Therefore, in order to create benefits for companies, managers need to rethink their CSR activities and plan them in an appropriate way. Relationships between businesses Society is very relevant to the functioning of the economy as a whole. Therefore, the concept of corporate social responsibility can be at the heart of these processes and can also benefit the economy.

To sum up, it can be observed that in recent years there has been a growing interest in and discussion of CSR in China, especially translating it into appropriate strategies that link it to the activities of other companies. The strategic role of CSR is becoming more and more important. Managers need to incorporate the assumption of CSR into corporate strategy. This type of operation can bring benefits to the company, society and nature, so it fits the concept of SCSR. However, it is important to understand and explore the conditions under which CSR can create value. The concept of CSR is very broad and comprehensive, so many can be identified that in order to create value, these aspects need to be interconnected for both society and the company. Therefore, developing CSR strategies and incorporating them into a

company's strategy may be a key step to a company's success. The key CSR literature is summarised in Table 2.1

Table 2. 1 Summary of Key CSR Literature

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Article or Book</i>	<i>Key Contents</i>
Sheldon (1924)	<i>The Philosophy of Management</i>	First to use the term ‘Corporate Social Responsibility’
Bowen (1953)	<i>Social Responsibilities of the Businessman</i>	Should not only achieve economic goals, but also set goals to benefit the society
Ansoff (1965)	<i>Corporate Strategy</i>	Stakeholder concept
Friedman (1970)	<i>The Social Responsibility of Business to Increase its Profit</i>	Shareholder primacy
Davis and Blomstrom (1975)	<i>Business and Society: Environment and Responsibility</i>	CSR refers to the obligation of a company to maintain and increase the overall social welfare while seeking profits
Carroll (1979)	<i>A Three-Dimensional Conceptual Model of Corporate Performance</i>	CSR definition
Freeman (1984)	<i>Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach</i>	Stakeholder theory
Guthrie and Parker (1990)	<i>Corporate Social Disclosure Practice: A Comparative International Analysis</i>	CSR disclosure
Carroll (1991)	<i>The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility: Toward the Moral Management of Organizational Stakeholders</i>	The pyramid of CSR includes economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic responsibilities
Elkington (1994)	<i>Triple Bottom Line Principle</i>	Environmental protection

Baron (2001)	<i>Private Politics, Corporate Social Responsibility and Integrated Strategy</i>	Creates the phrase ‘strategic CSR’
McWilliams and Siegel (2001)	<i>Corporate Social Responsibility: A Theory of the Firm Perspective</i>	Added that customers value companies’ social feature by their social contribution. They established the ‘profit maximization’ social responsibility model
Porter and Kramer (2006)	<i>Strategy and Society: The Link Between Competitive Advantage and Corporate Social Responsibility</i>	A company’s purpose is not only to seek to create company value and social sharing opportunities by employing ‘strategic CSR’
Carroll (2015)	<i>Corporate social responsibility: The centrepiece of competing and complementary frameworks.</i>	Carroll discusses CSR from the centrepiece of competing and complementary frameworks.
Chandler (2016)	<i>Strategic corporate social responsibility</i>	SCRS should be part of the day-to-day operations in order for it to be successful. Companies should aim at optimising value over the long term by focusing on their areas of expertise.
Chaffee (2017)	<i>The origins of corporate social responsibility</i>	Discuss the origins of CSR and introduce a new theory of the firm, collaboration theory. Collaboration theory not only explains how corporations exists, but it also explains why corporations exist.
Latapí Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir (2019)	<i>A literature review of the history and evolution of corporate social responsibility</i>	Focuses on the most relevant academic publications and historical events that have influenced the evolution of CSR as a conceptual paradigm.
Slezak (2020)	<i>From Traditional to Strategic CSR: Systematic Literature Review</i>	To discuss definitions of the CSR, present strategic CSR, exemplify how to embed the CSR concept into strategy and the complexity of the strategic approach to CSR.

In their discussion of CSR, Guthrie and Parker (1989) highlight that BHP Billiton, one of the largest companies in Australia, had started to disclose and publish its contribution to the interests of employees and the development of the community as early as 1885. Moreover, at the same time as the company's CSR disclosure, some European and American companies were starting to build schools, parks, churches, charities and other local infrastructure for the poor. From that time on, the world has been through two industrial revolutions and entered the era of the information revolution and biotech industry. CSR also experienced the germination, definition and different cognitive development periods, such as 'shareholder first', 'stakeholder', 'environmental protection' and 'enterprise code of production movement', until it entered the current stage of development with deepening connotation and expanding extension.

Referring to Carroll's (1999) view and marked by Bowen's (1953) publication of *Social Responsibilities of the Businessman*, the definition period of CSR is from the 1950s to the 1970s. In Bowen's article, he defines CSR as under the guidance of relevant government policies, enterprises should not only achieve economic goals, but also set goals to benefit the society, make corresponding business decisions and take actual actions. Davis and Blomstrom (1975) suggest that CSR refers to companies seeking the benefit while maintaining and increasing the liability of the whole social welfare. Carroll (1979) proposes that CSR includes economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic responsibilities. Enterprises should not only have a responsibility to shareholders, but also bear social responsibilities for other stakeholders.

The concept of shareholder first (also known as profit first) came into being at about the same time as the definition of CSR between the 1950s and the 1970s. The concept suggests that enterprises should not undertake high social responsibilities if they want to achieve quicker

development or they will damage their economic performance. This concept is represented by Friedman's (1970) New York Times article *The Social Responsibility of Business is to Increase its Profit*, in which he argued that only within the scope of laws or ethics can enterprises realise the social responsibility of increasing their own profits.

Since the 1960s, another view has evolved. The stakeholder concept was first proposed by Ansoff (1965) in his book *Corporate Strategy*. With the gradual standardisation of the law and regulations, companies must be recognised by the certain local departments if it wants to be legally registered and persistent to operate its business. Furthermore, the local government and legal departments have the right to close or dissolve companies. Nowadays, if a company wants to be established and grow in society, it needs to be recognized by the government and the society. It no longer only has a responsibility to shareholders. Moreover, profit maximization is no longer the most important goal to a company. Therefore, the managers of the company should make efforts to increase the return on long-term capital. This is an unavoidable way to assume social obligation, and the company should accept the social costs accordingly. In the 1980s, Western economists and management experts stated that enterprises should give attention not only to the growth of economic value, but also to environmental deterioration and social problems. Thus, the cognition of CSR entered the stage of 'environmental protection' and was incorporated into the later 'Triple Bottom Line principle' of CSR (Elkington, 1994).

From the viewpoint of behavioural motivation, Baron (2001) created the term strategic corporate social responsibility to refer to the corporate strategic behaviour of carrying social responsibility and maximizing profits. Baron (2001) explains that companies link their socially responsible activities that contribute to the society to their product sales performance. Porter and Kramer (2006) claim that a company's purpose is not only to seek to create company value

and social sharing opportunities by employing strategic CSR, but also to seek to solve social problems to obtain a sustainable competitive advantage and satisfy stakeholders, including giving full play to social influences, making companies more integrated into society, and eventually developing companies into social enterprises.

In summary, this section aim to provide a historical descriptive on the evolution of CSR as a conceptual paradigm through a literature review of the academic contributions to the concept as well as the most relevant factors that have shaped its understanding and definition. From the literature review that shows the definition and concept of CSR has evolved from being limited to the generation of profits to the belief that companies should focus on managing CSR to meet social expectation of the time. In addition to achieving profits to ensure the interests of invested shareholders, enterprises must be responsible for social laws, ethics, environmental protection, human values and the interests of market consumers. The public constantly classifies and defines the expectations of enterprises' production and operation and their own interests and evolves and innovates over time. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a mutual communication bridge between enterprises' production and operation and their social responsibilities and the, known as corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) introduces as following.

2.2 Corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR)

CSR applies to the process in which companies use distinct methods and technologies to disclose information of their corporate social responsibility status and the impact of social responsibility on corporate financial status and operating results. The CSR system should include six aspects: motivation, objectives, principles, content, mode of disclosure, and disclosure supervision (Jizi et al., 2013).

The motivation for CSRD relates to the reasons for the emergence and continuous development of CSR. From the perspective of the company itself, by disclosing its CSR information, it can indicate that it has complied with the stakeholder community's norms, expectations and contracts. This communication can improve the company's image and reputation, create core competitiveness, and achieve sustainable and harmonious development of the company (Godfrey, Merrill and Hansen, 2009; Gray et al. 1995a).

In the process of the CSRD development, protecting the rights and interests of relevant stakeholders to minimize inefficiencies caused by information asymmetry is always the goal of CSRD. The aim of CSRD is to provide stakeholders with the implementation of CSR through social responsibility information disclosure to assist information users to monitor and evaluate the enterprise and thereby improve the social benefits of the company's economic activities and realize social maximize the net contribution. Its basic purpose is to effectively coordinate the economic and social benefits of the enterprise by providing sufficient and effective information, and therefore the national economy can achieve a healthy operation and sustained healthy development from micro to macro (Healy and Palepu, 2001; Gray, Kouhy and Lavers, 1995a). CSRD's specific content provides useful CSR information to all interested individuals or groups related to the company's business activities by measuring and reporting on the company's performance of various social responsibilities, and therefore they can make correct and effective decisions (Clarke and Sweet, 1999; Cowen, Ferreri and Parker, 1987).

2.2.1 Principles of CSR information disclosure

Garcia-Sanchez and Cuadrado-Ballesteros (2013) and Michelon, Pilonato and Ricceri (2015) propose that to achieve the goal of CSRD, companies are required to construct a CSRD framework in accordance with the principles outlined below.

(1) Sociality

Companies must be required to stand in the perspective of society and CSR information disclosed can facilitate the evaluation of corporate social value, help to monitor the implementation of CSR, and help stakeholders to understand the social costs and social contributions of enterprises' production and operation.

(2) Reliability

The content of social responsibility must be in line with the original goal of the corporate activities and the true situation of companies' CSR practice. All generated accounting data and instructions must have true, reliable and objective characteristics.

(3) Validity

All information is required to be fully reported to information users to ensure that it is comprehensive, and the information cannot cover up negative information to ensure the needs of stakeholders to make their effective decisions.

(4) Consistency

This principle requires that the same model and method for information disclosure should be used in different periods and by different companies. Moreover, the method and content of information disclosure should be consistent. It is not appropriate for it to be changed frequently.

(5) Policy

This principle ask that the disclosure of CSR information should respond to the treatment of social relations between the company and other parties, and must strictly abide by the requirements of relevant national policies and regulations. The company should refer to the relevant standards and appropriately implement social responsibility accounting procedures and methods.

2.3 Research context – China

With the understanding of the definitions of CSR discussed above, it is not easy to define CSR in different countries with different cultures and social behaviour. China is a fast-growing economy nowadays. To remain competitive in the global market, Chinese company owners (executives/shareholders/bosses) realize that they must run their companies by complying with international CSR standards. In other words, they must run their companies socially and environmentally to show that they not only run the companies for profit, but also try to be good citizens.

2.3.1 The three-stage development of CSR in China

Wang and Juslin (2009) identified three-stage development of CSR in China, although Zhao (2014) proposed that the concept of the Western CSR concept was firstly adopted after 1978 when Deng Xiaoping decided to open the country for foreign investors, the core principles of CSR are not new and can be legitimately interpreted within traditional Chinese culture. This section aims to describe a three-stage development of CSR in China (Wang and Juslin, 2009) to take the Chinese reality and culture into consideration (Lam, 2014).

The philosophy of Confucius, founder of Chinese Confucianism, largely influenced the Chinese culture and society (Meng and Liu, 2006). In essence, Confucianism is a kind of moral political philosophy. It involves complex guidance on interpersonal relationships. Primarily, Confucianism relies on two aspects, which are *Ren* and *Li*. Colloquially, *Ren* is known as kindness, compassion, conscience, benevolence and willingness to help others (Warner and Zhu, 2002). Confucianism believes that the essence of human beings is to do good deeds and pursue happiness. According to Liu (1998, p.33) said: “the humane man, desiring to establish himself, seeks to establish others; desiring himself to succeed, helps others to succeed”. *Li* is performed after *Ren*, as *Li* is an acceptable and polite behaviour developed by individuals with

a benevolent heart and wisdom (Liu, 1998). There is a household word in Confucianism, that “What you do not wish for yourself, do not do to others” (Hutton, 2006). This rule can be referred not only to individual persons and other lives, but also to companies. To follow the Confucius’s household work, companies can run their business morally, effectively and profitably by enhancing their companies’ reputations (McMahon, 1986). Although Confucianism contains rich perspectives and thoughts of social responsibilities, it was challenged by the long history of war taking place in neoteric China, the Cultural Revolution during the period 1966–1976, and the introduction of Western culture, values and ideas after reform and opening-up policy in 1978. Therefore, the influence of Confucianism in China has gradually weakened (Rozman, 2002; Chaibone, 2000).

The first stage of CSR is the traditional CSR – Confucianism. In general, the concept of CSR originated from the West. In contrast, the development history of CSR in China is relatively short. However, the core principles of CSR are not completely unfamiliar to China. On the contrary, the core ideas can be traced back to a long history. Confucianism largely shapes Chinese culture and society. Confucian philosophy is based on two primary facets: *Ren* and *Li*, which are discussed above. In 2009, Wang and Juslin claimed that Confucius stated that Confucian traders adopt the Confucian virtue of righteousness – *Yi* – and sincerity – *Xin* – in their business to pursue a harmonious and responsible business relationship. Furthermore, Confucian traders utilize their wealth to help scholars and the poor (Huan, 1st Century BC). They are committed to the pursuit of social prosperity, and pursue benefits with integrity (Huang, 2008).

The second stage of CSR is modern CSR in China. Between the periods from 1949 to the mid-1990s, the Chinese government adopted a centrally planned economic system. The state

government controlled all main sectors of the economy and formulated all decisions of resource allocations and finance distribution. Since 1993, China started to implement economic system reform to build a socialist market-oriented economy. Through this reform, many SOEs have been privatised. Thereby, many private enterprises have been growing rapidly after then. In 2001, China joined the WTO and CSR has attracted increasing attention from the society in China. At this stage, CSR in China showed two notable characteristics. The first characteristic shows that most socially responsible behaviours of firms are government-oriented due to the preponderant influence of the government on the economy in China. The second characteristic reflects that economic responsibility should be regarded as the first social responsibility by companies as economic construction is the primary aim of the government.

The third stage of CSR is the scientific development concept and the construction of a harmonious society. Nowadays, the scientific concept of development and the construction of a harmonious society are the principal political driving force for the development of CSR in China, and the central policy guidance for China's sustainable development and social balance for all. The word 'harmony' is imbued with the spirit of Chinese culture, and harmonious society is the concept of a social system that includes a wide range of aspects. Building a harmonious society involves not only the productive forces and the relations of production, but also the economic foundation and the superstructure. To build a harmonious society, China's government and various organizations need to carry out their social responsibilities. The social organizations include the ruling party and government, enterprises, institutions, civil societies, and urban and rural communities (Li, 2007). Harmonious society is a scientific concept of development with people as the centre; the beneficiaries of building a harmonious society will be all the people in the whole society. Therefore, it is necessary for every unit and individual in the society to make joint efforts and assume the responsibility for building a

harmonious society. Commercial companies, as the universal basic organization of the society, are the important driving force for economic development and have a huge impact on changing society (Steiner and Steiner, 2011).

2.3.2 Awareness of CSR and responses to CSR in China

Pomeroy and Dolnicar (2009) present that Consumers' sense of CSR is primarily related to whether consumers are aware of CSR activities in their actual consumptions. According to Tian et al. (2011) and Singh et al.'s (2008) study, they believe that consumers' awareness of CSR is an exogenous construction, influenced by the social, political, and traditional culture of their living environment, and may vary from country to country. Gao (2009) believes that the CSR concept and development is still in the early stage. Thereby, it is believed that there are many consumers are not fully realised the CSR of a company from the level of morality, philanthropy and ethic (Bala and Yeung, 2009). This lack of awareness inhibits consumers' sensitivity to CSR to a certain extent, which also reflects why consumers do not fully consider whether CSR is in place when evaluating a company's products and services (Maignan, 2001; Smith, 2000). More recently, the stronger consumers' awareness of CSR, the more they understand and require the company to perform CSR (Lee and Shin, 2010). Therefore, it is believed that the higher the consumers' awareness and attention to CSR, the more recognition and positive attitudes they will show to the companies which perform more CSR actively and more willing of purchase intention (PI).

According to information processing theory (IPT), everyone is an information processing system. The human being obtain and process information in their lives and living environment. The procedure is proposed to include: understanding, judgment, reasoning and finally turning into behavior (Miller, 1956). Consequently, in order to understand consumers' responses to

CSR more accurately, companies need to consider not only external results such as PI, but also internal results such as consumers' awareness, attitudes and attributions to understand companies' motivations of engaging and carrying out CSR activities. This is especially important in the face of today's growing business competition in all areas (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004). Tian et al. (2011) explored the overall response and attitude of consumers to CSR in the Chinese market and found that there is a generally positive relationship between CSR and consumers' evaluation of companies (Ricks, 2005; Brown and Dacin, 1997), product association (Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001) and PI (Becker-Olsen et al., 2006; Berens et al., 2005; Carrigan and Attalla, 2001), which supports the recent research proposals in Western countries. According to the empirical research conducted by Singh et al. (2008) and Smith (2000), Chinese consumers' overall low level of awareness of CSR is due to their failure to respond positively to CSR in their daily life. It is noticeable that the study found Chinese consumers pay more attention to the consequences of CSR behaviors rather than the motivations of CSR. This is different from existing studies, which believe that consumers will respond to CSR behaviors based on perceived CSR motivations (Ellen et al., 2006). This result shows that Chinese consumers give more consideration of the results produced when facing the topic of CSR.

2.3.3 Drivers of CSR in China

Although China's economy has developed rapidly in recent years as seen, many issues such as the gap between the rich and the poor, environmental degradation, business ethics, energy shortage, people's livelihood rights and others have also attracted increasing attention from the public. It is believed that some of these problems may be caused by imperfect CSR performance of companies. These problems have also increased the huge pressure on the Chinese government to promote and improve CSR in multiple areas. Therefore, it is worth to

think and discover the driving forces for the development of CSR in China.

The primary driver is **Ethical driver**. As discussed in section 2.3.1 there is a long history of the development of CSR traced back from Confucianism, which has strongly shaped the Chinese culture and moral code (Wang et al., 2007; Murphy and Wang, 2006; Cho and Lee, 2001; Fan, 2000; Laurence et al., 1995). Primarily, Confucianism relies on two aspects, which are *Ren* and *Li*. *Ren* is known as kindness, compassion, conscience, benevolence and willingness to help others (Warner and Zhu, 2002), while *Li* is performed after *Ren*, as *Li* is an acceptable and polite behaviour developed by individuals with a benevolent heart and wisdom (Liu, 1998). Chuang (2007) and Wong et al. (1998) indicate that the contribution made to a harmonious society determines the degree of benevolence and righteousness of this person. This perspective also applies to business activities in China. The commercial profits obtained by enterprises should be based on its contribution to the society (Panget al., 1998). Another core idea in Confucianism is *Yi*. Jensen (2006) proposes that to become an excellent company, its goal is not only to obtain economic profits, but more importantly, to obtain the virtues of *Ren*, *Li*, and *Yi* to contribute to the construction of a harmonious society in all areas.

The second thing to discuss is the **Natural driver**. Today, China is facing the extreme environmental problems and they cannot be ignored. In the last 30 years, although China's economy has developed rapidly, it has also caused huge consumption and damage to China's natural environment (Chan and Welford, 2004). According to estimates in a report published by the World Bank in 2007, China spends 54 billion dollars annually, about 3.5% to 8% of China's annual GDP to manage the environmental problems (e.g. water and air pollution, degradation, garbage disposal problems, soil erosion and etc.) caused by economic development. This also reflects that economic development disregards environmental balance,

which will eventually cause economic consumption and losses (Word Bank, 2007).

China has a large population and huge energy consumption, making it to be the second largest energy consumption country in the world. China is currently facing the challenge of insufficient water resources and other natural energy sources (Li, 2003). According to Chow's (2007) study, the water shortage in China is about 6 million tons annually and imported 162.81 million tons of oil in 2006 to meet the needs. Excessive economic development and waste caused by economic development are the main reasons for energy shortage (Xinhua, 2004). Therefore, it is urgent to solve environmental and energy issues. The 11th Five-year plan are formulated to build a resource-saving and sustainable society in China (Seiji, 2007).

The third important driver is the **Labour driver**. Although China has a large population, the existing problems in the labour force cannot be ignored. Many scholars have found that the labour issues in China include: health and safety issues, the wage level is inconsistent with economic development, unfair employment contracts, social welfare is not sound and others (Zhou, 2006; Nordmann, 2005; Ying et al., 2006; Li and Li, 2005; and Pun, 2003). Nowadays, it is especially import to perfect the labour law, improve the labour environment and working conditions, ensure labour welfare and rights, and guarantee fair labour opportunities to attract and retain employees to develop their potential, which in turn can enhance the competitiveness of companies (CNTAC, 2006).

The fourth driver discussed is the **Legal driver**. Since 1st January 2006, the "Company Law of the People's Republic of China" took effect. This move can be regarded as a legislative stimulus for CSR (NPC, 2005). Incorporating the concept and requirement of CSR into its legal system is one of the important development of this law and changes to the companies in China. Article

5 stipulates that companies should bear social responsibilities, not only to abide by laws and administrative regulations, but also to abide by social expectations and business morality (NPC, 2005). Undoubtedly, the implementation of this law has externally promoted companies' awareness of fulfilling and committing their social responsibilities in China.

Market driver is another noticeable driver. Zhu et al. (2005) believe that the key driver of enhancing CSR performance in China is to increase exports and sales to foreign markets. This is because many developed countries have applied to CSR strict requirements, considerations and rules when import products to their home market, and multinational corporations establish high standards of CSR in their global supply chains. In addition, green trade barriers and labour trade barriers also exert pressure on China's companies. This pressure forces companies in China to strength their competitiveness in order to respond quickly to global market demands, especially in labour-intensive and export-oriented industries.

The last driver to elaborate is the **Political driver**. In China, the current dominant political goal is to establish a harmonious society, firstly proposed at the Fourth Plenary Session of the 16th Central Committee in 2004 (CPC Central Committee, 2004). This require to solve the existing problems of the human and environment, and achieve a balance in the process of social and economic development. At the Third Plenary Session of the 16th Central Committee in autumn 2003, the "Scientific Development" concept is proposed. This concept means "putting people first and aiming at comprehensive, coordinated and sustainable development" (CPC Central Committee, 2003). In practice, CSR is regarded as a part of the scientific development. The ultimate goal of CSR performance in China is to achieve a harmonious society under the effective guidance of the government (Sino-European CSR International Forum, 2005). From this point of view, CSR is inevitable and necessary for all companies in China. In other words,

all companies are liable for performing their social responsibilities and contributing to build a harmonious society.

2.3.4 Corporate Greenwashing in China

The word "greenwashing" is a mixture of the words "green" and "whitewash", which is a symbol of false environmental promotion and whitewashing by enterprises (Bowen, 2014) or to repair their brand reputation and improve their company's public image by promoting their products and companies' aims or policies as environmentally friendly (Ramusand Montiel, 2016; Marquis and Qian, 2014; Laufer, 2003). In the 1990s, influenced by the "green consumption movement" in the United States and other western countries, some enterprises began to carry out green bleaching to cater to consumers. In recent years, under the influence of the society's pursuit of green economy, consumers' preference for green consumption, information asymmetry and insufficient punishment, enterprises' greenwashing phenomenon is very common (Lyon and Montgomery, 2015).

There are many forms of corporate greenwashing, which are summarized by media and academic circles from different perspectives. TerraChoice (2009) summarised seven forms of greenwashing known as the "seven deadly SINS of greenwashing", namely, vagueness, concealment, insufficient evidence, irresponsibility, lying and cheating, avoiding serious matters, worship of certification, etc. In 2011, Southern Weekly also summarized ten manifestations of greenwashing, including blatant deception, intentional concealment, double standards, empty promises, backtracking, policy interference, putting the cart before the horse, distracting, blurred vision, and counterproductive. Lyon and Montgomery (2015) summarized, from the perspective of academic research, selective information disclosure, empty claims and

policies, dubious certification and labeling, false cooperation with NGOs, ineffective public welfare projects, misleading language, misleading images and other greenwashing forms. The concept of greenwashing was first brought to the public's attention in 2009 by Southern Weekly, which has published a ranking of greenwashing for six years in a row. It is reported that Greenwashing is very common in Chinese enterprises.

From the perspective of stakeholders and research country in China, the external driver of greenwash is coming from consumer and investor demand for green products, green services and green enterprises. Faced with the both pressure from consumers and investors, companies tend to actively publicise environmental behavior and performance, especially under the condition of imperfect laws and regulations (Vos, 2009). At the same time, the degree of competition is also an important factor affecting enterprises' greenwashing behavior. The fiercer the competition, the more enterprises need to pursue and claim their environmental protection (Lyon and Montgomery, 2015).

2.4 Research industry – food industry

The food industry today is highly diversified. It is ranged from small, traditional, and family-run activities. And divided into highly labour-intensive to large, capital-intensive and highly mechanized industrial processes. The food industry includes a variety of industrial activities such as food processing, transformation, production, preservation, packaging and transportation (Adams, 1993). In general, the food industry of agriculture, also known as farming, is the process of using the land to plant grain/grow food (World Bank, 2015). Moreover, the food process includes the process of transforming raw food (ingredients) into marketable food products (including drinks) for human consumption (Nestlé, 2013).

Gouk (2012) states that the food industry includes various activities related to food supply, including agricultural and fishery production as well as food production and distribution. It is related to the “food consumption, such as production, harvesting, storing, processing, packaging, transportation, distribution, consumption, and disposal”.

2.4.1 Food industry in China

2018 marks the 40th anniversary of China’s reform and opening up. After 40 years of rapid development, China has become one of the world’s largest producers and consumers of agricultural products and food. In recent decades, China’s food industry has developed from having no market to material abundance, from a single variety to a frequent feature, with a significant increase in product output and many new products, which have filled the gap in the market. There has been an endless stream of food science and technology innovation, which has become a new driving force for industrial transformation and upgrading. In addition, the food industry and safety improvement issues continue to develop towards intelligence, automation, digitisation and networking (Wang et al., 2016; Lin, Zhou and Ma, 2009).

However, the development and changes of China’s food industry are not perfect. According to the *Report of Prospects and Application of Market Strategy Analysis on China’s Food Safety Big Data Industry (2019–2024)*, big data has been applied to every corner of the food safety field, from the establishment of a food traceability system to the application and popularization of the internet of things technology. To achieve the supervision of food production, processing, transportation, packaging, storage and other aspects of quality problems, in theory, it is necessary to achieve comprehensive monitoring of food from farmland to the table. Furthermore, big data is used to provide corresponding changes and an impetus for risk assessment, risk management and risk communication in the process of food safety analysis.

Big data engineering is taken as the starting point to carry out construction of in-depth information on food safety and provide effective engineering and a technical guarantee for the establishment of a long-term mechanism of food safety in China. This shows that the food safety big data in China is small in scale and enterprises' participation is not at a high level.

Due to the close relationship with public health and safety, high social attention, strong correlation with industry influence and many other factors, the social responsibility of food companies in China is particularly important. Behind the rapid economic development in China, the problems of huge resource consumption, environmental damage, quality and safety accidents that occur from time to time, market credit challenges and other development problems become increasingly prominent. To deal with these problems, it is necessary to adjust the direction of economic development and change the pattern of economic development. In recent years, food safety has become one of the topics causing the most concern among the public. Xue and Qu (2016) emphasise that to restore public confidence in food consumption and ensure food safety, it is imperative for food companies to fulfil their social responsibilities.

Guosheng Huang, the President of China Food News Agency, states that taking the lead in the formulation of industry-based CSR evaluation standards and, based on this, carrying out the food CSR evaluation work are mainly based on the four aspects outlined below (Huang, 2015).

The first aspect is the current need. At present, China is in a great era of comprehensively deepening reform and realizing the 'Chinese dream'. It is not only an urgent requirement for the development of a company to be 'actively practicing social responsibility and being an excellent corporate citizen', but also an ardent expectation of the general public.

The second aspect is the need for the development of the food industry. In China, some food companies are large, international and managed in a modern way; however, a huge number of small, scattered food companies lack effective management. On the basis of national standards, the characteristics of the food industry should be integrated to formulate social responsibility evaluation standards for food companies, and then as the main body of the market economy, food companies should be encouraged to fulfil their social responsibilities, which can not only ensure food safety and health, but also promote the comprehensive development of food companies.

The third aspect is the need to ensure food safety. The new Food Safety Law makes it clear that enterprises have the main responsibility for food safety. In recent years, the overall situation of food safety in China has been improving; however, food safety incidents still occur from time to time. To ensure food safety fundamentally, there is an urgent need for food companies to strengthen the construction of good faith and fulfil their social responsibilities.

The final aspect is the need to meet the public expectation. Food is one of the most important things for the people to live. It is not only related to everyone's health, but also to the future of the country and the nation. Chinese people do not only eat food to satisfy their hunger, but also aim to eat well by consuming healthy food. Producing nutritious and healthy food is not only the basic responsibility of food companies, but also the direction of food companies to create their economic benefits.

Huang (2015) states that CSR evaluation in China has entered a stage of rapid development. Statistics from relevant departments show that by the end of 2013, more than 1,500 Chinese companies had issued CSR reports. Many companies have also established social responsibility

departments to coordinate and promote CSR work and integrated it into corporate strategy and daily management.

2.4.2 CSR issues in China's food industry

A summary of the main CSR issues in China's food industry according to Zhang, Li, and Zhang (2004), Shan, Zhang and Wu (2007), Liu and Yang (2009) and PwC (2018) is provided below.

(1) Lack of resources and environmental protection

These are the two biggest challenges that China's agriculture is facing. China has less than 0.1 hectares of arable land per capita, whereas the US has almost 0.5 hectares. With the increase in consumers' income, consumers' diet started to change towards animal products. It is estimated that it takes at least four times as much water to produce the same amount of meat as rice, and even 20 times as much for beef. With the development of animal husbandry and agriculture, the pollution of soil and water caused by excessive fertilizer and industrial pollution has gradually increased.

(2) Food safety management and food fraud loopholes

The Chinese market is highly competitive, and producers and operators of agricultural products and food products often have very thin margins. This pressure from strong competition can cause economic incentives, such as companies/people using cheap, inferior material as substitutes or to use illegal additives to gain the product attribute that determines the price.

(3) Complicated regulatory and enforcement structures

China has a large population, a vast territory and a complex economic situation. With the rapid development of China's economy, it is challenging for the national government to optimize the division of responsibilities among different departments and between national and local government agencies. At the national level, responsibility for food safety and quality is divided among the state administration for market regulation, the National Health Commission and the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs. The Food Safety Law of the PRC focuses on food production and management, while the law on Quality and Safety of Agricultural Products of the PRC focuses on primary agricultural products. In 2015, according to the Food Safety Law, the supervision of food production and trade was assigned to the China Food and Drug Administration, which was comprised into the newly established State Administration for Market Supervision and Regulation.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

CSR disclosure typically involves a public report in which a company provides internal and external stakeholders with a comprehensive picture of its behaviours, activities, and attitudes in terms of economic, environmental, and social aspects. It is of great importance to choose the right theories when studying CSR disclosure, as the theoretical framework influences people's cognition of the concept of CSR disclosure, its motivation, and its changes and differences. Three theories will be used to support this research: *stakeholder theory*, *legitimacy theory*, and *institutional theory*.

In terms of existing literature, most articles related to CSR disclosure are discussed from the perspectives of stakeholder and legitimacy theory; however, a large number of scholars (Fernando and Lawrence, 2014; Brammer et al., 2012; Amran and Devi, 2007; Kim, Amaeshi, Harris, and Suh, 2012; Yang and Rivers, 2009) have recently conducted studies on CSR

disclosure from the perspective of institutional theory. Although more than 30 theories have been summarised for application in CSR disclosure research (e.g., sustainable development theory, agency cost theory, social contract theory), studies have focused on several theories (e.g., stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory) particular (Gray et al., 1995). According to Wangombe (2013), the main theories employed to explain CSR disclosure are stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory, and institutional theory. This chapter aims to conduct a multi-dimensional analysis of the theoretical framework of CSR disclosure from these three theories and examine the connection between them.

2.5.1 Stakeholder theory

The formation of stakeholder theory is attributed to the pioneering work of Freeman (1984), who introduced a stakeholder approach for identifying and modelling the groups that are the stakeholders of the company. This approach describes and recommends ways that managers can appropriately take into account of the interests of various groups. Freeman suggested that managing stakeholders effectively and efficiently is the key fact that determines whether companies win or lose. The stakeholder theory can be summarised as descriptive, instrumental, and normative (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). The descriptive approach mainly focuses on defining the stakeholders of a company. Generally, stakeholders are determined to be the individuals and groups that can influence or are affected by the realisation of the corporate goals. On the basis of this view, shareholders, managers, employees, consumers, suppliers, creditors, governments, communities, the environment, and the public are all stakeholders. The instrumental approach analyses data to identify the connection between management and the traditional corporate goals (such as profit margins and growth rates) and explore whether the application of stakeholder theory to management can result in the same or better performance, to prove the rationality of this theory. The normative approach involves finding a 'normative

core' (or abstract category) for stakeholder theory in order to prove its rationality. Scholars have proposed various normative cores for this purpose; Freeman (1994), for example, proposed the 'Doctrine of Fair Contracts', which advises that stakeholder theory refers to an ethic of care or ecological principles. Donaldson and Dunfee (1999) raised the theory of 'comprehensive social contracts', which holds that the code of conduct is generated from the common goals, ideas, and attitudes of people or society to maintain the moral order of the society. The theory of comprehensive social contracts advocates that the judgment criteria of what is right and wrong and what behaviours are good and evil should vary with different societies. Phillips (2003) put forward the 'Principle of Stakeholder Fairness', which states that whenever an individual or a group of people voluntarily accept or sacrifice to contribute on their participation, the obligations of fairness exist. These theoretical explorations have further developed and improved stakeholder theory.

The core idea of stakeholder theory clearly defines companies as having corporate social responsibilities to stakeholders. It mainly explains the relationship between environmental responsibility and the company (Gray et al., 1996) and analyse the company's balance of conflicts between different stakeholders (Roberts, 1992). It pays attention to how a company should undertake liabilities for its stakeholders' obligations and considers the company as a group based on contractual relationships, the community, and the needs of stakeholders (e.g., shareholders, customers, the community, employees). Though the disclosure of CSR behaviors and activities, the needs of different stakeholders can be effectively and efficiently balanced. It helps the company to achieve a long-term success by maintain a good relationship between the main stakeholders. It is found that the CSR information disclosure level are strongly correlated and significantly influenced by stakeholder power, strategic management, and business performance (Robert 1992). Furthermore, CSR information disclosure was found to be a positive way for companies to manage stakeholders and the organisational environment. In

addition, it results in people realising that CSR information disclosure varies among stakeholders.

In section 2.1.1, Carroll’s CSR pyramid model was introduced. Carroll (1991) stated that CSR has four responsibilities: economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic. In fact, Carroll’s model is equivalent to a stakeholder model. In his model, each type of responsibility corresponds to the connection between the company and different stakeholders as explained below (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2. 1 Connection between Carroll’s CSR pyramid model and stakeholders

Economic responsibility, the most basic social responsibility, requires that the primary purpose of a company is to **gain profit**. Companies must make profits in order to survive and develop; only by making profits can they continue to grow and expand. It is the purpose of the existence of companies, as well as the premise and basis for companies to carry out other social responsibilities. However, different from the narrow view, profits are not only for the benefit of shareholders; on the contrary, they are more about the interesting relationship between companies and shareholders, as well as between employees and the government. First, shareholders invest many human, material, and financial resources to establish a company.

Only when the company is profitable can it attract shareholders to invest in the expansion and reproduction, as well as investors to invest in the company. Second, employees are also indispensable factors for the production and development of companies. The human capital they invest is an inexhaustible driving force for this development. Only by making profits can companies guarantee an income source for employees, retain them, and attract more excellent workers. Finally, governments contribute much to the development of companies by creating a good environment, including the input of land resources. The purpose of companies to gain profits is in line with the government's economic goals. Economic responsibility, therefore, requires companies to undertake their responsibilities to their shareholders, employees, and the government. In particular, companies should strive to achieve the maintenance and appreciation of the assets of shareholders, timely disclose true information to them, and pay them actual investment interests. In addition, it is necessary to actively safeguard the rights and interests of employees, continuously improve their living and working environment, and pay salaries and benefits on time. Furthermore, it is also important to correctly pay taxes to the government on time, actively cooperate with its regulations, and provide it with the necessary human, material, and financial support.

Legal responsibility requires companies to strictly comply with relevant laws, rules and regulations. The legal society requires the company to obtain profits and long-term development through legal operations, and take account into different stakeholders' interests. The development of companies is beneficial to the majority of society members only under this premise. The relationship between companies and stakeholders is contractual, and companies must perform their duties in accordance with the requirements of the contract. If a party goes against these requirements, the damaged party can only seek legal help. This is unfavourable for both parties as it results in too much time, energy, materials, and financial resources being

spent on litigation instead of production, which will only result in a huge waste of resources. Hence, the legal liability requires the company to provide the payment to the supplier on time and repay the money borrowed for the creditor according to the terms of the contract.

Ethical and philanthropic responsibilities are concerned particularly with moral requirements. Ethical responsibilities require that, under the premise of no interest relations and legal constraints, companies are still able to bear more social members' expectations to focus on consumer demand and social needs, rather than just the legal requirements. Consumers have expectations of receiving safe and reliable products and services at a reasonable price, and a perfect after-sales service can be provided by companies. The public also has expectation that profitable companies can contribute and support more to the society. Whereas, these expectations are sometimes ignored as companies focus on pursuing higher economic benefits. Consequently, ethical responsibility requires companies to meet consumers' expectation by providing with satisfied products and services. Furthermore, in the development of companies, they must also consider the impact on the environment, which is often the victim of economic development.

Philanthropic responsibilities are also charitable responsibilities. These involve companies acting as good social citizens that contribute to society, the community, and other stakeholders. Philanthropic responsibilities are non-mandatory and do not come from the public's expectations; instead, they are more dependent on the unilateral willingness of a company. Undertaking charitable responsibilities expands the scope of a company's stakeholders, making its development positive for more social members.

2.5.2 Legitimacy theory

Suchman (1995) states that the Organisational legitimacy is fundamentally worked by Weber and Parsons in 1974. With a vast investigation, Suchman (1995) provides a review of the early literature, defined legitimacy as “a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions” (p. 574).

There are three aspects of legitimacy are presented by Suchman (1995). Firstly, Suchman indicates that “legitimacy is generalised...” it “represents an umbrella evaluation that, to some extent, transcends specific adverse acts or occurrences” (p. 574). From this point of view, it is realised that legitimacy should be long-term behavior, but not a short-term. The second aspect proposed by Suchman (1995) is that “legitimacy is a perception or assumption”, as it “represents a reaction of observers to the organization as they see it” (p. 574). Finally, “legitimacy is socially constructed” as it “reflects a congruence between the behaviors of the legitimated entity and the shared (or assumedly shared) beliefs of some social group” (p. 547). The latter two aspects consider the legitimacy of a company from the perspective of its social relations and practice.

Dowling and Pfeffer (1975) point out that companies “seek to establish congruence between the social values associated with or implied by their activities and the norms of acceptable behavior in the larger social system of which they are a part” (p. 122). Moreover, Pfeffer (1981) added that in order to obtain the greatest support from internal and external stakeholders, the company then actively and positively seeks for the legitimacy. When the value system of the organisation seeking legitimacy is consistent with the social system of seeking legitimacy, the organisational legitimacy is considered to exist.

There are two main approaches in regard of the organisational legitimacy has been discussed. They are strategic approach and institutional approach. The **former considers** that legitimacy can be controlled. The company can make strategic decision and choices by adjusting its business activities, changing its business concepts, improving resources, etc., thereby changing its legitimacy (Aerts and Cormier, 2009, p. 3). Dowling and Pfeffer (1975), Ashforth and Gibbs (1990), and Lindblom (1994) believe that communication is one of the most effective methods. This point of view explains that CSR reports or other social and environment reports are the effective and significant to reveal companies' CSR performance. On the contrary, the **latter – institutional approach** (Meyer and Rowan, 1991) believes that legitimacy is a “set of constitutive beliefs” (Suchman, 1995, p. 576). This perspective dilutes the importance of managers' decision-making power, and the contradictions between companies and members have also been diminished. It believes that managers' decisions are often constrained by the same belief system that audiences respond to (Suchman, 1995). As a result, from the point of Institution approach, the company's communication strategy is not the only focus. Instead, the fundamental structure of the company has a broader background.

Woodward (1996) argued that although both legitimacy and stakeholder theory believe that companies are part of a broader social system, the former regards society as a whole while the latter holds that some groups in society are always more powerful than others. Deegan (2002) stated that legitimacy theory is one of the most likely motivations to explain why companies disclose their CSR information. In addition, its role can be used to explain the management decisions and behaviours of companies. Gray, Owen, and Adams (1996) proposed that legitimacy theory has a stronger explanatory power in terms of CSR information disclosure than stakeholder theory. They believed that the reason why companies survive is that the society companies depend on views the value system they operate as being consistent with

society's value system. The research on the motivation of CSR information disclosure can lead to better analysis of the influencing factors and effects of disclosure. Furthermore, it can also play a better guiding role for information disclosure policymakers and regulatory agencies to improve CSR information disclosure.

Lindblom (1994) argued that legitimacy theory is a dynamic concept. There are a variety of reasons for a company to be viewed as having no legitimacy. With the change of social expectations, corporate behaviours previously accepted may no longer be accepted. Lindblom also defined four strategies for companies to gain or retain legitimacy: (1) inform the relevant public about changes in organisational behaviour, (2) change the perception of the relevant public without actually changing organisational behaviour, (3) manipulate public perception by diverting public attention, or (4) change external expectations of organisational behaviour. Lindblom's paper are widely studied, cited and referenced by researchers of CSR and CSRD. His legitimacy theory is based on strategic perspective, laying a solid foundation to explain how to reasonably disclose CSR information.

Campbell (2003) proposed that among the various CSR theories, the legitimacy theory is the most widely cited and employed. The theory of legality holds that the purpose of the disclosure of CSR information is to prove the legality of the company's behaviour, and voluntary information disclosure is a part of the process of corporate legitimacy. There is a social contract relationship between a company and the society. This relationship is regarded as a contract, which represents the different expectations of the society on the ways of the company's business operations. Campbell (2003) believed that the company will obtain its legitimacy when the value of the company is in line with social expectations and values. Otherwise, the company faces certain threats and crises.

A large number of literature studies (Aerts, 1994; Hopwood 2009; De Villiers and Van Staden, 2006; Deegan and Rankin, 1997) have supported legitimacy theory. Aerts (1994) indicated that in order to prove the legitimacy of the companies' business behaviours and results, the company generally disclose CSR information which has descriptive characteristics. Deegan and Rankin (1997) stated that they believe the survival of a company depends on the attitude of the society. The company must consider whether they are consistent with the social value system when they carry out business activities, otherwise they will be out of touch with social value system, which will cause difficulties in their business activities. CSR disclosure is a mechanism to enable companies to maintain their social, legal status. For example, Hopwood (2009) believed that a company, by disclosing a CSR report, can increase its legitimacy or present a new and different image of itself. CSR information disclosure is a company's business strategy to acquire legitimacy.

In addition, legitimacy theory can reasonably explain that the disclosure of CSR information are influenced by cultural factors (Van der Laan Smith, Adhikari, and Tondkar, 2005). Social expectations vary from country to country, and these differences are influenced by culture (Williams, 1999). The company will disclose CSR information consistent with the comprehensive level of cultural value expectation of the country (De Villiers and Van Staden, 2006).

In the study of legitimacy, many research scholars focus on how companies achieve, maintain, or lose legitimacy and adopt different communication strategies. For example, Lindblom (1994) stated that companies employ four strategic means of legitimacy to narrow the legitimacy gap: informing stakeholders of their true performance, changing the views and opinions of

stakeholders, reducing the focus of the topic, and changing external expectations of performance. Likewise, O'Donovan (1997, 2002) identified that organisations adopt communication strategies to gain legitimacy, such as avoiding topics, changing social values, changing the perception of the organisation, and keeping in line with public values. Cho and Kim (2012) noted that companies obtain legitimacy through image promotion, as well as the avoidance of or deviation from negative or harmful activities in the social environment.

2.5.3 Institutional theory

Scott (1995) and Meyer and Rowan (1997) indicated that for the purpose of survival, organisations must comply with the rules and belief systems that prevail in their environment both structurally and procedurally, will win them legitimacy. Meyer and Rowan (1997) and DiMaggio and Powell (1983) argued that many human behaviours cannot be analysed by rational behaviours. This emphasises that human behaviours are often not driven by utilitarianism but are convergent for reasons of legitimacy or cognition under the pressures of coercion, imitation, and regulation. It is also believed that the choice preference of rational behaviour itself comes from the system, rather than a transcendental and external existence (DiMaggio and Powell, 2011; Steinmo, Thelen, and Longstreth, 1992; Hall and Soskice, 2003). Scott (2001) proposed that institutional theory is a theory on the deeper and more resilient aspects of social structure. In the consideration of the processes, the **social structures including** schemes, rules, norms, and routines to become an authoritative guideline for the society. Scott (2004) also argued that institutional theory is suitable for studying organisational behaviour from the perspective of organisations. Therefore, this theory is appropriate for the study of the social responsibility and sustainable development of companies.

Institutional theory emphasises three levels of cognition. First, from the perspective of

individuals, organisational individuals have a cognitive degree and a judgment level towards the environment. **The educational background and occupational association of managers and individual employees affect their cognitive level and behavioural decision making** (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Second, from the perspective of the organisation, the **organisational culture or criteria can affect the disclosure of CSR information**. Once the disclosure of CSR information has become a routine and repetitive institutionalised affair of the organisation, enterprises will continue to disclose social responsibility information regardless of external pressure (Zucker, 1983). Third, from the perspective of organisations and among organisations, institutional pressure comes from various groups, including not only government agencies and professional organisations, but also interest groups and public opinion (Oliver, 1991). In order to survive, organisations conform to widely accept social norms and behaviours. For the purpose of resources, an organisation will carry out activities with another organisation that controls resources in the external environment in which it is located, thus creating the dependence of one organisation on others.

With the development of institutional change theory, new institutionalist researchers have begun to pay attention to isomorphism (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Deephouse, 1996; Kondra and Hinings, 1998). As an institutional form, its organisation and diversity have always been the focus of many scholars. However, DiMaggio and Powell (1983) believed that modern organisations show great similarity in form and practice, and once the organisational field is formed, a great motivation of homogeneity will be generated. The most appropriate concept for understanding this phenomenon is isomorphism, which refers to the similarities in structure and practice between one organisation and others in the same environment. There are multiple types of isomorphism, including coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

Coercive isomorphism derives from the formal or informal pressure exerted on an organisation by the other organisations on which it depends and the sociocultural expectations of the society. This pressure can be forceful, persuasive, or inviting collusion (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Mizruchi and Fein, 1999). For instance, manufacturers use new pollution control technologies that comply with the requirement of environmental controls. Another example, there are many neighbourhood organisations in urban communities are forced to form organisational hierarchies in order to gain support from higher aid organisations and others. There is a huge impact on CSR information disclosure from rules and various social, economic, political, and institutional pressures, as well as from influential stakeholders such as foreign investors, governments, regulators, non-governmental organisations, the parent company, and other stakeholders of the mandatory mechanism. CSR information disclosure expresses the economic, social, environmental, and ethical values of influential stakeholders, as well as their attention and expectations. Therefore, coercive isomorphism is closely related to stakeholder theory and political influence (Dillard et al., 2004).

Mimetic isomorphism refers to an organisation mimicking the legitimacy or more successful behaviour of another organisation due to the uncertainty of its environment. For example, a company of an industry association may exhibit imitative behaviour and follow or imitate the innovation of other companies with common goals and values to maintain legitimacy and competitive advantages (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

Normative isomorphism refers to the behaviour that is required by the normative expectations of the professional community. In other words, it is mainly derived from the professionalisation; that is, the formal education and legalisation on account of the cognition produced by the university. The development and deepening of the career network which crosses the

organisation and the new model can distribute rapidly (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

To explain practical problems, the Western social sciences rediscovered the status and role of institutional analysis in the 1970s and 1980s. Consequently, the new institutional analysis paradigm are shaped. According to this theory, organisations are embedded in a broad social environment that will put forward institutional requirements and bring institutional pressure to organisations, thus affecting organisational behaviour (Meyer and Rowan, 1977; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). However, the close relationship between institutions and organisations implied by this theory seems to be weakening: On the one hand, existing institutional studies focus too much on institutions and institutional processes themselves, instead of using the institutional perspective to better understand and explain organisations and their behaviours (Greenwood et al., 2014). New institutional theory assumes that, on the other hand, the response of system pressure has the homogeneity, obey the system requirement, organisations will gain legitimacy and key resources needed for their survival and development, leading to organisational behaviour in institutional environment constraints convergence tendency. However, the default assumption is being questioned, because it is often difficult to fully and quickly obey when the system of organisation in the face of multiple competing or conflicting requirements. It is likely to violate the requirements of others while satisfying the requirements of one system (Heimer, 1999).

With the wide application of the new institutionalism theory in sociology, politics, economics, history and other fields, researches related to social responsibility based on the institutional dimension began to try to explore the impact of institutions on CSR from the dimensions of institutional environment and institutional pressure, and put the research focus on the institutional environment of organizational survival. Its core lies in the explanation of

institutional homomorphism and the establishment of institutional norms in the field of organization. The institutional theory holds that the firm is embedded in a series of political and economic systems that can influence the firm behavior and is influenced by the institutional environment embodied in the socially constructed conceptual system and normative system. The institutional environment of an enterprise includes not only the internal policies, management, structure and rules of the organization, but also the external laws and regulations of the organization (Campbell, 2007).

Institutional environment is an important factor affecting CSR activities, including macro institutional conditions such as national level, industrial level and regional level, as well as specific institutional factors such as legal and judicial efficiency, property rights protection, financial system, government regulation and economic development level (Deephouse and Suchman, 2012). The legitimacy theory points out that the existence and operation of an organization need to conform to the legitimacy, which includes conforming to laws, regulations and rules. Suchman (1995) believes that laws and regulations formulated by the government are the most direct and considerable coercive pressure in the behavior of social responsibility and information public disclosure. Campell (2007) points out that under the institutional environment conditions of strong government regulation and more obvious supervision of corporate responsibility by non-profit organizations, enterprises will show better social responsibility performance. China is a government compulsory institutional supply, the way of system supply is often top-down, although there has not been a formal law about CSR, but many laws and regulations include the content of CSR. In 2005, the Company Law of the People's Republic of China clearly stated for the first time that "a company engaged in business activities must be subject to the supervision of the government and the public and bear social responsibilities." The Environmental Protection Law, the Work Safety Law, the Labor Law, the

Product Quality Law, the Food Safety Law and other relevant laws have been promulgated and revised. In order to obtain the system legitimacy and the supply of resources, more CSR information is expected to be disclosed in compliance with laws and regulations.

Discussion on the issue of how organisations respond to institutional complexity can be traced back to the study of Oliver (1991), who identified five strategies for organisations to respond to institutional pressure – acquiescence, compromise, evasion, resistance, and manipulation – and emphasised that what strategies should be chosen depends on the organisational and situational factors, as well as factors related to specific institutional pressures.

In view of the different theoretical basis and research emphases of relevant empirical studies, the definition and measurement of the concept of "legalisation" are also different. For example, empirical studies based on institutional theory focus on judging the "legitimacy" of the market from the perspectives of compulsion, imitativeness and norms (Tan and Wang, 2011). In the research aiming at the issue of enterprise "legitimation", some scholars put forward the concept of "symbolic legitimation", which can be effectively measured using constructs of credibility, organisational professionalism, organisational achievement and stakeholder relationship quality (Oliver, 1991). In addition, some measurement dimensions of strategic acquisition of enterprise legitimacy include improvising activities, resource integration, external network establishment, etc. (Turcan, et al., 2012). At the same time, existing literature also involves some important concepts related to enterprise "legalisation", such as "impression management". Scholars Elsbach and Sutton(1992) combined the institutional theory with the perspective of impression management and proposed the contradiction between institutional consistency and organizational innovation, that is, on the one hand, organizations need to break through the existing institutional constraints to stand out. On the other hand, only by remaining consistent

with the existing system can an organization obtain the legitimacy necessary for its survival. Studies have shown that maintaining institutional consistency with the legalized structure and content itself or abandoning non-legalized behaviors will help enterprises to apply the "impression management" strategy to obtain recognition and support from stakeholders. However, at the same time, Enterprises may also take some "illegitimate actions" to obtain recognition and support of legalized status (Elsbach and Sutton, 1992). In the relevant studies on "legalisation" and "non-legalisation" behaviors, some scholars also point out that "legalisation" is a buffer area of "non-legalisation" (Glynn and Marquis, 2004). Although the above related concepts have attracted the attention of some scholars, the development of the concept of social responsibility based on Chinese enterprises lags behind, especially the definition, construct design and scale development of the relevant concepts of "legalisation", "non-legalisation", "de-legalisation" and "re-legalisation" of food companies still need to be further expanded.

Decoupling is a structure-oriented response strategy proposed by existing studies. It refers to the conscious separation of the legitimation-related organisational structure and the organisational practices related to the promotion of efficiency. Therefore, the decoupling strategy means that the organisation only gives ceremonial or symbolic commitment to the specific institutional logic and requirements, while still retaining its own core cognition (Boxenbaum and Jonsson, 2008). This is a common strategy adopted by organisations to coordinate conflicting institutional requirements, assist in hiding non-compliance behind surface compliance to a certain extent, and help in alleviating the pressure caused by the external institutional environment so that the organisation can achieve both legitimacy and efficiency. Despite the risk of losing legitimacy when decoupling behaviour is discovered, decoupling is often critical to organisational success, especially when organisations are faced

with high resource scarcity and heavy reliance on external institutions that control land, capital, manpower, and supply channels. However, Maclean and Behnam (2010) demonstrate the dangers of decoupling an organizational compliance program from the core business activities of an organization. They illustrate how decoupling created a “legitimacy facade” that enabled the institutionalization of misconduct and precipitated a loss of external legitimacy. At present, the occurrence mechanism, behaviour motivation, evolution process, behaviour result, and relationship with the organisational field of decoupling are still the focus of the theoretical circle (Greenwood et al., 2011).

From the perspective of this theory, social responsibility is a contractual obligation of a company to the society. First, companies are allowed to use natural resources and human resources by society and are also given the right to engage in productive activities and obtain the status of power. Hence, the intangible contract between the society and the companies asserts that society has the right to control and guide companies. As an integrated part of the social system and the carriers of a comprehensive social contract consisting of explicit and implicit contracts between stakeholders, companies are responsible not only to shareholders but also to other stakeholders who contribute to their success (Greenwood et al., 2014).

Second, from the perspective of performance, Gao (2013) divided the impact of companies on their micro-environment into three types of performance – economic, environmental and social – according to the three pillars of sustainable development identified by the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1986. This perspective mainly measures the performance caused by the CSR activities of companies, particularly in terms of social performance.

Third, Frances (2006) claimed that in accordance with the recipients, CSR behaviours have four aspects: social/community, employees, suppliers, and customers. Ruth et al. (2007)

proposed a multi-level theoretical model to explain the source of the CSR behaviours. They believed that in each level (individual, organisations, counties, and countries), the participants and interest groups have three main incentives to promote that companies carry out their CSR. The first incentive is the means, such as self-interest. The second is the relationship; for example, considering the relationship between the group's members. The third incentive is moral; for example, considering the ethical standards and code of ethics.

Over the years, the application of institutional theory in the study of CSR disclosure has been increasing. Adams and McNicholas (2007) held that, in the comparison of institutional theory and legitimacy theory, the latter can better explain the disclosure of CSR information. Furthermore, in some cases, the CSR report is the result of a more general social environment or the institutionalisation of consciousness (Aguilera et al., 2007). Institutional theory has great potential to explain the disclosure of CSR information (Rowe and Wehrmeyer, 2001) and provide a multi-level theoretical perspective to explain the internal and external behaviours of organisations (Milne and Patten, 2002). Kraatz and Flores (2015) proposed that an organisation has come to be seen as embodying key societal values and Institutional theory attends considers the processes by which structures, including schemas, rules norms and routines, become established as authoritative guidelines for social behaviour (David, Tolbert and Boghossian, 2019). In the light of understanding how an organisation reacts to changing social and institutional pressures and expectations to maintain its legitimacy, institutional theory is the best alternative to legitimacy and stakeholder theory (Deegan and Unerman, 2006).

2.6 Summary of current literature review

From the previous subsections, there are many scholars who contribute to the concept of CSR. A comprehensive definition of CSR, which is known as Carroll's CSR Pyramid is worth noting.

In his view, CSR includes four parts: economic responsibilities, legal responsibilities, ethical responsibilities, and philanthropic responsibilities.

In 2001, Baron creates the phrase “strategic CSR” (SCSR) and explains that companies link their socially responsible activities which contribute to the society to their product sales performance. SCSR is a new concept and an active strategic behavior, which elevates the status of social issues in the company to a new height and brings them into the inner core value of a company.

CSRD applies to the process in which companies use distinct methods and technologies to disclose information of their corporate social responsibility status and the impact of social responsibility on corporate financial status and operating results. The CSRD system should include six aspects: motivation, objectives, principles, content, mode of disclosure, and disclosure supervision (Jizi, Salama, Dixon and Stratling, 2013). The motivation for CSRD refers to the reasons for the emergence and continuous development of its CSR. From the perspective of the company itself, by disclosing its CSR information, it can indicate that it has complied with the stakeholder community’s norms, expectations and contracts.

China is a fast-growing economy nowadays. In order to keep competitive in the global market, the management of a company in China realises that they must run their companies by complying with international CSR standards. In other words, they must run their companies socially and environmentally to show they do not only run for profit but also try to be good citizens. The CSR is not new in China, a three-stage development of CSR in China was detailed above. They are **Traditional CSR-Confucianism, Modern CSR and Scientific Development Concept and the Construction of a Harmonious Society**. However, Gao (2009) believes

that the CSR concept and development is still in the early stage. Thereby, it is believed that there are many consumers are not fully realised the CSR of a company from the level of morality, philanthropy and ethic (Bala and Yeung, 2009). This lack of awareness inhibits consumers' sensitivity to CSR to a certain extent, which also reflects why consumers do not fully consider whether CSR is in place when evaluating a company's products and services (Maignan, 2001; Smith, 2000).

Six drivers (natural driver, labour driver, legal driver, market drivers, political driver, and ethical driver) of CSR in China are discussed above. In summary, the drivers of CSR in China are regarded as initiative and passive drivers refer to the traditional Chinese culture, social environment and social demands that actively drive companies to implement and carry out CSR in China.

Both legitimacy and stakeholder theory assume that companies can influence other social organisations through their relevant disclosure information. Organisations are part of a broader social system that affects and is affected by other organisations within the social system. The question of how organisation, structure, culture, norm, and custom constitute social behaviour are come up by the institutional theory. Each of these three theories points out the external pressure of the organisation and notes that the existence of the organisation is influenced by the cognition of the external environment.

However, different theories have their own understanding of the definition of external pressure and management measures. According to stakeholder theory, external pressure comes from the stakeholders who influence the organisation and are also affected by the organisation at the same time. These stakeholders have the power, legitimacy, and importance of prominence that

affect the organisation (Mitchell et al., 1997). For legitimacy theory, external pressure refers to the relevant social public that influences the organisation through resource supply and social recognition and recognise the demand differences of different stakeholders on the basis of the macro concept. Institutional theory instead defines external pressure as the institutional pressure that promotes the convergence of organisations (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Scott, 1991) and influences corporate behaviour through three institutional mechanisms: coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism.

In spite of the different understanding of these theories, they are closely related to each other. Legitimacy and stakeholder theory are derived from sociopolitical theory, which recognises the relevance between an organisation and its operating environment. There is a contractual relationship between the companies and the society and companies are regarded to be an integral part of society (Patten, 1992). Furthermore, stakeholder theory is a continuation of legitimacy theory. It does not only consider the entire society, but also focuses on specific interest groups. The two theories overlap in certain ways (Deegan, 2006). In addition, legitimacy theory comes from institutional theory and social and economic research. Only by following the surrounding institutional environment can an organisation gain legitimacy, resources, stability, and survival prospects. Milne and Patten (2002) believed that rather than a strategy, the legitimacy is also an institution in essence. It is the process of coordination between an organisation and its institutional environment.

Legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, and institutional theory constitute the basic theories in the research literature on CSR information disclosure. Each theory has its unique research angle, theoretical logic, and important status, as well as a large number of empirical studies supporting its research views. However, no single theory can completely replace the other theories as the

sole research purpose. Because CSR information disclosure is multi-faceted, it is difficult to fully explain the complex CSR by relying solely on one theory or one method. Islam and Deegan (2008) agreed that in the comparison of considering a single theory, the combination of stakeholder, legitimacy, and institutional theory can provide a stable foundation for comprehensively understanding and interpreting CSR information.

Three CSR issues in China's food industry are indicated. First, lack of resources and environmental protection. Second, food safety management and food fraud loopholes. Third, complicate regulatory and enforcement structures. The previous subsections form the basis for the four hypotheses.

In summary, through the extensive and intensive review of top ten journals in the areas of CSR in China's food companies, it is found that there are only numbered journals contain the topic about CSR in China. In addition, there is no article about CSR in China's food industry from the top ten journals (see table 1.1). This is a research gap identified.

The research gap identified is worth to be investigated. After the reform and opening up, China's food industry has developed rapidly, and its contribution to economic growth has increased year by year. However, due to the low barriers to entry the food industry, the number is large but scale is small and scattered. According to Li, Khalili and Cheng (2018) state, the company and social actions with regard to national conditions and global changes. In the past period, food companies in China have their own problems including low level of management skills, and business ethic consciousness, and lack of effective supervision of regulatory authorities. This results in little research on the CSR of China's food industry.

This current literature review discusses the western CSR concept and the three-stage development of CSR in China to contribute the definition of CSR, called the Harmony Approach (Wang and Juslin, 2009) which is recognised by previous President Mr. Hu as a society “*that is democratic and ruled by law, fair and just, trustworthy and fraternal, full of vitality, stable and orderly, and maintains harmony between man and nature*” (Lam, 2014). In spite of many problems caused by pervasive corruption, product safety scandals or environmental issues that are slowing down a process of enforcement, CSR became an essential characteristic of business management strategy in China.

It can be observed that in recent years there has been a growing interest in and discussion of CSR in China, especially translating it into appropriate strategies that link it to the activities of other companies. The strategic role of CSR is becoming more and more important. Managers need to incorporate the assumption of CSR into corporate strategy. This type of operation can bring benefits to the company, society and nature, so it fits the concept of SCSR. However, it is important to understand and explore the conditions under which CSR can create value. The concept of CSR is very broad and comprehensive, so many can be identified that in order to create value, these aspects need to be interconnected for both society and the company. Therefore, developing CSR strategies and incorporating them into a company's strategy may be a key step to a company's success and also how the food companies in China develop their CSR on the basis of stakeholder, legitimacy and institutional theories to meet each requirements and needs are meaningful to be investigated.

The contributions of this research are as below:

1. Applying known research instrument in a new area.

A scorecard used to be applied by managers to measure employee performance, to assess customers for creditworthiness, and to record or summary a sport player's details or statistics (Lawrie and Cobbold, 2004). In this research, the scorecard is the first time to be applied to assess a food company's CSR performance. The approach of scorecard used in this research is consistent as it is used to be. The selection of scorecard items is according to the related CSR reference and regulations. Then the designed scorecard used to assess food companies' CSR reports to receive scores. By analysing the scores from different angles to obtain results. The scorecard design and application will be explained in the chapter of research method.

2. Adding to previously original work

One objective of this thesis is to explore the motivation and challenges by employing in-depth interviews. By interviewing the participants (the interview selections are explained in the chapter of research method), who are Chinese nationalities with different positions can provide ideas from their own visions, while combining with their Chinese culture background. Therefore, the results of CSR behaviour in China's food companies with Chinese characteristics can be added to previous work.

3. Theoretical significance

Western scholars have carried on the extensive and profound study on the CSR (Moon and Shen, 2010), on this basis, Chinese scholars study combined with the actual situation in China, the meaning of corporate social responsibility accounting information in China's definition, evaluation system and disclosure conducted extensive research and achieved some results, but in view of the enterprise in the industry, the social responsibility accounting measurement, accounting and disclosure content. Especially the present food safety situation is urgent. Chinese people are aware of the social responsibilities a food company need to fulfil. The

questions are to identify the weakness of food companies' performance and find the suitable theory and policy to improve the situation. Therefore, through the research on the disclosure level of food companies' social responsibility accounting information, this study aims to make up for the deficiency of relevant theoretical research and provide a theoretical basis for standardizing the disclosure of food company's social responsibility accounting information.

The research on the CSR information disclosure of China's food companies can help food companies to objectively and impartially publicize their social responsibilities in the process of production and operation, to achieve the balance of rights and obligations, and effective in relieving malignant food safety events occurring due to the continuous crisis of confidence caused by food companies, set up the enterprise good social image, improve enterprise's market share and consolidate the status of enterprise in the market, realize win-win situation of the enterprise economic benefit and social benefit. For consumers, it can make consumers effectively evaluate the fulfilment of social responsibility by food companies, which is conducive to better protect the legitimate rights and interests of consumers. Meanwhile, it is also a useful constraint for enterprises to assume social responsibility. For the government, it can help the government to formulate more targeted macro measures, guide the healthy development of the food industry, establish a fair, reasonable and effective new order of socialist market economy, comply with the requirements of sustainable development in China, and promote the construction of a harmonious society in China.

2.7 Hypotheses development

The previous subsections introduced and discussed existing literatures, research context of China, the food companies in China, as well as the theoretical framework. They form the basis for the hypotheses of this research. In this section, four hypotheses are developed.

In China, some food companies are large, international and managed in a modern way; however, a huge number of small, scattered food companies lack effective management. On the basis of national standards, the characteristics of the food industry should be integrated to formulate social responsibility evaluation standards for food companies, and then as the main body of the market economy, food companies should be encouraged to fulfil their social responsibilities.

Refer to the Institutional theory, it emphasises three levels of cognition. First, from the perspective of individuals, organisational individuals have a cognitive degree and a judgment level towards the environment. The educational background and occupational association of managers and individual employees affect their cognitive level and behavioural decision making (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Second, from the perspective of the organisation, the organisational culture or criteria can affect the disclosure of CSR information. Once the disclosure of CSR information has become a routine and repetitive institutionalised affair of the organisation, enterprises will continue to disclose social responsibility information regardless of external pressure (Zucker, 1983). Third, from the perspective of organisations and among organisations, institutional pressure comes from various groups, including not only government agencies and professional organisations, but also interest groups and public opinion (Oliver, 1991). In order to survive, organisations conform to widely accept social norms and behaviours. For the purpose of resources, an organisation will carry out activities with another organisation that controls resources in the external environment in which it is located, thus creating the dependence of one organisation on others.

As explained previously, there are a large volume of food companies in China but their specifications vary. In light of Duff (2014)'s paper to access CSR in accountancy firm by

analysing of mean number of disclosures by firm size, the first hypothesis is generated that larger companies in food industry have a significantly higher CSR performance compared to smaller companies. It is worth to find out if larger company has the more organisational culture or criteria can affect the level of CSR discourse. This brings the first research hypothesis. The T-test and non-parametric test will be applied to test this first hypothesis.

H1: Larger companies have a significantly higher CSR performance compared to smaller companies as measured by the mean value on the scorecard.

Refer to legitimacy theory, Dowling and Pfeffer (1975) point out that companies “seek to establish congruence between the social values associated with or implied by their activities and the norms of acceptable behavior in the larger social system of which they are a part” (p. 122). Moreover, Pfeffer (1981) added that in order to obtain the greatest support from internal and external stakeholders, the company then actively and positively seeks for the legitimacy. There are two main approaches in regard of the organisational legitimacy has been discussed. They are strategic approach and institutional approach. The former considers that legitimacy can be controlled. The company can make strategic decision and choices by adjusting its business activities, changing its business concepts, improving resources, etc., thereby changing its legitimacy (Aerts and Cormier, 2009, p. 3). Dowling and Pfeffer (1975), Ashforth and Gibbs (1990), and Lindblom (1994) believe that communication is one of the most effective methods. This point of view explains that CSR reports or other social and environment reports are the effective and significant to reveal companies’ CSR performance. On the contrary, the latter – institutional approach (Meyer and Rowan, 1991) believes that legitimacy is a “set of constitutive beliefs” (Suchman, 1995, p. 576). This perspective dilutes the importance of managers’ decision-making power, and the contradictions between companies and members

have also been diminished. It believes that managers' decisions are often constrained by the same belief system that audiences respond to (Suchman, 1995). As a result, from the point of Institution approach, the company's communication strategy is not the only focus. Instead, the fundamental structure of the company has a broader background.

In terms of legal driver, since 1st January 2006, the "Company Law of the People's Republic of China" took effect. This move can be regarded as a legislative stimulus for CSR (NPC, 2005). Incorporating the concept and requirement of CSR into its legal system is one of the important development of this law and changes to the companies in China. Article 5 stipulates that companies should bear social responsibilities, not only to abide by laws and administrative regulations, but also to abide by social expectations and business morality (NPC, 2005). Undoubtedly, the implementation of this law has externally promoted companies' awareness of fulfilling and committing their social responsibilities in China.

In addition, in the consideration of ethical and philanthropic elements from Stakeholder theory, companies are still able to bear more social members' expectations to focus on consumer demand and social needs, rather than just the legal requirements. Confucian philosophy proposes *Ren* and *Li*. *Ren* is known as kindness, compassion, conscience, benevolence and willingness to help others (Warner and Zhu, 2002). *Li* is performed after *Ren*, as *Li* is an acceptable and polite behaviour developed by individuals with a benevolent heart and wisdom (Liu, 1998). There is a household word in Confucianism, that "*What you do not wish for yourself, do not do to others*" (Hutton, 2006). This rule can be referred not only to individual persons and other lives, but also to companies. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Food companies which are considered to have more responsibilities to the customers

will lead to more CSR practice and show their higher CSR concerns.

Pomeroy and Dolnicar (2009) present that Consumers' sense of CSR is primarily related to whether consumers are aware of CSR activities in their actual consumptions. According to Tian et al. (2011) and Singh et al.'s (2008) study, they believe that consumers' awareness of CSR is an exogenous construction, influenced by the social, political, and traditional culture of their living environment, and may vary from country to country. Gao (2009) believes that the CSR concept and development is still in the early stage. Thereby, it is believed that there are many consumers are not fully realised the CSR of a company from the level of morality, philanthropy and ethic (Bala and Yeung, 2009). This lack of awareness inhibits consumers' sensitivity to CSR to a certain extent, which also reflects why consumers do not fully consider whether CSR is in place when evaluating a company's products and services (Maignan, 2001; Smith, 2000).

According to the empirical research conducted by Singh et al. (2008) and Smith (2000), Chinese consumers' overall low level of awareness of CSR is due to their failure to respond positively to CSR in their daily life. It is noticeable that the study found Chinese consumers pay more attention to the consequences of CSR behaviors rather than the motivations of CSR. The interviews with participants can further explore this phenomenon when this hypothesis is proved to be true. This brings to the hypothesis 3:

H3: All participants will have a low level of CSR awareness and their knowledge of CSR will not be comprehensive.

According to information processing theory, everyone is an information processing system. The human being obtain and process information in their lives and living environment. The

procedure is proposed to include: understanding, judgment, reasoning and finally turning into behavior (Miller, 1956). Consumers' awareness of CSR mainly discusses whether consumers are aware of CSR activities in real consumptions. This is especially important in the face of today's growing business competition in all areas (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004). Tian et al. (2011) explored the overall response and attitude of consumers to CSR in the Chinese market and found that there is a generally positive relationship between CSR and consumers' evaluation of companies (Ricks, 2005; Brown and Dacin, 1997), and product association (Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001) and purchase intention (Becker-Olsen et al., 2006; Berens et al., 2005; Carrigan and Attalla, 2001), which supports the recent research proposals in Western countries. According to the empirical research conducted by Singh et al. (2008) and Smith (2000), Chinese consumers' overall low level of awareness of CSR is due to their failure to respond positively to CSR in their daily life. It is noticeable that the study found Chinese consumers pay more attention to the consequences of CSR behaviors rather than the motivations of CSR. This is different from existing studies, which believe that consumers will respond to CSR behaviors based on perceived CSR motivations (Ellen et al., 2006). This result shows that Chinese consumers give more consideration of the results produced when facing the topic of CSR. This phenomenon extends to different groups of CSR stakeholders and results in the following hypothesis 4:

H4: The CSR information that each group is concerned with will be closely related to their own interests and subjected to personal perception and knowledge.

Hypotheses are proposed explanation for phenomenon, and help to provide link to theories and research questions (Bulajic et al, 2012). By comparing and understanding the differences in CSR performance between large companies and small companies (H1), understanding the

differences in CSR performance of companies producing specific products (H2) and understand the level of CSR awareness of people in the study country (H3 and H4), so that to further analyse and explain the phenomenon, to meet the research objectives, and find and improve the issues.

Chapter 3 Methods

In this chapter, the research methods used in this study are introduced and explained. There are four main sections: research methods introduction (section 3.1), research framework (section 3.2), quantitative research (content analysis - Scorecard) (section 3.3) and qualitative research (thematic analysis - Interviews) (section 3.4).

The overall structure of this chapter is as follows. Section 3.1 introduces mixed-method research and describes six types of research design and analyses the one this study employs, while section 3.2 introduces the framework for the current research and explains how the research objectives can be achieved by employing the appropriate research methods. This section also includes a timetable for the field research. Section 3.3 explains the content analysis method used in the current research and describes the development of the research instrument (scorecards), the sample selection, the data analysis techniques and the hypotheses discussed in Chapter 2. Finally, section 3.4 explains how thematic analysis was used to examine the results of the semi-structured interviews and outlines how the interviews were conducted, what the interview guidelines were, the computer software used for the qualitative data analysis (NVivo), and the hypothesis discussed in Chapter 2.

3.1 Mixed Methods

3.1.1 Introduction

This study uses a mixed-method approach which includes both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Two forms of data were collected: quantitative data generated from five-year CSR reports and qualitative data from semi-structured interviews.

According to Hossler and Vesper (1993), a mixed-methods approach can be called a ‘concurrent triangulation method design’. Moreover, Creswell, Clark et al. (2003, p. 210) further described as “triangulation of data collection, separate data analysis, and the integration of databases at the interpretation or discussion stage of the report”. According to the current literature, this approach can also be explained as a multi-method design combining qualitative and quantitative data (Bryman, 1988; Creswell, 1994; Miles and Huberman, 1994), mixed-methods research integrating qualitative and quantitative approaches (Greene et al., 1989; Glik et al., 1986; Steckler et al., 1992),) and multitrait-multimethod research (Fielding and Fielding, 1986; Campbell and Fiske, 1959). From combining all of these studies, a suggested definition of ‘mixed research methods’ based on a combination of all of these is as follows:

A mixed methods study involves the collection or analysis of both quantitative and/or qualitative data in a single study in which the data are collected concurrently or sequentially, are given a priority, and involve the integration of the data at one or more stages in the process of research (Creswell et al., 2003, p. 212).

As both qualitative and quantitative methods have limitations, combining them can help address some of their disadvantages (Jick, 1979). In addition, although qualitative research methods have become a popular and legitimate form of social science research and contribute valuable contextualised information, the social phenomena these methods look at tend to be complex and multi-layered (Greene and Caracelli, 1997). Therefore, a mixed methods approach is needed to understand these complexities and strengthen the research results (Greene and Caracelli, 1997). For example, Bayoud, Kavanage and Slaughter (2012) explored the factors influencing levels of CSR in Libyan firms by conducting a regression analysis on 40 annual reports and also interviewed 31 financial managers and information managers to examine their opinions of the determinants of CSR.

3.1.2 Types of Research Design

Creswell et al. (2003) described six types of major research designs that differ according to their implementation, priority, integration and theoretical perspective. A sequential explanatory design has two phases. The first phase is to collect and analyse the quantitative data, and then followed by the collection and analysis of qualitative data. The intention of this design is to use the results of the qualitative research to further explain the results of the quantitative research; however, it is not clear how to move from the first phase of data collection and analysis to the second phase.

Similarly, a sequential exploratory design also has two phases, but the qualitative data is collected and analysed first followed by the quantitative data. In general, this design is used to develop instruments (e.g. surveys), to develop a classification for testing or to identify variables (Bergman, 2008). In contrast, in a sequential transformative design, the researchers are allowed to determine which type of data is collected first (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007).

A concurrent triangulation design is the most well-known design and is where both types of data are collected at the same time. In other words, the two types of data are seen as equal. Researchers tend to use this design to cross-validate or confirm findings (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004), and Morgan (1998) and Creswell (2007) suggested that researchers apply this design by analysing the different types of data separately and then comparing and/or combining them. This design has three main advantages. First, it is familiar to most researchers, which means it is easy to apply well and has certified findings (Creswell, 2007). Second, the weaknesses of one method can be minimised by the strengths of the other (Sale, Lohfeld and Brazie, 2002; and Creswell, 2013). Third, it can expand quantitative data through the collection

of open-ended qualitative data (Creswell, 2007). This design also has two main limitations, however. First, it is difficult for researchers to compare results due to the combination of the two different forms of data. Second, a lot of extra work and specific knowledge might be needed to properly study a phenomenon (Creswell, 2007; Creswell and Clark 2007; Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007).

Concurrent nested design is also known as concurrent embedded design. This is a one-phase design where priority is given to one approach and the other is embedded or nested into the project and provides a supporting role (Creswell, 2007). This design is useful for enriching one type of data with another one (Morse, 1991). It has also been described as a multilevel design by Tashakkori and Teddie (1998). One advantage of this design is that it enables researchers to gain different perspectives of the findings by using two types of data. It also has limitations, however. For example, the data needs to be transformed so it can be used in the analysis, which can lead to discrepancies between the two types. Also, priority is given to one type of data, which could impact the interpretation of the findings.

A concurrent transformative design involves collecting both types of data (quantitative and qualitative) at the same time. Theoretical perspectives are used to guide the design, such as participatory research and critical theory, and its purpose is to examine the perspectives at different levels of analysis (Creswell, 2013).

The current study used a concurrent triangulation design where quantitative data and qualitative data are collected separately. The priority of the two types of data were considered to be of equal priority. At the end, the interpretation of the results was integrated. The research method and progress are explained in detail below.

3.2 Research Framework

As described in Chapter 1, the current research aimed to study the current CSR disclosing level of China's food industry and to explore the motivations and obstacles to conduct CSR practice.

In consequence, the research aim to achieve the following three objectives:

1. To undertake a quantitative study by developing a measurement instrument – Scorecard (content analysis) to explore the scale of the current level and situation of CSR of China's food industry;
2. To undertake a qualitative study by in-depth interviews to explore the motivations and challenges to carry out CSR practice and disclose CSR information.
3. To offer practical improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and comprehension of CSR in China's food industry.

To achieve these three objectives, this research used both quantitative and qualitative research. Mixed methods are applied when the research involves collecting, analysing and integrating quantitative and qualitative research (Creamer, 2017). By mixing both quantitative and qualitative research data, the author is able to obtain a better and broader understanding of the research objectives (Creswell and Clarks, 2011).

Quantitative research is concerned with discovering facts about social phenomena by measuring things (Gupta and Khanna, 2011). The data are then analysed using numerical comparisons and statistical inferences (Balnaves and Caputi, 2001). In this study, the research instrument was designed to examine the CSR reports of selected food companies in China to explore the scale of the current level and situation of CSR and CSRD of China's food industry. In contrast, qualitative research is concerned with understanding human behaviour from the informant's perspective. Data are collected through participant observation and interviews and

then analysed by categorising patterns and reporting meaningful findings (Flick, 2014; Major and Savin-Baden, 2013). In the current study, semi-structured interviews were used to collect qualitative data regarding the motivation for and obstacles to CSR practice within these companies.

With respect to the first research objective, the research process consisted of four stages. First, the top 100 food companies (available online: <https://baike.baidu.com/item/中国食品百强企业>) in China were identified according to their 2011 turnovers and their CSR reports from 2011 to 2015 (including stand-alone and integrated reports) were collected. The top 100 food companies and their 5 years CSR information are selected in the consideration of data quality. Tayi and Ballou (1998) advise that ‘fitness for use’ is the best definition in terms of ‘data quality’. The data of CSR information from top 100 companies are more reliable, and 5 years (2011 to 2015) are select in the consideration of this research starts in 2016. If a company did not have any CSR reports or integrated reports, any relevant information available on the internet regarding their CSR practice was considered. Second, a scorecard (the development of scorecard is explained in following section of 3.3.2) was designed in terms of the CASS-CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility Reporting for Chinese Enterprises) and GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) indexes before being used in the third stage to assess the CSR reports. In the final stage, the scorecard data was analysed.

The second research objective also involved a four-stage process. First, four different versions of the interview questions were designed according to the four different types of interviewees (consumers, general employees, managers and government staff). Next, the prospective interviewees were selected and contacted to see if they were willing to be interviewed. Third, one-to-one interviews were conducted and the data was collected via voice recording and

written notes. Finally, the data was analysed using the NVivo software. The work with NVivo software is explained in following section 3.4.4.

For the third research objective, the discussion regarding improvement was a three-stage process. The first stage involved identifying CSR disclosure deficiencies by reviewing the scorecard results, while the second looked at the insights and ideas generated using NVivo regarding the interviews. In the final stage, recommendations were offered according to the data analysis results. Figure 3.1 shows a summary of the research framework.

Figure 3. 1 A summary of the research framework

Research objective 1: To undertake a quantitative study by developing a measurement instrument to explore the current level and situation of CSR in China's food industry.

Research objective 2: To undertake a qualitative study using semi-structured interviews to explore the motivation for and challenges to carry out CSR practices and disclosing CSR information, and

Research objective 3: To offer practical improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and comprehension of CSR in China’s food industry.

Table 3.1 offers a timetable of the exploratory field research. The field research comprised the generation of the scorecard and semi-structured in-depth interviews. The following two sections describe and detail the methods applied in this research.

Table 3. 1 Field research timetable

	Date	Duration (Days)	Task
Scorecard (generation and CSR report assessment)	1 Oct to 31 Oct 2016	31	Review GRI and CASS-CSR indexes
	1 Nov to 30 Nov 2016	30	Generate scorecard
	1 Dec to 15 Feb 2017	77	Search CSR reports
	1 Mar to 30 May 2017	90	Assess CSR reports using scorecard
	Date	Duration (Days)	Task
In-depth interviews	15 Jul to 20 Sep 2017	65	Generate interview questions
	1 Oct to 20 Nov 2017	50	Contact interviewees
	1 Jan to 31 Mar 2018	89	Conduct in-depth interviews

3.3 Content Analysis- Scorecard

Content analysis enables researchers to identify the meaningful patterns and any correlations between these patterns in a large amount of textual information (Hodder, 1994; Krippendorff, 2013). Also, Duriau, Reger and Pfarrer (2007) argued that content analysis **is an important bridge that connects quantitative and qualitative research methods**. Researchers looking at corporate social disclosure (CSD) often employ content analysis as it is the most popular method of data analysis (Admas et al., 1998; Duff, 2014; Ernst and Ernst, 1978; Gray et al., 1995a, 1995b; Guthrie, Cuganesan, and Ward, 2008; Guthrie and Parker, 1990). The purpose of content analysis is to systematically examine the published information to identify the results can be compared (Duff, 2014; Guthrie et al., 2008; Krippendorff, 2013). Indeed, the existing literature indicates that content analysis is a successful method for examining CSR reports.

Table 3. 2 Examples of CSR papers that used content analysis

Name of authors	Year published	Title	Publisher	Page
Yongqiang Gao	2009	Corporate social performance in China: Evidence from large companies	Journal of Business Ethics	89: 23–35
Angus Duff	2014	Corporate social responsibility reporting in professional accounting firms	The British Accounting Review	1–13
Heledd Jenkins and Natalia Yakovleva	2004	Corporate social responsibility in the mining industry: Exploring trends in social and environmental disclosure	Journal of Cleaner Production	14: 271–284
Manuel Castelo Branco and Lucia Lima Rodrigues	2006	Communication of corporate social responsibility by Portuguese banks: A legitimacy theory perspective	Corporate Communications: An International Journal	11: 232–248
Judy L. Holcomb, Randall S. Upchurch and Fevzi Okumus	2007	Corporate social responsibility: What are top hotel companies reporting?	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	19: 461–475

3.3.1 Sample selection

The first objective of the current research was to study the current level of CSR in China's food industry. As Section 2.4.1 introduced, the food industry in China is diversified and scattered including small, medium, big companies, family-running, private or state-owned business. There is no exactly figure can be found to tell the total numbers of food companies in China between 2011 to 2015. Therefore, this study focuses on the top 100 food companies in China (Bvhlkmm20109, 2012) according to their 2011 annual turnover were selected. This can avoid self-selection bias. Due to the current CSR circumstances in China, these 100 companies are chosen in the consideration of data quality. In the Chapter of Literature review, it learns that CSR is developing in China, the Top 100 companies are regarded as large companies rather than small companies and are thought to be more willing to practise CSR to increase their brand reputation and enhance their market value. Therefore, more CSR information can be pulled out from their reports.

Examining all the CSR reports of a company, including stand-alone CSR reports and integrated reports (CSR information contained in an annual report), can be viewed as an intuitive presentation of a company's CSR practice (Dienes, Sassen and Fischer, 2016). It is a straightforward (Dienes, Sassen and Fischer, 2016) way to find out which CSR information they have disclosed. Apart from the publication of stand-alone or integrated CSR reports, those companies that had no official publicised CSR reports had their online CSR information (e.g. on the company website) used instead. Regardless of what kind of CSR information disclosing form, or even a company has no CSR information disclosing, these phenomena comprehensively reflect the level and situation of CSR in China's food companies.

The years 2011 to 2015 were looked at as this enabled the identification of any trends and changes and the comparison of differences in CSR information disclosure in the food industry

as a whole and within individual companies. By searching and reviewing the food companies' CSR reports, their CSR disclosure information was recorded as numerical notations in a specifically designed scorecard corresponding to each index. Section 3.3.2.2 explains the development of the scorecard.

3.3.2 Development of scorecard

Beattie and Thomson (2007, p. 135) stated that “content analysis requires a description of how to know when a category occurs, any qualifications or exclusion, and examples of categorized information”. It was therefore important to define the CSR categories and elements of CSD that could be obtained to allow researchers to explain their findings (Duff, 2014).

In February 2008, the **Corporate Social Responsibility Research Centre of the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences (CASS)** was set up. This centre contributes to the development of China's CSR practice in all industry sectors. In December 2009, the first Guidelines on Corporate Social Responsibility Reporting for Chinese Enterprises (CASS-CSR) was issued to integrate international and local standards. This event was a significant milestone in CSR development in China, and the guidelines are currently in their third edition, which is known as the CASS-CSR 3.0.

The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is an international not-for-profit and network-based organisation whose mission is to make sustainability reporting a standard practice and to enable all companies to have a reference to report their CSR performance. Its guidelines were designed to apply to organisations of any size and within any sector. The GRI guidelines are now in their fourth edition and are known as G4.

When designing the scorecard, the publication ‘Linking CASS-CSR 3.0 and GRI’s G4 Sustainability Reporting Guidelines’ was a useful cross-referencing tool for CASS-CSR 3.0 and G4. Refer to this publication and in the consideration of stakeholder, legitimacy and institutional theories, items of scorecard include relevant stakeholders’, legal and policy items.

The research instrument contained four sections. Section A recorded the company’s name, while section B recorded the format of the CSR report format, i.e. stand-alone CSR report, integrated report, web information only or no CSR information at all. Section C classified the auditing and assurance of the CSR information and included two items: ‘disclosure about internal assurance’ and ‘disclosure about external assurance’. Their variables were defined as 1 if they were explained and 0 if there was no discussion. Finally, section D captured the details of the CSR disclosure and included 10 subsections, each of which contained a different number of items. A summary structure and examples of items in section D are shown in Table 3.3.

In this study, all items in the scorecard are considered have the same weight. Variables were defined as 1 if relevant information were explained or disclosed, otherwise, the variables were defined as 0 if no discussion or information was disclosed. The consideration of keeping the items at the same weight is to avoid complexity of measurements and easy for researchers to find a defect of information disclosure items, and then can discuss further to find reasons which result in this phenomenon by interviews.

The sample included the 100 largest food companies operating in the research country, China, ranked on the basis of their 2011 annual turnover, brand influence and food safety status of markets (available online: <https://baike.baidu.com/item/中国食品百强企业>). The ground search of the Top 100 food companies’ CSR reports (standalone, integrated or web information

only) were conducted and all types of reports were downloaded and saved for assessing. The raw data was obtained by applying the designed scorecard to assess the CSR reports of the 100 largest companies for five years (2011 to 2015).

Table 3. 3 Structure of Scorecard and examples of items in Section D

<i>Section</i>	<i>No. of items</i>	<i>Description</i>
A	1	Company names
B	4	Reporting format
C	2	Auditing and assurance
D	63	CSR disclosure categories based on G4 and CASS-CSR 3.0
<i>Section D</i>	<i>No. of Items</i>	<i>Example item</i>
D1 Organisational strategy and analysis	2	D1a Top decision-maker statement D1b Major impacts, risks and opportunities
D2 Organisation information	6	D2a Organisation name D2b Primary brands D2c Operational structure of the organisation D2d Location of the organisation’s headquarters D2e Nature of ownership and legal form D2f Awards received in the reporting period
D3 Report content	6	D3a Reporting period D3b Reporting cycle D3c Contact information D3d Process for defining report content D3e Boundary of the report D3f Data measurement techniques
D4 Governance, commitment and engagement	5	D4a Governance structure D4b Mechanisms for shareholders and employees to provide recommendations or direction D4c Mission, values, codes of conduct and principles relevant to economic, environmental and social performance D4d Externally developed economic, environmental and social charters, principles or other initiatives D4e Key concerns of stakeholders

D5 Economic performance	5	D5a Direct economic value generated and distributed D5b Wage compared to local minimum wage D5c Policy, practices and proportion of spending on locally D5d Procedures for local hiring from the local community D5e Development and impact of infrastructure investments and services provided for public benefit
D6 Environment indicators	16	D6a Materials used by weight or volume D6b Percentage of materials used that are recycled D6c Direct energy consumption D6d Indirect energy consumption D6e Energy saved due to efficiency improvements D6f Initiatives to provide energy-efficient or renewable-energy-based products and services and reductions in energy requirements D6g Initiatives to reduce indirect energy consumption and reductions achieved D6h Percentage and total volume of water recycled and reused D6i Description of significant impacts of activities, products and services on biodiversity D6j Habitats protected or restored D6k Strategies, current acts and future plans for managing impacts on biodiversity D6l Total direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions by weight D6m Initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and reductions achieved D6n Waste disposal method D6o Products sold and their packaging materials derived from recycled material D6p The energy-saving of transporting for the organisation's operation
D7 Social responsibility index	7	D7a Total workforce by employment type, employment contract, region and gender D7b Total number and rate of employee by age group, gender and region D7c Benefits provided to employees D7d Rates of injury, occupational diseases, lost days and absenteeism and number of work-related fatalities listed by region D7e Education, training, counselling, prevention and risk-control programmes in place to assist workforce members D7f Ratio of basic salary of men to women by employee category D7f Ratio of returning to job after maternity/paternity leave
D8 Social: Human rights	6	D8a Percentage and total number of significant investment agreements that include human rights clauses D8b Total hours of employee training on policies and procedures D8c Total number of incidents of discrimination and corrective actions taken D8d Operations identified as having significant risk for incidents of child labour and measures taken to eliminate child labour D8e Operations identified as having significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour and measures taken to eliminate these D8f Total number of human rights field grievances through a formal complaint mechanism

D9 Social: Society	3	D9a Actions taken in response to incidents of corruption D9b Actions taken in response to anticompetitive behaviour, anti-trust and monopoly practices and their outcomes D9c Actions taken to prevent or reduce potential or actual adverse impacts on local communities
D10 Product responsibility	5	D10a Health and safety impacts of products and services D10b Total number of incidents of non-compliance with regulations and voluntary codes D10c Customer satisfaction surveys D10d Programmes for adherence to laws, standards and voluntary codes D10e Total number of substantiated complaints
D11 Philanthropic responsibility	3	D11a Donation to local community D11b Donation to natural disaster area D11c Employee assistance

3.3.3 Hypotheses

To match the research objectives, two hypotheses were stated.

H1. Larger companies have a significantly higher CSR performance compared to smaller companies as measured by the mean value on the scorecard.

In China, some food companies are large, international and managed in a modern way; however, a huge number of small, scattered food companies lack effective management. On the basis of national standards, the characteristics of the food industry should be integrated to formulate social responsibility evaluation standards for food companies, and then as the main body of the market economy, food companies should be encouraged to fulfil their social responsibilities. Refer to the Institutional theory, it is worth to find out if larger company has the more organisational culture or criteria can affect the level of CSR discourse. To test this hypothesis, the top 100 companies were divided into three groups according to the size of the companies and the average score for each group and each category were calculated.

To test this hypothesis, T-test and non-parametric test will be applied.

H2. Food companies which are considered to have more responsibilities to the customers will lead to more CSR practice and show their higher CSR concerns.

This hypothesis arose during the data collection as an interesting phenomenon caught my attention.

As a type of food industry, liquor companies produce alcohol products that are harmful to human health. Therefore, it is necessary to understand if this kind of company are willing to show high CSR awareness and how they practice their CSR activities. In addition, during the data collection of CSR reports from the top 100 food companies, it was found that these companies seemed to disclose more CSR information. Therefore, this was an interesting area to examine more closely. The quantitative data analysis chapter does not just discuss the results for these two hypotheses, however, but also analyses which categories has been paid more or less attention, and the situation of CSR reporting format.

In terms of legal driver, since 1st January 2006, the “Company Law of the People’s Republic of China” took effect. This move can be regarded as a legislative stimulus for CSR (NPC, 2005). Incorporating the concept and requirement of CSR into its legal system is one of the important development of this law and changes to the companies in China. Article 5 stipulates that companies should bear social responsibilities, not only to abide by laws and administrative regulations, but also to abide by social expectations and business morality (NPC, 2005). Undoubtedly, the implementation of this law has externally promoted companies’ awareness of fulfilling and committing their social responsibilities in China.

In addition, Confucian philosophy proposes Ren and Li. Ren is known as kindness, compassion, conscience, benevolence and willingness to help others (Warner and Zhu, 2002). Li is performed after Ren, as Li is an acceptable and polite behaviour developed by individuals with a benevolent heart and wisdom (Liu, 1998). There is a household word in Confucianism, that “What you do not wish for yourself, do not do to others” (Hutton, 2006). This rule can be referred not only to

individual persons and other lives, but also to companies.

3.4 Thematic analysis - Interviews

The analysis technique used for this research was thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is one of the most popular qualitative data analysis techniques used for analysing interview data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 79) also stated that thematic content analysis is the method used for “identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within the data”. Indeed, Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 97) argued that a “rigorous thematic approach can produce an insightful analysis that answers particular research questions”. When using thematic content analysis, it is important to consider and determine the themes in the interview data (Boyatzis, 1998; Crabtree, 1999; Charmaz, 2006; Saldana, 2009) and to link these themes to form a meaningful pattern to achieve their full significance (Bazeley, 2009). As Bazeley (2009) argued, ‘describe, compare, relate’ is a straightforward three-step way to report the analysis results. The most widely used thematic content analysis approach is the six phases of coding developed by Braun and Clarke (2006). These six phases are:

- Becoming familiar with the data (reading and re-reading);
- Generating initial codes (labelling) for the whole text;
- Searching for themes with broader meaningful patterns among the codes;
- Reviewing the identified themes to confirm they fit the data;
- Defining and naming the themes;
- Writing the final report.

3.4.1 Interviewees

Participants from four different groups were interviewed: food company managers, food company general employees (non-management), government staff and consumers. These types of participants were selected for the following reasons:

- 1) **Managers** work as a part of the company's management. This group of people have a good understanding of their companies' policies and guidelines and can provide valuable and targeted opinions due to their management experience. For example, they can explain their companies' CSR policies and activities and provide explanations as to why the companies do or do not practise CSR.
- 2) **General employees** were selected in this research as non-management as, although companies have policies and guidance, what the actual cases in their companies are the real purpose of this research. General employees can provide practical opinions regarding companies' CSR practices as opposed to information about CSR policies.
- 3) **Government representatives** have knowledge regarding government policies and can explain the government's perspective of the current CSR policies related to food companies in China.
- 4) **Consumers** are the people who purchase food products and determine whether a food company is successful or not. Therefore, their opinions regarding food companies' CSR practices are very valuable to this research.

By conducting interviews with these four groups, this research identified more specific thoughts and opinions from different angles.

A total of 22 Chinese interviewees were selected: three managers, three employees, one government representative and 15 consumers. The three managers and three employees were introduced by a government staff (who is also one of interviewees) from Anhui Chuzhou Economic and Technological Development Zone which has a Food industrial park. The 15 consumers were selected by sending interview invitations to these people the researcher knows. Table 3.4 provides a summary of the interviewees' background information. The three managers and three employees were selected from large food companies and the government representative was from a government department that administrates food companies. The 15 consumers were selected from different cities and varied in occupation, age and gender.

Table 3. 4 A summary of the interviewees' demographic information

Group	Case no.	Interviewee code	Gender	Age (years)	Company	Position	Interview mode
Managers	1	M1	M	40	Dong Peng	Manager	Face-to-face
	2	M2	M	50	Le Long	Director	Face-to-face
	3	M3	M	45	Pan Pan	Manager	Face-to-face
General employees	4	E1	F	35	Dong Peng	Officer	Face-to-face
	5	E2	F	29	Le Long	Worker	Face-to-face
	6	E3	F	28	Pan Pan	Worker	Face-to-face
Government staff	7	G1	F	30		Office administrator	Telephone
Consumers	8	C1	M	36		BEng PhD	Face-to-

					electric engineer	face
9	C2	M	32		IT test engineer	Telephone
10	C3	F	27		Jewellery buyer	Face-to-face
11	C4	F	54		University associate professor	Telephone
12	C5	F	37		Purchasing specialist	Telephone
13	C6	F	29		Chief financial officer	Telephone
14	C7	F	55		Vice president of finance department	Face-to-face
15	C8	M	29		University lecturer	Telephone
16	C10	M	60		Director	Face-to-face
17	C11	F	55		Housewife	Face-to-face

3.4.2 Conducting the interviews

Interviews were used to collect qualitative data as they allow the researcher to obtain multiple perspectives with respect to the research questions. Indeed, Folkestad (2008) stated that researchers can acquire new insights into a common social phenomenon by employing qualitative interviews as the interviewees are allowed to reflect on a variety of subjects in numerous ways (Creswell, 2007; Jugder, 2012). By conducting interviews, researchers can gather a wide range of information about people's open-ended ideas, feelings and attitudes. Interviews were a vital part of the current investigation into the CSR situation in China because they are a useful tool for discovering rich and detailed information that can be used for in-depth analyses (Lofland and Lofland, 1995).

The interviewees were contacted beforehand via email and sent an invitation to participate and a participant information sheet. The **participant information sheet** explained the purpose of the research project, why they had been chosen to participate, what would happen if they agreed to take part, the financial reward or travel expenses given for taking part, the other benefits of taking part, any physical discomfort or harm that it may involve, any embarrassment or other psychological stress that may be involved, how this project would be kept confidential, how their data would be used, who can review this study, what to do if they are unhappy during their participation in this project and how they take part. Each participant was required to sign a consent form before taking part. All the face-to-face interviews are conducted during the data collection period in China, and the other interviews were arranged and conducted by telephone.

In addition, regarding the interviews in this research, there are two points that need to be mentioned. First, as the research country was China, the interviewees are all Chinese. Therefore, all the interview documents (including the invitation to participate, the participant information sheet, and consent form and interview questions) were all translated into Chinese. In consideration of validity of the translation, Jianjun Ren obtained Bachelor (from the University of the West of Scotland) and Master degree (from the University of Glasgow) in the UK was invited to validate the Chinese to English translation voluntarily. Second, the interviews were audio-recorded with the permission of the interviewees.

3.4.3 Interview questions

The interviews were semi-structured as Gubrium and Holstein (2001) and Kvale (2007) suggested that this type of interview allows participants to express their views more openly. Fully structured

interviews were not used as Hopf (1978) argued that:

- 1) Rigorously following an interview guide might restrict the benefits of participant openness.
- 2) The interviewees might be interrupted at the wrong time in order to move to the next question or to finish the interview, leading to a state of oppression.
- 3) There is a dilemma between pressure of time and the interest in information the researchers are looking for on purpose.

Four versions of the interview questions were designed for the four different types of participants (see Appendix 5). In all versions, section 1 involved an explanation of the aim of the research, the importance of the interviewees' participation and an assurance of the confidentiality of the interviews. After it was established that the participant had signed the interview consent form and the permission for audio recording, the interview would formally begin.

Section 2 involved questions about the interviewees' general awareness of CSR as a concept and their opinions about the current level of CSR disclosure in China's food industry. Employees and managers of food companies were asked to describe the CSR policies and activities that were conducted within their companies and to talk about the companies' history of CSR development. The government representative was asked to talk about how government policies affect CSR policies and activities in China.

In section 3, the interviewees were asked to talk about the motivation for and obstacles to a company practising CSR. These questions were adjusted according to the type of interviewee, for

example, consumers were asked if they were willing to purchase a more expensive product if it had been produced by a food company with higher CSR performance, whereas the food company employees were asked if a good CSR performance had attracted them to the company. Company managers were asked if their companies benefitted from practising CSR, and the government representative was asked how companies could benefit from following the government's CSR policies.

Section 4 aimed to identify possible improvements that could be made to CSR practices and the interviewees were invited to provide recommendations and suggestions to develop and improve future CSR policies and activities in China's food industry. Finally, section 5 concluded the interview and the interviewees were asked to discuss any unclear or incomplete points and encouraged to give suggestions for future research.

3.4.4 Data analysis - NVivo

NVivo is a qualitative data analysis program (Maxwell, 2013). Bazeley and Jackson (2013) suggested that NVivo can assist research by carrying out a quality analysis of qualitative data. They also stated that by using NVivo, researchers can easily manage their research data and answer their research questions. In other words, this computer software is for data management and analysis (McNiff, 2016). According to Bazeley and Jackson (2013), Richards (2009), Richards and Morse (2012) and Flick (2014), using NVivo to conduct qualitative data analysis helps researchers in five ways. First, NVivo can help to manage data. It enables researchers to keep track of records by classifying and organising data and allows them to ask either simple or complex questions regarding the data. Then this NVivo program determines answers using all relevant information

according to the database. It is known as Query data.

NVivo can also visualise data and the relationships between the ideas, concepts, cases, etc. to assist abstraction and conceptualisation. Finally, outcomes can be reached by using the contents of the database, which can then enable researchers to generate a report to assist with the analysis of the results. The process of coding regarding the current research is introduced and explained in Chapter 5.

3.4.4.1 Work with NVivo

Interview were conducted in Chinese and all transcripts were provided in both Chinese and English. To minimise errors due to the different languages, all data are analysed in Chinese by NVivo. However, the results are then translated into English.

Figure 3.2 shows the process of using NVivo. The first stage is to design the NVivo database, including designing thinking cases and importing sources to the software. The second stage is the coding. As Bazeley and Jackson (2013) state, the primary purpose of conducting qualitative analysis is to generate themes to address the research objectives; therefore, coding helps the researcher to quickly identify the relationships between factors and identify the relevant ideas and connections among them. The next stage is to query and visualise in order to find words or phrases in the sources by comparison and opening of a specific node, and then, the findings can be presented.

Figure 3. 2 Simplified flow diagram of an NVivo project

Before importing our sources into NVivo, a paid website (<https://www.xfyun.cn>) was employed to transpose all the audio files into text files; 17 text files were produced in total. Then, in each text file, comments were noted regarding the interview questions. All the notes were made in English. Figure 3.3 shows a sample of the comments made in the text files.

Figure 3. 3 Sample of comments made in the text files

After tidying up and annotating the 17 files, we imported them into NVivo, as shown in Figure 3.4

below. Figure 3.5 shows a sample of ribbon and the navigation, list, and detail views.

Figure 3. 4 Cases in NVivo

Figure 3. 5 Sample – NVivo workspace showing ribbon and navigation, list and detail views

The navigation view allows the user to select which component of the project they wish to access such as sources or nodes. In addition, the user can further organise items into sub-folders. The list view is a list of all the projects (here, transcripts) for the user to select from. Finally, the detail view shows the actual detail (content) of an opened project, thus allowing the user to work on it directly (Bazeley and Jackson, 2013). The next step is the most important and meaningful stage, which is to analyse the qualitative data.

3.4.5 Hypotheses

There were two hypotheses relating to the interviews:

Hypothesis 3: All participants will have a low level of CSR awareness and their knowledge of CSR will not be comprehensive.

To test this hypothesis, all participants were asked to discuss their understanding of CSR and their knowledge of CSR.

Hypothesis 4: The CSR information that each group is concerned with will be closely related to their own interests and limited to a broad extension.

This hypothesis was tested by asking each participant about their motivation for paying attention to CSR information and how it benefits them.

The semi-structured interviews did not only test these two hypotheses, however. In addition, the open-ended questions allowed for the collection of various types of opinions and ideas, which are discussed in Chapter 6.

Chapter 4 Results – Scorecard

This chapter reports the findings of content analysis. To achieve the first objective, this research undertakes a quantitative study by developing a measurement instrument – a scorecard (content analysis) to explore the current level and situation of CSR and CSRD in China’s food industry. This chapter includes four sections, section 4.1 presents the analysis of CSRD by company size. Section 4.2 presents the analysis of CSRD by disclosure category in section D of the scorecard. Section 4.3 explains the results of the analysis of CSRD by report format. Section 4.4 provides the results of the analysis of CSRD by food companies with different food types. Finally, section 4.5 presents a summary of the findings.

The sample included the 100 largest food companies operating in the research country, China, ranked on the basis of their 2011 annual turnover, brand influence and food safety status of markets (available online: <https://baike.baidu.com/item/中国食品百强企业>). According to the Baidu information, 10 companies are state-owned food companies and others are private or foreign-owned. The raw data was obtained by applying the designed scorecard to assess the CSR reports (standalone, integrated or web information only) of the 100 largest companies for five years (2011 to 2015).

As the raw data was obtained by the scorecard assessment, two calculations were performed using the equation in Excel. One of the calculations was used to calculate the total scores of each company’s CSR reporting in each year. The other calculation was used to calculate the average amount (mean number) of sub-classified elements in each section and each specific element for the five-year period. Appendix 1 presents a summary of the calculation results. This calculation

was necessary for further data analysis and comparison as below.

4.1 Results of CSRD by company size

In order to test the **H1. Larger companies have a significantly higher CSR performance compared to smaller companies**, the 100 food companies were subdivided into three groups based on their 2011 annual turnover ranking: (1) companies ranked 1–20; (2) companies ranked 21–50; and (3) companies ranked 51–100. The collected primary data shows that two cliffs occur between the companies ranked lower than 64, especially those ranked between 80 and 100.

4.1.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4. 1 Analysis of mean value of disclosures by three groups

	Companies 1–20	Companies 21–50	Companies 51–100	Average
Section B				
Reporting format	1.66	1.17	0.54	1.12
<i>Total of Section B</i>	<i>1.66</i>	<i>1.17</i>	<i>0.54</i>	<i>1.12</i>
Section C				
C1	0.20	0.02	0.05	0.09
C2	0.22	0.01	0.00	0.08
<i>Total of Section C</i>	<i>0.42</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>0.17</i>
Section D: CSR disclosure categories based on the GRI and the CASS-CSR 3.0 Index				
D1 – Organisational strategy and analysis				
D1a	0.63	0.31	0.20	0.38
D1b	0.61	0.31	0.20	0.37
<i>Total Organisational strategy disclosures</i>	<i>1.24</i>	<i>0.63</i>	<i>0.40</i>	<i>0.76</i>
<i>Total Organisational strategy as % of total CSDs</i>	<i>5%</i>	<i>6%</i>	<i>7%</i>	<i>6%</i>
D2 – Organisation information				
D2a	0.73	0.45	0.23	0.47
D2b	0.73	0.45	0.23	0.47
D2c	0.61	0.31	0.15	0.36
D2d	0.57	0.31	0.15	0.35
D2e	0.49	0.31	0.15	0.32
D2f	0.62	0.37	0.23	0.41
<i>Total Organisation information disclosures</i>	<i>3.75</i>	<i>2.21</i>	<i>1.15</i>	<i>2.37</i>
<i>Total Organisation information as % of total CSDs</i>	<i>16%</i>	<i>20%</i>	<i>19%</i>	<i>18%</i>
D3 – Report content				
D3a	0.47	0.45	0.19	0.37
D3b	0.35	0.19	0.18	0.24
D3c	0.36	0.20	0.14	0.23
D3d	0.30	0.04	0.02	0.12
D3e	0.15	0.00	0.02	0.06
D3f	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.09
<i>Total Report content disclosures</i>	<i>1.91</i>	<i>0.87</i>	<i>0.54</i>	<i>1.11</i>
<i>Total Report content as % of total CSDs</i>	<i>8%</i>	<i>8%</i>	<i>9%</i>	<i>8%</i>
D4 – Governance, commitment and engagement				
D4a	0.65	0.37	0.10	0.38
D4b	0.38	0.17	0.06	0.20
D4c	0.59	0.45	0.22	0.42
D4d	0.25	0.07	0.05	0.12
D4e	0.43	0.22	0.09	0.25
<i>Total Governance, commitment and engagement disclosures</i>	<i>2.30</i>	<i>1.28</i>	<i>0.52</i>	<i>1.37</i>
<i>Total Governance, commitment and engagement as % of total CSDs</i>	<i>10%</i>	<i>11%</i>	<i>9%</i>	<i>10%</i>
D5 – Economic performance				
D5a	0.60	0.40	0.15	0.38
D5b	0.14	0.00	0.02	0.05
D5c	0.41	0.24	0.04	0.23
D5d	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.05
D5e	0.30	0.13	0.02	0.15
<i>Total Economic performance disclosures</i>	<i>1.61</i>	<i>0.77</i>	<i>0.22</i>	<i>0.87</i>
<i>Total Economic performance as % of total CSDs</i>	<i>7%</i>	<i>7%</i>	<i>4%</i>	<i>6%</i>
D6 – Environment index				
D6a	0.31	0.01	0.04	0.12
D6b	0.37	0.05	0.04	0.15
D6c	0.33	0.16	0.14	0.21
D6d	0.31	0.15	0.12	0.19

D6e	0.70	0.43	0.18	0.44
D6f	0.72	0.46	0.23	0.47
D6g	0.57	0.30	0.21	0.36
D6h	0.28	0.13	0.05	0.15
D6i	0.27	0.01	0.04	0.11
D6j	0.18	0.00	0.04	0.07
D6k	0.17	0.01	0.04	0.07
D6l	0.25	0.15	0.00	0.13
D6m	0.53	0.43	0.22	0.39
D6n	0.31	0.01	0.12	0.15
D6o	0.25	0.01	0.03	0.10
D6p	0.30	0.01	0.02	0.11
Total Environment index disclosures	5.85	2.35	1.50	3.24
Total Environment index as % of total CSDs	25%	21%	25%	24%
D7 – Employment index				
D7a	0.20	0.11	0.03	0.11
D7b	0.11	0.01	0.04	0.05
D7c	0.72	0.43	0.23	0.46
D7d	0.25	0.13	0.06	0.15
D7e	0.61	0.36	0.18	0.38
D7f	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.03
D7g	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.02
Total Employment index disclosures	2.04	1.04	0.54	1.21
Total Employment index as % of total CSDs	9%	9%	9%	9%
D8 – Social: human rights				
D8a	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.07
D8b	0.29	0.13	0.06	0.16
D8c	0.17	0.09	0.06	0.11
D8d	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.02
D8e	0.05	0.00	0.02	0.02
D8f	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.02
Total Social: human rights disclosures	0.80	0.23	0.18	0.40
Total Social: human rights as % of total CSDs	3%	2%	3%	3%
D9 – Social: society				
D9a	0.14	0.01	0.02	0.06
D9b	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
D9c	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.03
Total Social: society disclosures	0.19	0.03	0.04	0.09
Total Social: society as % of total CSDs	1%	0%	1%	1%
D10 – Product responsibility				
D10a	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.05
D10b	0.16	0.01	0.04	0.07
D10c	0.43	0.27	0.16	0.28
D10d	0.27	0.13	0.00	0.13
D10e	0.06	0.01	0.04	0.04
Total Product responsibility disclosures	1.08	0.43	0.24	0.58
Total Product responsibility as % of total CSDs	5%	4%	4%	4%
D11 – Philanthropic responsibility				
D11a	0.73	0.48	0.23	0.48
D11b	0.73	0.47	0.23	0.48
D11c	0.73	0.48	0.23	0.48
Total Philanthropic responsibility disclosures	2.19	1.43	0.70	1.44
Total Philanthropic responsibility as % of total CSDs	10%	13%	12%	11%
Total of Section D	22.96	11.25	6.04	13.42
Total of all the Sections	25.04	12.45	6.63	14.71

The result from Table 4.1, shows that the company size effect is noticeable. At the bottom of this table, the figures show that on average, the companies ranked 1–20 made **25.04** CSRDs,

whereas **12.45** CSRDs were made by the companies ranked 21–50 and **6.63** CSRDs were made by the companies ranked 51–100. By comparing these three figures to the average of these three groups, **14.71** CSRDs, it shows that the companies ranked 1–20 are in the only group that made a higher number of CSRDs than this figure. Furthermore, on taking a closer look at this table, it is easy to identify that the companies ranked 1–20 made a higher number of CSRDs in each section and each element than those in the other two groups. It is obvious that larger companies made a higher number of CSRDs than smaller companies. This finding supports the Hypothesis 1 that larger companies are more willing to disclose their CSR information. The larger companies attempt to enhance their reputation and distinguish themselves from other smaller and less influential companies that are regarded as their competitors (Duff, 2014; Toms, 2002).

In order to compare and analyse these three groups' data, SPSS software is applied to conduct the T-test and Non-parametric test.

4.1.1.1 T-test results

The T-test is a statistical hypothesis test and is usually used to tell how significant the differences between group means are. In addition, a t test uses a t-statistic and compares this to t-distribution values to determine if the results are statistically significant under the null hypothesis (H₀) (Pfanzagl and Sheynin, 1996). The aim of the independent (two-sample) T-test is to calculate the P value. When the null hypothesis (H₀) is true, the probability of a result that is more extreme than the obtained sample observation results. If the P value is small, it means that the probability of the null hypothesis is small, and if it is, according to the small probability principle, we have reason to reject the null hypothesis. The smaller the P value is, the more reason we have to reject the null hypothesis. In short, the smaller the P value, the more significant the result. In general, P is 0.05.

The mean value of each section from Scorecard for each groups is extracted. Then every two groups are compared and analysed by using the SPSS. The results are as below:

(1) Group 1 (companies 1-20) vs Group 2 (companies 21-50)

H0a (null hypothesis): There is no statistically significant difference (Group 1's performance is worse than Group 2's)

H1a (Alternative hypothesis): There is statistically significant difference (Group 1's performance is better than Group 2's)

Table 4.2 Group 1 vs Group 2 Descriptive

	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Score	Top1-20	14	1.79	1.64	1.52	0.407
	Top21-50	14	0.891	0.820	0.755	0.202

Table 4.3 Group 1 vs Group 2 P value of T-test

	Statistic	df	p
Score	1.97	26.0	0.030

Because the result of P is 0.03 less than 0.05, which has a significant difference. Therefore, H0a is rejected and H1a is adopted. It can tell that Group 1's CSR performance is better than Group 2's.

(2) Group 2 (companies 21-50) vs Group 3 (companies 51-100)

H0b (null hypothesis): There is no statistically significant difference (Group 2's performance is worse than Group 3's)

H1b (Alternative hypothesis): There is statistically significant difference (Group 2's performance is better than Group 3's)

Table 4.4 Group 2 vs Group 3 Descriptive

	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Score	Top21-50	14	0.891	0.820	0.755	0.202
	Top51-100	14	0.473	0.460	0.428	0.114

Table 4.5 Group 2 vs Group 3 P value of T-test

	Statistic	df	p
Score	1.80	26.0	0.042

Because the result of P is 0.042 less than 0.05, which has a significant difference. Therefore, H0b is rejected and H1b is adopted. It can tell that Group 2's CSR performance is better than Group 3's.

In summary of T-test results, Group 1 has the best CSR performance, then followed by Group 2, and Group 3 is the last. Furthermore, the non-parametric test is also applied to analyse the performance among these three groups.

4.1.1.2 Non-parametric test result

Non-parametric tests are an important part of statistical analysis methods, which are the basic content of statistical inference together with parametric tests. Parametric test is a method to infer the parameters of the population distribution such as mean value and variance when the form of the population distribution is known. However, in the process of data analysis, due to

various reasons, people often cannot make simple assumptions about the overall distribution, so the method of parameter test is no longer applicable. Based on this consideration, non-parametric test is a kind of method to infer the general distribution form by using sample data when the population variance is unknown or little known. The non-parametric test method is named "non-parametric" test because it does not involve parameters related to the population distribution in the process of inference (Bagdonavicius, Kruopis and Nikulin, 2011).

In this study, Kruskal-Wallis test is employed. Kruskal-Wallis test is essentially an extension of Mann-Whitney U test with two independent samples under multiple samples, and is also used to test whether there are significant differences in the distribution of multiple populations. The null hypothesis (H_0) is that there is no significant difference in the distribution of multiple populations with multiple independent samples. The basic idea is as follows: first, multiple sets of sample data are mixed and sorted in ascending order to find the rank of each variable value; Then, the mean values of each group were investigated to see whether there were significant differences. It is easy to understand: if there is no significant difference in the mean of each group's rank, it is the result of sufficient mixing of multiple groups of data with little difference in values, and it can be considered that there is no significant difference in the distribution of multiple populations. On the contrary, if there are significant differences in the mean values of each group, it means that multiple groups of data cannot be mixed, and the values of some groups are generally larger, while those of others are generally smaller. Therefore, it can be considered that there are significant differences in the distribution of multiple populations (Corder and Foreman, 2014).

H_0 hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference among these three groups (Group 1: companies 1-20; Group 2: companies 21-50; Group 3: companies 51-100)

H1: There is statistically significant difference among these three groups.

By applying the SPSS, the result is shown as Table 4.6. The P value is 0.01 less than 0.05.

Therefore H0 is rejected and H1 is adopted.

Table 4.6 Kruskal-Wallis result

	χ^2	df	p
Score	9.15	2	0.010

The P value result of Kruskal-Wallis test can prove that the three groups' performance are different (there is difference), but it cannot prove which is better or worse than which. However, the median from below box diagram (Figure 4.1) can show that Group 1's performance is the best, followed by Group 2's and then Group 3's.

Figure 4.1 Median of three groups

To summarise the above analysis, the data results support hypothesis 1 discussed in chapter 2. The results show that larger companies have significantly higher CSR performance and a significantly higher information disclosure level while smaller companies have lower CSR performance.

It is not surprised that larger companies have a higher number of CSRDs than smaller companies. It is interesting to think about the mechanisms behind this phenomenon.

Refer to the economic responsibility from Carroll's CSR pyramid, the most basic social responsibility, requires that the primary purpose of a company is to gain profit. Companies must make profits in order to survive and develop; only by making profits can they continue to grow and expand (Carrol 1991). Financial analysts from the Dow Jones Sustainability Indices found that stocks of companies that took these factors into account outperformed those that did not. In an addition, the core idea of stakeholder theory clearly defines companies as having corporate social responsibilities to stakeholders. It mainly explains the relationship between environmental responsibility and the company (Gray et al., 1996). Innovate Strategic Value Advisors also found that for those companies with excellent "environmental performance" their financial performance is also good. Therefore, the larger companies which aim to gain more profit are more willing to take the CSR factors into account and performance better.

Furthermore, link to ethical and philanthropic responsibilities from Carroll's CSR pyramid, Consumers have expectations of receiving safe and reliable products and services at a reasonable price, and a perfect after-sales service can be provided by companies. The public also has expectation that profitable companies can contribute and support more to the society. Whereas, these expectations are sometimes ignored as companies focus on pursuing higher

economic benefits. Consequently, ethical responsibility requires companies to meet consumers' expectation by providing with satisfied products and services. The more a company pays attention to CSR, the more likely its products and services will gain a larger market share. Today's customers have gradually strengthened their social awareness. They not only pay attention to whether the product can meet their key purchase factor, such as price, quality, safety, convenience, etc., but also care about how a company acts to meet the social expectations and contribute to society, the community and other stakeholders.

Finally, according to the legitimacy theory, Deegan and Rankin (1997) stated that they believe the survival of a company depends on the attitude of the society. The company must consider whether they are consistent with the social value system when they carry out business activities, otherwise they will be out of touch with social value system, which will cause difficulties in their business activities. CSR disclosure is a mechanism to enable companies to maintain their social and legal status. As a result, the larger companies are more willing to disclose their CSR activities to demonstrate that they are effectively complying with government regulations.

4.2 Results of CSR by disclosure category in section D of the scorecard

Table 4.1 also displays the mean number of CSRDs for each category and element in section D of the scorecard. When considering the results as a whole, the category with the widest disclosure of information is **D6 – Environment index (3.24 CSRDs and accounts for 24% of all CSRD disclosures)**. The Environment index measured issues relating to materials used, recycling that has been done, energy consumption and saving, habitat protection, waste disposal method, and the initiatives, strategies and plans for conducting environmental action. When considering these three groups' CSR performance individually, each of them provides the widest disclosure information in the Environment index (companies ranked 1–20: **5.58**

CSRDs and account for **25%** of all CSRD disclosures; companies ranked 21–50: **2.35** CSRDs and account for **21%** of all CSRD disclosures; and companies ranked 51–100: **1.50** CSRDs and account for **25%** of all CSRDs disclosures). The finding is that regardless of which group they are in (whether they are larger or smaller companies), all 100 companies have deep concern about environmental issues. All the companies prefer to conduct more activities relating to environment protection, which is an important social issue in China. However, one point which should be noted is that the disclosure elements in D6f – *initiatives to provide energy-efficient or renewable energy-based products and services, and reductions in energy requirement*, D6g – *initiatives to reduce indirect energy consumption and reductions achieved*, and D6m – *initiatives to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and reductions achieved*, show high scores in all three groups (D6f: **0.72** vs **0.46** vs **0.23**; D6g: **0.57** vs **0.30** vs **0.21**; D6m: **0.53** vs **0.43** vs **0.22**).

It is necessary to understand that these three elements (D6f, D6g and D6m) are selected to evaluate the companies that have initiatives but have not actually/practically conducted the activities. The high scores of these three elements in all three groups indicate that, in general, the CSRD level in China's food companies is in a developing phase. Many companies show concern about their CSR activities. In other words, they have aims and plans to conduct activities on environmental protection. However, they do not have actual behaviour to show how much they have done.

The second largest category of CSRD disclosures is **D2 – Organisation information** (average: **2.37** CSRDs and accounts for up to **18%** of all CSRD disclosures). This category measured issues relating to basic information of organisations, such as name, brands, products, services, operational structure, company location, nature of ownership, legal form, and awards received

in the reporting period. Comparison of three groups' scores (companies ranked 1–20: **3.75**; companies ranked 21–50: **2.21**; and companies ranked 51–100: **1.15**) shows that larger companies performed better in this category of CSR practice. However, when considering the percentage of total CSRDs for each group (companies ranked 1–20: **16%**; companies ranked 21–50: **20%**; and companies ranked 51–100: **19%**), the company size is not an explanatory factor that influences their disclosures. In other words, the three groups of companies, including large and small companies, all show high awareness and are more willing to disclose information about the organisation. This phenomenon may be due to the assumption that it is natural to disclose this type of information and it exists when a company is set up even if it does not perform any CSR activities.

D11 – Philanthropic responsibility is the third largest disclosure category (on average: **1.44** CSRDs and constitutes **11%** of all CSRD disclosures). This category measured issues relating to companies' philanthropic activities, including donations to the local community and natural disaster area (charitable practice) and assistance to the employees. Again, company size is not an explanatory factor that influences the three groups' overall disclosures (companies ranked 1–20: **10%**; companies ranked 21–50: **13%**; companies ranked 51–100: **12%**) when considering the percentage of the all CSRDs. However, looking at the scores from another perspective (companies ranked 1–20: **2.19**; companies ranked 21–50: **1.43**; companies ranked 51–100: **0.70**), there is no doubt that larger companies have higher scores. This phenomenon shows that the Chinese traditional social culture, Confucianism, and today's Harmonious Society have an impact on the whole of Chinese society rather than on an individual company or person. Companies prefer to show their CSR performance by carrying out philanthropic activities. Activities of this type contribute to companies' reputation and good social image. In addition, they enable companies to obtain the trust from the public, their employees and other

stakeholders. Therefore, larger companies have better performance than smaller companies. Moreover, this category is the one that companies would disclose regardless of whether they are large or small companies.

The **D4 – Governance, commitment and engagement** category has an average of **1.37** CSRDs and accounts for to **10%** of all CSRD disclosures. This category measured issues involve governance structure, mechanisms for shareholders and employees to provide advice, missions, values, codes of conduct, and principles related to economic, environmental and social performance, key concerns of stakeholders, and environmental principles or other initiatives. The three groups have a similar disclosure percentage (companies ranked 1–20: **10%**; companies ranked 21–50: **11%**; and companies ranked 51–100: **9%**); however, the individual score is very different (companies ranked 1–20: **2.30**; companies ranked 21–50: **1.28**; and companies ranked 51–100: **0.52**). This phenomenon is related to category D2 above.

D7 – Employment index has an average of **1.21** CSRDs and accounts for **9%** of all CSRD disclosures. This category measured issues relating to employment type, contract, turnover, benefits provided, rates of injury, diseases, absenteeism, education and training in place, and others. The company size effect is noticeable: larger companies have a higher average score than smaller companies (companies ranked 1–20: **2.04**; companies ranked 21–50: **1.04**; and companies ranked 51–100: **0.54**). However, when considering the percentage of all CSR disclosures (companies ranked 1–20: **9%**; companies ranked 21–50: **9%**; and companies ranked 51–100: **9%**), it is clear that all three groups of companies deemed this category equally important. This indicates that both large and small companies think highly of their employees and attach importance to their employees' value.

D3 – Report content has an average of **1.11** CSRDs and constitutes **8%** of all CSRD disclosures. The category measured issues relating to the CSR report content, for example, the reporting period, reporting cycle, contact information, process for defining report content, boundary of the report, and data measurement techniques. It is not difficult to understand why this category measured basic information that is easy to disclose; however, it still has a low disclosure score (companies ranked 1–20: **1.97**; companies ranked 21–50: **0.87**; and companies ranked 51–100: **0.54**), as overall, the number of disclosed reports (including standalone CSR report, integrated report and web information only) was limited. Without available information, this category was counted as none.

The next two categories, **D1 – Organisational strategy and analysis** and **D5 – Economic performance**, show the same percentage for all CSRD disclosures (**6%**), although their averages are slightly different (D1: **0.76**; D5: **0.87**). D1 measured issues relating to the top decision maker statement and major impacts, risks and opportunities. D5 measured issues related to the economic value generated and distributed by the company (e.g. revenues, profits, business running costs, compensation, and charitable donation), wage compared to the local minimum wage, local policy, practices and expenditure ratios, and recruiting local employees from the local community procedures, the development and impact of infrastructure investments, and the services provided to the public. The low level of disclosures reflects that the companies have limited actions in these two categories and limited reporting of actions in their CSR practice. These two indexes are associated as economic performance can be affected by organisational strategy and analysis.

D10 – Product responsibility, which measured issues relating to the companies' products, including health and safety impacts of products and services, total number of incidents of non-

compliance with regulations and voluntary code, customer satisfaction survey, programmes for adherence to laws, standards and voluntary codes, and total number of substantiated complaints, shows an average of **0.58** CSRDs and accounts for **4%** of all CSRDs. The low level of product information disclosures reflects the limited range of services that food companies currently provide to pay attention to their products. Based on the food scandals in China, the low level of product responsibility disclosures suggests that food companies do not feel it is necessary to give significant attention to these actions. There are two possible explanations for this. First, although the public know about the food scandals, the present regulation implemented by the Chinese government does not require the food companies to disclose this information relating to their product responsibilities. Therefore, the food companies choose not to disclose their product responsibilities action as it should be disclosed. Second, it is possible that currently, the non-disclosure food companies are not doing very well in this category. Therefore, they choose to ignore and take no actions relating to product responsibilities rather than disclose their actual circumstances.

The two categories with the lowest disclosure are **D8 – Social: human rights** (average CSRDs is **0.40** and constitutes **3%** of all CSRDs) and **D9 – Social: society** (average CSRDs is **0.09** and accounts for **1%** of all CSRDs). These two categories measured issues relating to human rights of employees, including total number of incidents of discrimination and corrective acts taken, child labour or compulsory labour and measures taken to eliminate these, total number of human rights field grievances through a formal complaint mechanism, and acts taken in response to incidents of corruption, anti-competitive behaviour, anti-trust and monopoly practices. The lowest level of social disclosures reflects that the food companies in China carried out limited actions regarding these issues. This does not mean, however, that these issues are not essential to the public; conversely, some social issues such as incidents of

discrimination and corruption have been the focus of attention of the society. A possible explanation for this is that these issues are sensitive, since it is not compulsory to disclose them, and therefore food companies prefer to ignore them if it is possible. Back to consider the **D7** which discloses employment index, measured issues relating to employment type, contract, turnover, benefits provided, rates of injury, diseases, absenteeism, education and training in place, and others. The company size effect is noticeable: larger companies have a higher average score than smaller companies (companies ranked 1–20: 2.04; companies ranked 21–50: 1.04; and companies ranked 51–100: 0.54). However, when considering the percentage of all CSR disclosures (companies ranked 1–20: 9%; companies ranked 21–50: 9%; and companies ranked 51–100: 9%). Link D7, D8 and D9, these three sections can be treated as associated. Although companies think highly of their employees and attach importance to their employees' value, they do not widely or further consider the human rights of employee such as child labour, complaint mechanism, corruption, anti-competitive behaviour, monopoly and many others.

From the above results, it shows that companies have corporate social responsibility disclosure preference. In other words, some classifications of CSR information are well disclosed rather than others. This phenomenon can be explained by the strategic corporate social responsibility (SCSR) discussed in Chapter 2. Baron (2001) proposes that from the perspective of behavioural motivations, SCSR refers to the corporate strategic behaviour of carrying out social responsibility and maximising profits. SCSR places more emphasis on the relationship between social responsibility and corporate strategy (Siegel and Vitaliano, 2007).

SCSR assumes that management determines the level of company resources allocated to social activities based on cost-benefit analysis. In addition, in the short term, the practice of the

company to actively fulfil CSR will increase transaction costs in the process of strategic decision-making and reduce corporate earnings, whereas in the long term, fully practice CSR will enhance the corporate image and increase the trust between buyers and sellers to reduce transaction costs (Siegel and Vitaliano, 2007). From one side, the management aims to lead the company to contribute to society, obtain the sustainable competitive advantage and satisfy stakeholders. However, from other side, the management's first objective is to maximise the profits. Therefore, with the limit of resources in the short term, the management choose to active CSR by some certain parts rather than fully fulfil CSR. As Yang (2007), a Chinese scholar, believes that SCSR is the strategic behaviour where companies take the initiative to assume CSR and influence corporate activities from the strategic perspective.

From the most widely disclosed index- D6 environmental index and third disclosed index- D11 Philanthropic responsibility, it is interesting to note that although conduct environmental and philanthropic activities can increase transaction cost in practice, whereas in the long run, SCSR will strengthen the corporate reputation trust between buyers and sellers to reduce transaction costs (Siegel and Vitaliano, 2007). SCSR improves the common utility of the enterprise and stakeholders by saving transaction costs, thus demonstrating the positive impact of SCSR on enterprises and society from the perspective of economics.

Donaldson and Preston (1995) argue that, in long term, actively fulfil SCSR not only responding to the demands of stakeholders, but also improving the reputation of enterprises, solidifying the relationship between stakeholders and enterprises, and reducing business risks. Therefore, the above results show that, although the top 100 companies are hardly to fulfil the CSR or publish high quality CSR report, they still disclose some certain CSR information to meet the social expectation and demand.

4.3 Results of CSRD by report format

Section B of the scorecard relates to the disclosure format of the CSR. The report format is classified into four categories: standalone CSR report, integrated report, web information, and no CSR information. This section of the assessment aims to identify which type of CSR disclosure format is most widely used. In general, a company that uses a public standalone CSR report is regarded as having a high level of CSR awareness and may have better performance as it may conduct more CSR activities. Although, a public standalone CSR reports are not compulsory, this group of companies uses a public standalone CSR show that they are more willing to play their CSR roles in society. In terms of SCSR, these companies meet the following characteristics: to enable stakeholders (e.g. consumers) build awareness of products they received have the value of CSR contained; manage the stakeholder relationship can enhance a company or an organisation's value; take an active part in social activities other than those required by law; and look for current market opportunities to solve social problems (Husted and Allen, 2007).

The integrated report here means that the CSR information is not published in a standalone report but is included in other reports, such as accounting reports or annual reports. The web information format means that neither a standalone report nor an integrated report can be found but relevant CSR information is provided or explained on the website. Finally, it is not difficult to understand 'no CSR information', which means that no relevant CSR information can be found. Table 4.2 below shows the percentage of each type of report format.

Table 4. 7 Analysis of the CSR report format

Report Format	Number	Percentage
Standalone CSR report	136	27.20%
Integrated report	4	0.80%
Web information	61	12.20%
No CSR information	299	59.80%
<u>Total</u>	<u>500</u>	<u>100.00%</u>

Since there are 100 companies and their CSR reports for five years are assessed, the total number is 500. As reported in Table 5.2, the number of standalone CSR reports is 136, which accounts for 27.20% of the total. There are only four integrated reports, which accounts for 0.8% of the total. The number of web information reports is 61, which accounts for 12.2% of the total. The number for no CSR information is 299, which accounts for 59.80% of the total. It is evident that the CSRD level of China's food companies is quite low. The selected companies are the top 100 food companies according to the 2011 ranking; however, even the top companies show an unsatisfactory result. This indicates that low levels of disclosure lead to low levels of practice. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the CSR practice in China and that strengthening publicity to raise public awareness of CSR in China is urgently required.

4.4 Results of CSD by food companies that produce liquor products

In the process of data collection, it was interesting to note that the food companies which produce liquor products (e.g. beer and wine) show that they have high levels of CSR awareness and a high information disclosure level. Table 4.3 presents the analysis results.

In Table 4.3, it is clear that for each index in section D, liquor companies have a higher score than other companies. However, both liquor companies and other companies have a similar percentage of total CSRD disclosures. This phenomenon reflects one aspect: regardless of what

type of products they produce, companies exhibit similar concern and attention to each issue of their CSR. This could be due to the social culture, government policy and social influence. It is necessary to discuss the reasons that lead the liquor companies to have better performance in their CSR.

The first reason may be that the liquor companies have higher comprehension of their public duty. Generally, the products produced by the liquor companies are beer, wine and other alcoholic drinks, which are considered as unhealthy for the human body, and the people who have excessive alcohol consumption may cause anti-social behaviour. Furthermore, according to the theory of organisational legitimacy, companies seek to show their congruency between the social values and the norms of acceptable behaviour in society (Scott, 2003). It is important to establish and maintain good and beneficial relationships between an organisation and the public and its stakeholders (Patel, Xavier and Broom, 2005). In addition, according to the institutional theory, the survival of an organisation depends not only on its material resources, operation, technique and marketing, but also on its perceived legitimacy (Powell and DiMaggio, 1991). As a result, the liquor companies earnestly fulfil their corporate social responsibilities and build an enterprise with sustainable development to reveal that they are legitimate, helpful and meaningful to the society and their stakeholders in some respects. Moreover, the liquor companies' good performance on their CSR can help them to obtain public support, which, in turn, can help them to achieve and maintain the success of the business operation.

Second, there is another important reason that cannot be ignored. On 20th October 2011, China Alcoholic Drinks Association (CADA) Science and Technology Awards was set up. These awards were established to encourage and reward liquor companies that have made contributions to production technology, equipment designs, energy conservation and emission

reduction, environmental protection, and technical innovation and development. The liquor companies that are nominated and rewarded will obtain the government and the association's incentive and awards. It can be seen that these rewards motivate the liquor companies to improve their CSR practices. This result can also be explained by the institutional theory. Within the organisational field, organisations (liquor companies) attempt to comply with recognisable and acceptable standards that help to cultivate their organisational legitimacy. The institutional theory emphasises the normative influence of the social environment on organisational activities and behaviour (Bess and Dee, 2008). In other words, the liquor companies' better performance in their overall CSR practices may be due to the positive effect of the whole industry. The correct and positive policy and regulation play an important role to lead the entire industry. It shows that, as hypothesis 2 suggests, particular food companies – in this case, liquor companies – have more responsibilities to customers, which leads to more CSR practices, and they show their higher CSR concerns.

Table 4. 8 Analysis of mean number of liquor companies vs other types of company

	Liquor	Other types	Average
Section B			
Reporting format	1.93	0	0.965
<i>Total of Section B</i>	<i>1.93</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0.965</i>
Section C			
C1	0.1	0	0.05
C2	0.06	0	0.03
<i>Total of Section C</i>	<i>0.16</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0.08</i>
Section D: CSR disclosure categories based on GRI and CASS-CSR 3.0 index			
D1 – Organisational strategy and analysis			
D1a	0.49	0.19	0.34
D1b	0.47	0.19	0.33
<i>Total Organisational strategy disclosures</i>	<i>0.96</i>	<i>0.38</i>	<i>0.67</i>
<i>Total Organisational strategy as % of total CSDs</i>	<i>5%</i>	<i>6%</i>	<i>5%</i>
D2 – Organisation information			
D2a	0.70	0.21	0.45
D2b	0.70	0.21	0.45
D2c	0.47	0.17	0.32

D2d	0.44	0.16	0.30
D2e	0.44	0.15	0.30
D2f	0.61	0.19	0.40
Total Organisation information disclosures	3.38	1.08	2.23
Total Organisation information as % of total CSDs	18%	18%	18%
D3 – Report content			
D3a	0.61	0.16	0.39
D3b	0.43	0.10	0.26
D3c	0.40	0.09	0.25
D3d	0.13	0.04	0.09
D3e	0.04	0.03	0.03
D3f	0.07	0.04	0.06
Total Report content disclosures	1.69	0.46	1.07
Total Report content as % of total CSDs	9%	8%	9%
D4 – Governance, commitment and engagement			
D4a	0.47	0.17	0.32
D4b	0.31	0.07	0.19
D4c	0.70	0.17	0.44
D4d	0.19	0.05	0.12
D4e	0.24	0.13	0.18
Total Governance, commitment and engagement disclosures	1.90	0.59	1.25
Total Governance, commitment and engagement as % of total CSDs	10%	10%	10%
D5 – Economic performance			
D5a	0.63	0.15	0.39
D5b	0.02	0.03	0.03
D5c	0.23	0.11	0.17
D5d	0.04	0.02	0.03
D5e	0.19	0.06	0.12
Total Economic performance disclosures	1.10	0.36	0.73
Total Economic performance as % of total CSDs	6%	6%	6%
D6 – Environment index			
D6a	0.16	0.04	0.10
D6b	0.20	0.06	0.13
D6c	0.40	0.08	0.24
D6d	0.35	0.07	0.21
D6e	0.59	0.20	0.40
D6f	0.70	0.21	0.45
D6g	0.66	0.13	0.40
D6h	0.22	0.06	0.14
D6i	0.15	0.04	0.09
D6j	0.07	0.04	0.06
D6k	0.04	0.05	0.05
D6l	0.26	0.02	0.14
D6m	0.65	0.17	0.41
D6n	0.20	0.07	0.14
D6o	0.04	0.06	0.05
D6p	0.07	0.05	0.06
Total Environment index disclosures	4.76	1.34	3.05
Total Environment index as % of total CSDs	25%	23%	24%
D7 – Employment index			
D7a	0.13	0.05	0.09
D7b	0.07	0.03	0.05
D7c	0.70	0.20	0.45
D7d	0.21	0.06	0.14
D7e	0.55	0.17	0.36
D7f	0.00	0.02	0.01
D7g	0.00	0.01	0.01
Total Employment index disclosures	1.67	0.54	1.10
Total Employment index as % of total CSDs	9%	9%	9%

D8 – Social: human rights			
D8a	0.07	0.02	0.05
D8b	0.25	0.06	0.16
D8c	0.21	0.03	0.12
D8d	0.00	0.01	0.01
D8e	0.00	0.02	0.01
D8f	0.06	0.01	0.03
Total Social: human rights disclosures	0.60	0.16	0.38
Total Social: human rights as % of total CSDs	3%	3%	3%
D9 – Social: society			
D9a	0.05	0.03	0.04
D9b	0.00	0.00	0.00
D9c	0.01	0.02	0.02
Total Social: society disclosures	0.07	0.05	0.06
Total Social: society as % of total CSDs	0%	1%	0%
D10 – Product responsibility			
D10a	0.01	0.03	0.02
D10b	0.07	0.04	0.06
D10c	0.53	0.10	0.32
D10d	0.16	0.05	0.11
D10e	0.06	0.02	0.04
Total Product responsibility disclosures	0.84	0.23	0.54
Total Product responsibility as % of total CSDs	4%	4%	4%
D11 – Philanthropic responsibility			
D11a	0.70	0.22	0.46
D11b	0.70	0.21	0.46
D11c	0.70	0.22	0.46
Total Philanthropic responsibility disclosures	2.11	0.64	1.38
Total Philanthropic responsibility as % of total CSDs	11%	11%	11%
Total of Section D	19.09	5.83	12.46
<u>Total of all the Sections</u>	<u>21.18</u>	<u>5.83</u>	<u>13.51</u>

4.5 Summary of findings

The first objective of this thesis is to undertake a quantitative study by developing a measurement instrument- Scorecard (content analysis) to explore the current level and situation of CSR and CSRD of China's food industry. Table 4.4 provides a summary of the findings.

Table 4. 2 Summary of findings

Issue	Findings
Results of CSRD by company size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The company size effect is noticeable Larger companies produce more CSRDs than smaller companies

Results of CSRD by disclosure category in section D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Environment index is the category with the most reports • The category with the fewest reports is the Social index • Company size is not an explanatory factor that influences the three groups' overall disclosures if considering the percentage of all CSRDs • The Philanthropic index is the category that companies would prefer to disclose regardless of whether they are large or small companies
Results of CSRD by report format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CSR disclosure level is low in China's food companies • In total, 59.80% of companies have no CSR information
Results of CSRD by liquor companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liquor companies have better performance than food companies that produce other product types in China • Relevant CSR organisation plays an important role to improve the CSR practice • It is useful to set up awards to promote the development of CSR in China

From the content analysis result, in the light of Objective 1, the research findings show that the Philanthropic index is the category that food companies in China would like to disclose more, both large and small companies. Also, the Environment index is the most widely disclosed category. Through above two most disclosed categories, companies show their charitable activities and public spirit. The literature review (section 2.3.1 The three-stage development of CSR in China) also reveals that CSR, which is not new to China, has a long development history and is changing with the times. There is a three-stage development of CSR within China, starting with Traditional CSR – Confucianism, moving to Modern CSR and then on to the Scientific Development Concept and the Construction of a Harmonious Society. Wang and Juslin (2009) proposed a new definition of CSR, called the Chinese harmony approach. They examined CSR via traditional Chinese culture and philosophy. In this thesis, the current data obtained from the Scorecard can show that the primary reason for China's companies to apply CSR is to contribute to a harmonious society (Wang and Juslin, 2009). The concept of CSR

among Chinese firms and markets is rooted in traditional Confucianism. In order to better adapt to the government's policy of constructing a harmonious society, Chinese companies are expected to exhibit social responsibility. This thesis adds to the extant knowledge of the Chinese harmony approach, revealing that companies in China carry out their CSR activities to show their concerns for nature and kindness to people.

The content analysis also show that liquor companies have a stronger performance compared to other food product companies in China. This phenomenon can be explained by the legitimacy theory. As liquor companies produce alcoholic products, regarded as harmful to human health, the Chinese public (both consumers and the government) expects the liquor companies to contribute to society more to gain the public's confidence as well as to compensate the public. Liquor companies attempt to comply with recognisable and acceptable standards to cultivate an organisational legitimacy. Moreover, institutional theory suggests that better CSR performance results in another important effect, which both coercive and normative isomorphism can effectively explain. Coercive isomorphism derives from the formal or informal pressure exerted by other organisations on which a company depends as well as the sociocultural expectations of that society. This pressure can be forceful, persuasive, or inviting collusion (Mizruchi and Fein, 1999; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Many neighbourhood organisations in urban communities form organisational hierarchies in order to gain support from other hierarchical aid organisations and others. In addition, normative isomorphism refers to the behaviour required by the normative expectations of the professional community. In other words, it is mainly derived from professionalisation, that is, the formal education and legalisation based on the cognition created by the university and the development and deepening of a career network that permeates the organisation, so the new model can spread rapidly (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). China's alcoholic drinks association's Science and

Technology awards were established on 20th October 2011 to encourage and reward liquor companies who have contributed to production technology, equipment designs, energy conservation and emission reduction, environmental protection, technical innovation and development. In order to survive competition, they comply with laws and policies and follow the trend of their peers.

Chapter 5: Results – In-depth Interviews

Chapter 3 explains that two research methods are employed to conduct this research. Content analysis is the first method, while in-depth interviews are the other research method employed to achieve the research objectives. As stated in Introduction, Objective 2 of this thesis is to undertake a qualitative study using in-depth interviews to explore the motivations and challenges to carrying out CSR practice and disclosing CSR information. Objective 3 is to offer practical improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and comprehension of CSR in China's food industry.

This chapter is divided into two sections. Section 5.1 presents the results produced by NVivo analysis. This section is sub-classified into four parts – results regarding managers, general employees, government staff and consumers, respectively. Section 5.2 provides a summary of the findings.

5.1 Results

As the interviewees are classified into four groups (managers, general employees, government staff and consumers), the data analysis results are divided into four sections accordingly.

5.1.1 Results from participants' responses – managers

1. CSR disclosure level and current CSR situation

Our three interviews with managers all indicate that the current CSR disclosure level in China is developing, but that it is still low compared to that in Western countries. One point that must be noted is that Chinese people are less aware of the concept of CSR; even many highly

educated people lack knowledge in this area. For example, one manager (M1) stated:

I believe companies in China, no matter what kind of company, are working on the improvement of CSR performance... such as some charitable activities and providing help and benefits to their employees. However, it is difficult and impractical to ask every company to follow regulations or policies to fully apply CSR... In general, CSR in China is a developing concept and has been improving quickly in the past decades, but there are very different levels of performance in different companies.

Another manager M2 particularly mentioned CSR in the food industry in China:

Relevant governmental departments such as the Food and Drug Administration and the Environmental Protection Agency have set up more detailed policies and regulations to supervise food companies' CSR activities. Also, both from the government and on social media, the publicity for CSR has been stepped up. I would like to say our CSR performance has improved rapidly, but there's still a long way to go.

2. Managers' CSR awareness

The research findings showed that it is necessary to understand managers' awareness regarding CSR because they are particularly relevant to the overall management of a company. They are decision-makers; in other words, their opinions shape their management approaches, which have a strong reflection on the whole company and thus may lead to success or failure. Managers' CSR awareness definitely influences their companies' CSR performance. M1 stated that:

In my company, from the top to the bottom, we have a strong awareness of CSR. We realise the importance of CSR practice, which will definitely bring future benefits to our company. We treat CSR as part of our management culture and also we would like to show the public that we are concerned about society and the environment. In addition, we would like to tell the public about the CSR activities we have done to care about other stakeholders. (M1)

However, although all three of the participating managers state that they and their companies' senior management have a strong awareness of CSR and that they have positive attitudes towards implementing CSR activities as much as they can, they are unfortunately limited in terms of fully developing their CSR practice by a number of factors. M2 stated that:

As I know, even large companies cannot make sure to follow all CSR policies

or meet shareholders' every expectation. It is not only due to cost and time consuming from a company's management concerns, the most important point is as I know, we don't have a proper organisation to circulate an integral CSR policies to varied industries. We are not fully educated or timely updated in terms of the CSR policies by the certain government department. (M2)

3. Motivations for conducting CSR activities

From a company's perspective, the first motivation for conducting CSR activities is to contribute to society. Eventually, these contributions will be beneficial for the company reputation and then help to gain social recognition. A positive reputation also leads to increasing profits for a company, which becomes a further incentive for the company to continue carrying out CSR activities and contributing to society. This process is seen as a virtuous circle. For example, M1 mentioned that:

Economic conditions of Chinese people are getting better and better, and therefore, people's pursuit of quality of life is also becoming more and more important. In order to meet the needs of the public, companies not only need to offer quality products, but also to provide good service and show their concern for society, including through environmental protection, charitable activities, employee benefits, etc. By employing CSR activities, companies improve their reputation, which can attract more customers.

In the framework of stakeholder theory, effectively and efficiently meeting stakeholders' needs is the key factor in a company's success or failure (Freeman et al., 2005). Gaining profits is the most important aim for a company to ensure its survival (Wall et al., 2007). Conducting CSR activities enhances a company's visibility, supports its brand development and helps it to maintain better customer relationships. Although there are costs involved in CSR activities, they bring further profits to companies in the long term.

The second motivation is based on **pressure from social media and peers**. Through the media, community and government promotion, and education campaigns, the overall consciousness

about CSR in China is improving. From our participating managers' perspectives, they have consciousness and motivation around promoting their CSR activities and disclosing their CSR information. In line with the framework of institutional theory, liquor companies often perform better CSR because their other peers have also done so effectively. For example, M3 stated:

I shall say, to disclose CSR information is not compulsory in China. For example, our company does not have to publish an annual CSR report. However, we still carry out CSR practice and publish CSR information due to the pressure we feel from our peers. (M3)

We would like to show that we have the awareness to keep at the same level as our peer companies to improve our company's image and enhance our reputation as well as to improve the overall CSR awareness level of this industry. (M1)

Finally, the third motivation is the **government regulations**, which have an important effect on companies' CSR performance. It is unavoidable that relevant policies, laws and regulations are the largest driving force. M1, M2 and M3 stated that:

We do what the government asked us to do. (M1)

We definitely follow the policy required by our government. (M2)

We follow the government guide. (M3)

According to the requirements of stock exchange regulators and company listings regulators, some listed companies are required to disclose their CSR reports. Other companies – for example, small companies – also follow the government policy requirement to implement CSR activities. Participant M1 mentioned that:

For example, our government requires food companies to cut down environmental pollution such as carbon emissions and sewage discharge; we follow our government's policy. (M1)

4. Obstacles

Taking into consideration the low CSR disclosure level in China, we asked our participating managers about the obstacles to conducting CSR activities and whether they have any reasons

that take no action on the CSR.

There managers did not give much response in terms of explaining the obstacles to conducting CSR practice. On the contrary, they all stated that their companies positively implement CSR policies and conduct CSR activities. Their CSR policies are supported at all levels, from the head of the company down to the least senior employees. Furthermore, their CSR activities have been processed and hold successfully and smoothly. Only one interviewee, M1, mentioned encountering one obstacle stoped his company to conducting CSR activities.

My company attempted one donation activity that was refused by the beneficiary party as that individual did not want to be treated as poor and wanted to succeed based on his own efforts. (M1)

This phenomenon can be explained by the indifference of CSR awareness, and the CSR implementation is not comprehensive.

There are more responses from other groups (general employees and consumers), compared to the interviews with the managers. This is a common type of challenge that can arise for qualitative researchers who employ interviews, which is known as interview bias.

5. CSR practice

In the interviews, we asked the managers to tell us about the CSR practices or activities they have conducted.

From each interview, the respondent positively talked about the CSR practice and activities that their company carries out. It is also easy to identify that they all discussed CSR activities related to the environment, philanthropy and products. This phenomenon match to the results

of Scorecard. These findings indicate that these food companies show a willingness to contribute to society, protect the environment and provide high-quality products. In addition, the respondents show a high level of concern for their employees – they mentioned that their companies provide good employee benefits according to the government requirements and offer multiple activities, such as company paid holidays, to their staff. Furthermore, they provide help to employees who are encountering difficulties in their lives.

6. Improvement approaches

Another topic that needs to be addressed with regard to the interviews with managers is the improvement approaches they suggested.

One respondent suggested that, from the company perspective, each company is supposed to obey the government's policies and regulations. At the same time, they suggested that the government should provide relevant **education** and promotion, not only to companies but also to the public, to increase the overall CSR awareness of Chinese society. For example, participant M1 and M2 suggested that:

I think the low level CSR awareness is resulted in the lack of CSR concept promotion. Not only the common people, even the middle and senior manager cannot fully explain what the CSR is. The school, government and social media should properly promote the concept of CSR. (M1)

Education is the foundation to radically change the situation to finally improve the CSR performance in every industry in China. (M2)

In addition, the three manager participants clearly suggested that the government needs to further **improve regulations and policies** to guide companies and the public in the area of CSR. It could also contribute by improving supervision and imposing tougher penalties on violators of CSR regulations. For example, participant M1 and M3 proposed that:

I think the specific CSR policies should be set up in terms of different industries. In addition, yearly or every few years CSR policies reviews are necessary to match International standard. (M1)

I think the precise penalties should be in place. The penalties is not limited to monetary punishment, also should be extended to social status and rights. (M3)

5.1.2 Results from participants' responses – general employees

The interviews with general employees did not yield as much information as expected. However, the findings that we did obtain are not surprising. Figure 5.1 shows the categories and the frequency with which each was discussed in each of Cases 4, 5 and 6.

Figure 5. 1 Categories and frequency of mentions in Case 4, 5 and 6

	A : Case 4	B : Case 5	C : Case 6
1 : CSR practice - Economic	0	0	0
2 : CSR practice - Employment	0	1	1
3 : CSR practice - Environment	1	0	1
4 : CSR practice - Philanthropy	1	0	5
5 : CSR practice - Product	0	0	0
6 : CSR practice - social human rights	1	0	0
7 : CSR practice - social society	0	0	0
8 : CSR concept	0	0	0
9 : CSR current situation	0	0	0
10 : CSR development history	0	0	0
11 : CSR disclosure format	0	0	0
12 : CSR disclosure level	2	1	1
13 : Government policies	0	0	0
14 : Improvement approach	1	0	0
15 : Most important social responsibilities	0	0	0
16 : Motivation	1	2	1
17 : Obstacles	0	1	0
18 : Suggestion to the research	2	0	0

1. CSR disclosure level and current situation

In the general employees' responses, they suggested that their companies perform good CSR activities than they expect. The respondents stated that their companies care about them (employees) and carry out many charitable activities every year. However, when the interviewer asked about other CSR activities such as specific measures related to environmental protection, quality-checked production processes to ensure suitable products,

aftercare services, etc., the respondents indicated that they were not familiar with these and had not thought about them. This point reflects that these lower-level employees lack in-depth CSR knowledge. At their level, they only think about CSR related to their own interests (employee benefits), without fully comprehending that CSR practice may apply to other areas of society.

For example, participant E1 stated:

Our companies have some activities about CSR such as environmental protection, staff benefits and charitable activities. However, as far as I know, not every company has awareness of CSR, and even some companies who have the awareness may not implement it due to complex and variable reasons.(E1)

2. Motivations for conducting CSR

The employees proposed that their companies conduct CSR due to the company's leadership. Their corporate culture is to be grateful to share, to make contributions to society and to benefit future generations. During the interviews, the respondents were asked whether they prefer a company that carries out their CSR at a higher level when they are looking for a job. All the participants responded to this question affirmatively. They believe that a responsible company can offer a better working environment and, from an employee's perspective, this is beneficial for their personal skills improvement and career development.

3. Obstacles

A key point to address here is that the majority of the employee participants believe that **cost** is the biggest obstacle to implementing CSR activities. For example, participants E2 and E3 explained that:

To protect the environment, our companies installed proper sewage systems. This cost large amounts of money. Obviously, not every company can afford it or will be willing to spend such large amounts of money if they are not sure when the costs will be covered.(E2)

As I know, my company cuts cost on unnecessary expenses. Some of the CSR activities cannot bring profit in short term, for example improve all equipement, but overspending. My company chose not to do it. (E3)

It is a concern that each CSR activity comes with costs, and companies cannot be sure of the level of monetary returns they will result in. The bottom line is that corporations exist for profit; thus, in terms of costs, some companies, especially small and medium-sized ones, may not be willing to lay out large amounts of money that may return less or even nothing.

4. Improvement approach

With regard to the improvement approaches proposed by employees, they suggested that their companies should conduct more interaction with employees from different departments to understand their needs and desires. For example, E1 suggested that:

In the consideration of CSR activities related to us, as general staff, I would like to say I wish companies would provide more staff training to increase our competitiveness. (E1)

Similarly, participant E3 suggested that **education** is a key priority, not only for managers and top decision makers, but for employees at all levels. They stated that:

I believe, if the overall awareness and knowledge of CSR is improved, the CSR level may increase, and it may be performed better in China.

The findings from the general employees' interviews do not contain a great deal of information; the respondents mostly focused on themselves and did not show a broad horizon to considering other issues. Although the in-depth interviews were organised as semi-structured and all the participants were encouraged to keep an open mind and discuss anything they believed to be relevant, the results from these respondents are not fully satisfactory for the researcher.

5.1.3 Results from participants' responses – government staff

The interview with a government staff member aimed to identify the current government policies with respect to CSR in China as well as improvement approaches for developing CSR.

1. Motivations for carrying out CSR activities

According to participant G1, there are three motivations for carrying out and developing CSR activities.

First, the government encourages profitable companies to help others who need support and to contribute to society, including in terms of environmental protection, supporting their own employees and carrying out charitable activities with financial subsidies. For example, participant G1 explained that:

Currently, as a member of government staff, I would like to emphasise that our government has provided many incentives to encourage companies to implement CSR in their companies; for example, Land Use Tax Relief, Personnel Training Subsidies and other kinds of financial benefit. (G1)

The second motivation for carrying out CSR proposed by this respondent is the company leader's willingness. If a company leader has a high level of education or conducts international business, they may have a strong awareness of CSR and understand the benefits their company can achieve by focusing on relevant activities. This type of motivation is known as autonomous consciousness.

Finally, it is undeniable that the pressure from the social media and increasing attention from the public constitute another motivation for companies to focus on their CSR practice. These factors mean that companies can gain public trust and make a positive impression, helping

them to maintain effective business operations. Meeting social needs is the government's responsibility towards the people. Thus, the government is accountable for setting up CSR policies and regulations as well as ensuring that companies obey these regulations and put them into effect. Participant G1 added that:

I would like to say that social media has been a big driver. Our government has pressure from social media that we have to improve our CSR regulations to match the international level and have a responsibility to supervise other organisations' implementation of CSR. (G1)

2. Current CSR situation

In terms of this issue, participant G1 stated that:

The current CSR situation is getting better; more and more companies are realising the importance and benefits of carrying out CSR. However, there are many difficulties and obstacles involved in asking any companies, whether large, medium or small, to implement CSR. (G1)

Although carrying out CSR activities will benefit a company in the long run, there are costs involved in implementing them. As a result, it may cost too much for even large companies to implement some CSR activities, and small companies are even more reluctant to implement CSR practices or at least are not willing to cost any to carry out CSR. The respondent highlighted that, in consideration of this issue, current government policies mainly aim to encourage companies to carry out CSR activities, as discussed further below.

3. Government policies for improvement of CSR practice in China

Currently, the government mainly supports and encourages companies to implement positive CSR practices. First, in order to encourage companies to carry out CSR activities, some preferential policies have been introduced such as **Land Use Tax Relief**, **exemptions** and **profit tax reductions**. The government provides these incentive policies out of consideration

for the monetary cost of implementing CSR. Companies may have more willingness to spend money on CSR activities if they will see cost reductions and thus save money in other ways.

Second, training courses and education classes are provided by some government departments, including the General Administration of Quality Supervision and the Environmental Protection Administration. The government realise that it has a responsibility to offer the latest information and guide companies to fulfil their social responsibility. However, this will only be effective if the government also pays attention to strengthening regulations, plays an effective guiding role and provides meaningful support.

Finally, the participating government staff member also indicated that companies that break the regulations receive penalties. For example, if a company fails to comply with the requirements regarding sewage discharge equipment and causes pollution, it will be penalised by the Environmental Protection Administration. However, the respondent kept emphasising that, although there are penalties, the main method used is that of encouragement. When asked about the reason for this, she stated that the current CSR level in China is underdeveloped, overall consciousness of CSR is low, and many managers and employees in companies may not completely understand what CSR is and what to do to comply with the relevant requirements. Therefore, returning to the previous point, it is the government's responsibility to improve the development of CSR by enhancing publicity and education campaigns.

5.1.4 Results from participants' responses – consumers

The total number of consumers participating in the study is ten. Figure 5.2 shows the categories and the frequency with which each was discussed in these ten cases.

Figure 5. 2 Categories and frequency of mentions from consumers' responses

	A : Case 10	B : Case 11	C : Case 12	D : Case 13	E : Case 14	F : Case 15	G : Case 16	H : Case 17	I : Case 8	J : Case 9
1 : CSR concept	1	2	0	1	2	1	2	1	1	1
2 : CSR current situation	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1
3 : CSR development history	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4 : CSR disclosure format	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 : CSR disclosure level	0	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
6 : CSR practice - Economic	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7 : CSR practice - Employment	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8 : CSR practice - Environment	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9 : CSR practice - Philanthropy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10 : CSR practice - Product	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11 : CSR practice - social human rights	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12 : CSR practice - social society	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13 : Government policies	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14 : Improvement approach	3	1	5	2	1	6	3	2	5	5
15 : Most important social responsibilities	2	0	3	1	1	1	1	2	0	2
16 : Motivation	2	1	3	1	2	2	2	3	0	1
17 : Obstacles	0	2	2	1	1	2	1	4	3	2
18 : Suggestion to the research	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0

Valuable information from these findings with respect to the research objectives is discussed below.

1. Current CSR disclosure level

The consumers' responses regarding CSR disclosure can be summarised as reflecting the view that it is at a low level and underdeveloped, but it is improving. For example, C2, C3 and C11 stated that:

I think recently the CSR performance has improved in China. But that is hardly to say the level of CSR performance or disclosure is high. I prefer to say that there are a lot of things that are needed to be done. (C2)

Participant C3 mentioned that:

I know, nowadays, the social media talks about food safety all the time. As a consumer, I can see that more and more people are raising the awareness of CSR; however, I have to say that we do not have a fully comprehensive concept or knowledge of CSR. I would like to say we have a lot of things to learn from the Western counties. (C3)

Additionally, Participant C11 said:

I hardly to know the CSR reports. I would like to say I have never been aware of CSR reports from any food companies. I had no idea about this kind of report before you asked me this question. Therefore, I think the current CSR performance in China must

be at a very low level. (C11)

2. Consumers' awareness

Some respondents stated that they had no idea about CSR and did not even know about the concept before participating in this study. In preparation for the interview, they did some research into CSR and then realised that the development of CSR in China has a long way to go. They have barely heard of CSR reports being disclosed by food companies. Although they agree that many companies conduct philanthropic activities, they do not think these companies fully understand CSR or comply by the requirements to meet international standards. However, they are in agreement that CSR practice in China has been developing and improving in recent years due to increased social discussion as well as the increased concern of the public following the exposure of food scandals.

Participant C6 is a chief financial officer, and C7 is a vice president of a finance department.

Both of them demonstrated a deep understanding of CSR. They expressed that:

I fully understand the knowledge of CSR as it is also a part of what we need to work on now. (C6)

As a professional financial staff, we do not only work on financial reports; we also need to work together with colleagues and clients to consider their CSR activities. Particularly in a large company, it seems to be a trend that you have to show your CSR performance. (C7)

Participants C4 and C8 are university staff members – a professor and a lecturer, respectively.

They also showed a good level of awareness of CSR. On the other hand, C11 and C5 showed a limited knowledge of CSR. This reflects that participants with high levels of education or who work in a relevant field had better awareness of CSR.

In my University, as a lecture, I am required to attach some personal development courses. There are some relevant CSR information I have learned about. (C4)

3. Motivation to concern the CSR

In the interviews with consumers, they were asked why they concern the CSR activities of companies in the Chinese food industry. It is noticeable that all these respondents stated that they started to be concerned with this issue due to the food scandals exposed on social media.

The exposure of food scandals has increased consumers' general attention towards food quality and safety. Our consumer respondents understand that costs rise with improved quality and that costs of products increase when a company conducts more CSR activities. However, they would still be more willing to buy products from companies with better CSR performance as they place more trust in such companies. For example, participant C11 said:

To be honest, I cannot say I know what CSR is. But after your explanation, I would like to say that I definitely pay attention to CSR due to the news always reporting some food safety scandals. (C11)

As participant C2 added:

Regarding the particular food companies, I am care of their CSR activities because I believe only a responsible company may produce responsible products for consumers. I am willing to buy a product at a higher price if the company has better CSR performance. (C2)

Another motivation is that, with the general improvement of quality of life, people are paying more attention to other issues, including the natural environment, personal health, the next generation's interests, their working environment, etc. All these factors are related to CSR and mean that consumers have increasing demands in terms of companies' performance. They prefer to see that companies not only pursuit profits but also contribute to society through specific and meaningful activities. For example, participant C10 stated that:

I would like to say Chinese people have wealth and resources now. People are getting wealthier and it's life-changing. We began to pursue a high-quality life. We would like to support companies that are responsible and to resist companies who are irresponsible. (C10)

4. Obstacles to conducting CSR activities in China

Our consumer respondents provided valuable information in relation to this question. It seems that they feel more freedom to discuss this question and point out the actual problems that they believe exist.

The first obstacle is based on the lack of a standardised system and any guidance and discipline from the government. It is hard to count on all companies to autonomously operate a CSR policy and conduct appropriate CSR practices. The government should be the first executor to supervise companies. Currently, the Chinese government does not have a specific department that is in charge of CSR development and operations.

Furthermore, the penalties for companies that fail to meet CSR requirements (such as by breaking safety regulations or polluting the environment) are inadequate. Directors or managers thus have no fear of the consequences of not complying with the government's CSR policies. Some of the consumer respondents suggested that any companies that cause social harm – for example, by produce unsafe food products – should suffer severe penalties and their managers or directors must be severely punished such as with imprisonment or restrictions to or prohibition of operating their business. For example, participant C5 stated:

I feel that even when some scandals happened, the government just shut down their factories. I barely hear that they have received severe punishment. I even believe that these bosses can just reopen another factory to produce unqualified products again.
(C5)

Third, companies often aim to pursue profits rather than to spend money on carrying out CSR activities. Our consumer respondents believe that some companies' managers have an awareness of CSR but prefer to ignore it to save money and thus improve their profits to satisfy stakeholders' requirements. For example, participant C1 said:

In China, CSR is not a new term. It exists everywhere. Decision makers of companies definitely know the importance of CSR; however, due to the cost, they may prefer to ignore it so that they can pursue higher profits. (C1)

Another factor that causes an obstacle to conducting CSR practice is company managers lacking knowledge of the field. From the interviews with managers and the analysis results of the scorecard, it seems that managers have a general awareness about the importance of employee benefits, philanthropic activities and actions to protect the environment. However, they may not fully comprehend CSR. For example, CSR practice also includes organisational structure, a balanced ratio between female and male employees, activities to counter corruption, staff training and education, after-sales service, etc. Additionally, it is part of a company's CSR to disclose its CSR information via specific or integrated reports. However, research so far suggests that the general awareness of CSR across the whole of Chinese society is relatively poor. For example, participant C10 is a lecturer who teaches a module that is relevant to CSR. He stated the following:

I am teaching the module of Enterprise Engineer. CSR is one of the topics I put on my syllabus. The students are supposed to learn how to be a qualified enterprise engineer in different industries such as food companies, oil companies, the garment manufacturing industry and so on. CSR is inevitable content that they have to learn. (C10)

Moreover, they added that:

Only when everyone from the top to bottom of a company, the government to the general public, and the highly educated population to the general standard living population have an awareness of CSR may the overall level of CSR performance in China be improved.

5. Improvement approaches

The improvement approaches proposed by the consumers are in line with the previous section. In other words, the consumers made suggestions for improvement based on the identified obstacles. As participant C10 advised, providing CSR courses to senior-level managers and

government staff should be the first step towards actually increasing overall CSR knowledge. Only when top-level managers comprehensively realise the benefits to be gained by implementing CSR will they become more interested in spending time and money to do so.

Furthermore, participant C10 stated that:

Since 2017, all postgraduate students in China must attend a course named Engineering Ethics. (C10)

First, the term ‘engineering’ here refers to various industries, not just to engineers in the traditional sense. For example, in the food industry, the people who design and create new food products are called food design engineers. Engineering ethics is the set of rules and guidelines that engineers adhere to, based on a moral obligation to their profession and to the word. It is very important and applies to every type of engineer (Cohen, McDaniels and Qualter, 2005; Bowen, 2009). From this module, students learn how engineering ethics apply within various industries. For example, companies have to be aware of their CSR. It is a company’s responsibility to contribute to the society and community that it profits from and to behave ethically for the benefit of both the company and its community. The module is designed to increase postgraduate students’ knowledge of safety, health, property and public welfare. This type of education can fundamentally raise the awareness of CSR and ultimately improve CSR practice in China.

Other improvement approaches have been discussed similarly as above, including: 1) increasing the intensity of penalties; 2) improving laws and regulations; 3) stepping up social media publicity; and 4) governmental encouragement of companies to carry out CSR activities.

5.2 Summary of findings

In summary, the results from the four groups of participants' show that they have some awareness of CSR, but that the level of this awareness is relatively low and their knowledge in this field is insufficient. Their main motivations come from social media, the government and self-efficacy; however, the high costs of undertaking the CSR activities and the lack of a standardised system, guidance and discipline from the government are resulting in slow CSR development. A brief summary of the findings follows in Table 5.1.

This study's findings explain the connection between the Harmonious approach and Shareholder theory, Legitimacy theory and Institutional theory, which can explain the motivations and challenges to carry out CSR practice and disclose CSR information, discussed as below.

First of all, in order to as much as possible to improve the quality of people's livelihood, food companies have responsibilities to carry out their economic responsibilities, and also they are expected to contribute to the rapid and stable development of the national economy. Reducing costs, increasing sales, making correct business decisions are regarded as the most direct way to make financial profits.

In China, the harmonious approach means to love and respect people as well as nature. The core idea of Stakeholder theory clearly asserts that companies have a corporate social responsibility to stakeholders (Gray et al., 1996; Roberts, 1992). Stakeholder theory can be categorised as descriptive, instrumental and normative (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Among these, the normative approach is to find a 'normative core' for stakeholder theory; that is, to find an abstract category to prove its rationality. The 'normative core', as proposed by different

scholars, takes on different meanings; for instance, Freeman (1994) proposed the ‘Doctrine of Fair Contracts’, wherein Stakeholder theory refers to an Ethic of Care, or Ecological principles. Donaldson and Dunfee (1999) suggested ‘Comprehensive Social Contracts’, which holds that a code of conduct is generated from the common goals, ideas and attitudes of a people or society to maintain the moral order of that society. According to Carroll’s CSR Pyramid model, philanthropic responsibility is one of the big four responsibilities of a company to be a good corporate citizen (Carroll, 1991).

Secondly, food companies have the contractual obligations to the society. They are expected and required to legally operate business activities by complying with the Labour Protection Law, the Law on Environmental Protection, and Consumer Protection Act. In addition, food companies have the responsibilities to encourage and supervise their employees to carry out work in accordance with local laws and regulations.

In China, to construct a harmonious society, companies are required by legislation to carry out their business activities with consideration of their stakeholders, shareholders, the environment and many other aspects. Per the Legal driver and Political driver as stated in Chapter 2, CSR is incorporated into Chinese legal system; in particular, large companies are required and expected to obey the law. Bansal and Clelland (2004) and Suchman (1995) noted that, in order to achieve legitimacy, companies are required to obey the law, policies, rules, guides, norms and public expectations, while the legal systems are completed by well-established and implemented. However, Peng (2003), Zhou and Poppo (2010) and Wei, Shen, Zhou and Li (2015) have argued that, in developing countries exhibiting a transitional economy, legitimacy performance among companies is challenged by legal inefficiency and incompleteness. Such research has found that the top 100 food companies show a certain degree of CSR performance

because they aim to follow political and legal rules; however, an incomplete and inefficient legal system weakens China's food companies' CSR performance, as reflected in the Scorecard result of low-level CSR performance.

As the findings of this research are based on a Chinese context, they also show the impact of political strategies on companies. This study adds to the literature on legitimacy, especially political legitimacy, as Zhao (2012) noted that CSR is a non-ignorable political strategy to achieve political legitimacy. To improve business performance, it is critical for companies to obtain political legitimacy. In addition, business and political legitimacy enable companies to benefit from government support and help them avoid excessive government intervention. As China has a developing economy, the government has considerable power to allocate resources to individuals, institutions and certain departments. Such crucial resources include governmental funding, the right of land use and preferential tax policy (Sheng et al., 2011; Ahlstrom and Bruton, 2008; Bai et al., 2006).

Thirdly, the important task of constructing a harmonious society is to vigorously develop social undertakings and ensure the balanced development of economy and environment. The stability and harmony of the society and the direct interest of the people depend on the development of social security, education, medical and health care and other social infrastructure. To become a good corporate citizen, food companies in China are expected to fully develop their capital advantages to carry out charitable activities and give back to the society. The contribution can effectively support the development of community education, local infrastructure and construction, culture and many others. In terms of Institutional theory, a company with a certain institutional characteristic must make a certain choice of action. The construction of a harmonious society depends on the sociocultural expectations of that society; hence, pressure

can be forceful, persuasive or inviting collusion (Mizruchi and Fein, 1999; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

The Institutional theory observes that modern organisations show great similarity in form and practice, and, once an organisational field is formed, a strong motivation of homogeneity will be generated (Kondra and Hinings, 1998; Deephouse, 1996; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). The most appropriate concept for understanding this phenomenon is isomorphism, which refers to similarities in structure and practice between an organisation and other organisations in the same environment. Types of isomorphism include coercive, mimetic and normative isomorphism (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Extant theories state that coercive is closely related to the Stakeholder theory (Dillard et al., 2004). In addition, one company within an industry association, due to their common goals and values, will exhibit imitative behaviour, and this company will follow or imitate the innovations of other companies to maintain legitimacy and competitive advantage (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). According to mimetic isomorphism, an organisation mimics the legitimacy or more successful behaviour of another organisation due to the uncertainty of its environment (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Therefore, mimetic isomorphism is closely related to Legitimacy theory (Dillard et al., 2004).

According to the in-depth interviews, four groups of interviewees showed their awareness of CSR (high awareness from managers); however, they also noted that it is not easy to fully implement CSR policies. It is interesting that the participating managers were reluctant to discuss the reasons of the difficulties; however, according to other groups of participants, the reasons include the high cost of implementing CSR activities and strategies, non-standard systems and lack of guidance and discipline from the government, and inadequate punishment for lack of compliance. Luo (2011) argued that companies expecting to perform their social

responsibilities are influenced by external institutions, such as other industrial companies, and are responding to social norms, rules and regulations. These companies understand that abiding by social norms will result in further value, because those companies that contribute to society via ethical behaviour will be regarded as trustworthy.

Jamili and Neville (2011) suggested that CSR activities are culturally defined; thus, as the context of this research is China, the unique perspectives of Chinese CSR are considered. Giddens (1995) stated that it is becoming increasingly significant that socially responsible companies exhibit ethical behaviour to achieve important global positions. Moreover, it is critical that companies in transitional economies develop an attitude of social responsibility and consciousness, even under current or potential prevalence and pressure of unethical activities by other institutions. According to the managers' responses in this thesis (5.1.1, 3. Motivations for conducting CSR activities), companies conduct CSR largely influenced by other companies and social trends. They are willing to follow the tide of society, but they do not correctly and fully adopt CSR.

This phenomenon and data results reflect the decoupling strategy introduced and explained via theories section (2.5.3 Institutional theory). Decoupling is a common strategy adopted by organisations to coordinate conflicting institutional requirements, aiding organisations in hiding the non-compliance behind the surface compliance and, to a certain extent, helping to alleviate the pressure caused by the external institutional environment; thus, the organisation can achieve both legitimacy and efficiency. In China's institutional environment, due to different interests, institutional influence and cultural and historical reasons, there are some institutional phenomena, such as lack of government order, variation in execution, difficulty in coordination, frequent changes in government order, and prevalence of unwritten rules. This

research found that most Chinese food companies are only formally participating in CSR activities, rather than fully understand all their responsibilities in various aspects.

Table 5. 1 Summary of in-depth interview findings

	Manager	General Employees	Government Staff	Consumers
CSR situation	Not quite at a high level, but improved	Low level	Improving	Low level
Awareness	High awareness, but not easy to implement	Have some awareness, but not a full understanding	High awareness, but need to learn more	Have some awareness, but not a full understanding
Motivations	1. Company reputation 2. Pressures from social media and peers 3. Government regulations	1. Self-benefits	1. Development needs 2. Companies' willingness 3. Pressures from social media and the public	1. Self-benefits
Obstacles	Barely discussed	Cost	Barely discussed	1. Non-standard system and lack of guidance and discipline from the government 2. Inadequate penalties 3. High costs
Improvement	1. Education 2. Improve regulations and policies	Education	1. Encourage policies 2. Education and training 3. Punishment	1. Education 2. Social media 3. Government policies 4. Intensify penalties

Chapter 6 Discussion and Conclusion

The aim of this thesis is to study the current CSR disclosing level of China's food industry and to explore the motivations and obstacles to conduct CSR practice. In consequence, the research aim to achieve the following three objectives:

1. To undertake a quantitative study by developing a measurement instrument – Scorecard (content analysis) to explore the scale of the current level and situation of CSR of China's food industry;
2. To undertake a qualitative study by in-depth interviews to explore the motivations and challenges to carry out CSR practice and disclose CSR information.
3. To offer practical improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and comprehension of CSR in China's food industry.

As objective 3 specifies, this study offers practical improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and comprehension of CSR in China's food industry. Hence, this chapter aims to discuss the study findings in the light of research objectives and theoretical approaches.

6.1 Discussion of Research Findings

From the content analysis result, in the light of Objective 1, the research findings show that the Philanthropic index is the category that food companies in China would like to disclose more, both large and small companies. Also, the Environment index is the most widely disclosed category. Through above two most disclosed categories, companies show their charitable activities and public spirit. The literature review (section 2.3.1 The three-stage development of CSR in China) also reveals that CSR, which is not new to China, has a long development history and is changing with the times. There is a three-stage development of CSR within China,

starting with **Traditional CSR – Confucianism**, moving to **Modern CSR** and then on to the **Scientific Development Concept** and **the Construction of a Harmonious Society**. Wang and Juslin (2009) proposed a new definition of CSR, called the Chinese harmony approach. They examined CSR via traditional Chinese culture and philosophy. In this thesis, the current data obtained from the Scorecard can show that the primary reason for China's companies to apply CSR is to contribute to a harmonious society (Wang and Juslin, 2009). The concept of CSR among Chinese firms and markets is rooted in traditional Confucianism. In order to better adapt to the government's policy of constructing a harmonious society, Chinese companies are expected to exhibit social responsibility. This thesis adds to the extant knowledge of the Chinese harmony approach, revealing that companies in China carry out their CSR activities to show their concerns for nature and kindness to people.

The content analysis also show that liquor companies have a stronger performance compared to other food product companies in China. This phenomenon can be explained by the **legitimacy theory**. As liquor companies produce alcoholic products, regarded as harmful to human health, the Chinese public (both consumers and the government) expects the liquor companies to contribute to society more to gain the public's confidence as well as to compensate the public. Liquor companies attempt to comply with recognisable and acceptable standards to cultivate an organisational legitimacy. Moreover, **institutional theory** suggests that better CSR performance results in another important effect, which both coercive and normative isomorphism can effectively explain. *Coercive isomorphism* derives from the formal or informal pressure exerted by other organisations on which a company depends as well as the sociocultural expectations of that society. This pressure can be forceful, persuasive, or inviting collusion (Mizruchi and Fein, 1999; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Many neighbourhood organisations in urban communities form organisational hierarchies in order to

gain support from other hierarchical aid organisations and others. In addition, *normative isomorphism* refers to the behaviour required by the normative expectations of the professional community. In other words, it is mainly derived from professionalisation, that is, the formal education and legalisation based on the cognition created by the university and the development and deepening of a career network that permeates the organisation, so the new model can spread rapidly (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). China's alcoholic drinks association's Science and Technology awards were established on 20th October 2011 to encourage and reward liquor companies who have contributed to production technology, equipment designs, energy conservation and emission reduction, environmental protection, technical innovation and development. In order to survive competition, they comply with laws and policies and follow the trend of their peers.

In light of Objective 2, this study's findings explain the connection between the Harmonious approach and **Shareholder theory**, **Legitimacy theory** and **Institutional theory**, which can explain the motivations to carry out CSR practice and disclose CSR information, discussed as below.

First of all, in order to as much as possible to improve the quality of people's livelihood, food companies have responsibilities to carry out their economic responsibilities, and also they are expected to contribute to the rapid and stable development of the national economy. Reducing costs, increasing sales, making correct business decisions are regarded as the most direct way to make financial profits.

In China, the harmonious approach means to love and respect people as well as nature. The core idea of **Stakeholder theory** clearly asserts that companies have a corporate social

responsibility to stakeholders (Gray et al., 1996; Roberts, 1992). Stakeholder theory can be categorised as descriptive, instrumental and normative (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Among these, the normative approach is to find a ‘normative core’ for stakeholder theory; that is, to find an abstract category to prove its rationality. The ‘normative core’, as proposed by different scholars, takes on different meanings; for instance, Freeman (1994) proposed the ‘Doctrine of Fair Contracts’, wherein Stakeholder theory refers to an Ethic of Care, or Ecological principles. Donaldson and Dunfee (1999) suggested ‘Comprehensive Social Contracts’, which holds that a code of conduct is generated from the common goals, ideas and attitudes of a people or society to maintain the moral order of that society. According to Carroll’s CSR Pyramid model, philanthropic responsibility is one of the big four responsibilities of a company to be a good corporate citizen (Carroll, 1991).

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implemented. However, Peng (2003), Zhou and Poppo (2010) and Wei, Shen, Zhou and Li (2015) have argued that, in developing countries exhibiting a transitional economy, legitimacy performance among companies is challenged by legal inefficiency and incompleteness. Such research has found that the top 100 food companies show a certain degree of CSR performance because they aim to follow political and legal rules; however, an incomplete and inefficient legal system weakens China's food companies' CSR performance, as reflected in the Scorecard result of low-level CSR performance.

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Thirdly, the important task of constructing a harmonious society is to vigorously develop social undertakings and ensure the balanced development of economy and environment. The stability and harmony of the society and the direct interest of the people depend on the development of social security, education, medical and health care and other social infrastructure. To become a good corporate citizen, food companies in China are expected to fully develop their capital advantages to carry out charitable activities and give back to the society. The contribution can

effectively support the development of community education, local infrastructure and construction, culture and many others. In terms of **Institutional theory**, a company with a certain institutional characteristic must make a certain choice of action. The construction of a harmonious society depends on the sociocultural expectations of that society; hence, pressure can be forceful, persuasive or inviting collusion (Mizruchi and Fein, 1999; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

The Institutional theory observes that modern organisations show great similarity in form and practice, and, once an organisational field is formed, a strong motivation of homogeneity will be generated (Kondra and Hinings, 1998; Deephouse, 1996; DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). The most appropriate concept for understanding this phenomenon is isomorphism, which refers to similarities in structure and practice between an organisation and other organisations in the same environment. Types of isomorphism include coercive, mimetic and normative isomorphism (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Extant theories state that coercive is closely related to the Stakeholder theory (Dillard et al., 2004). In addition, one company within an industry association, due to their common goals and values, will exhibit imitative behaviour, and this company will follow or imitate the innovations of other companies to maintain legitimacy and competitive advantage (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). According to mimetic isomorphism, an organisation mimics the legitimacy or more successful behaviour of another organisation due to the uncertainty of its environment (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Therefore, mimetic isomorphism is closely related to Legitimacy theory (Dillard et al., 2004).

According to the results of both of the content analysis and interview results, there is another interesting phenomenon is worth to think about: the category of philanthropic responsibility, which is the third-largest disclosure category. This category measures issues relating to

companies' philanthropic activities, including donations to the local community, natural disaster areas and assistance to employee experiencing difficulties. This phenomenon shows that China's food companies pay attention to their stakeholders; although some may not be closely related to their economic profits, the companies still offer help and assistance to demonstrate their kindness and generosity. This phenomenon reflects how Chinese culture and society are largely shaped by Confucianism, the harmonious society, as it is known today.

However, the other categories from the Scorecard, including Product responsibility and– Social: human rights and D9 – Social: society, show poor CSR performance. In terms of Stakeholder theory and the content explained in Chapter 3, section 3.1.2, there is a connection between the Carroll's CSR Pyramid model and Stakeholder theory. However, the data analysis results do not show this connection. A plausible explanation for this phenomenon is managers' incomplete and unsound consciousness and knowledge concerning CSR. China's food companies do not fully understand the code of conduct for CSR. They give to charity because of the benevolence of the Chinese culture and meet the social expectations to build harmonious society but, in the actual implementation of CSR, they do not specify the specific code of conduct, implementation objects, purposes, process, need, and specific requirements according to the law or social expectations.

In addition, this phenomenon is also reflected in by the in-depth interview findings. According to the in-depth interviews, four groups of interviewees showed their awareness of CSR (high awareness from managers); however, they also noted that it is not easy to fully implement CSR policies. It is interesting that the participating managers were reluctant to discuss the reasons of the difficulties; however, according to other groups of participants, the reasons include the high cost of implementing CSR activities and strategies, non-standard systems and lack of

guidance and discipline from the government, and inadequate punishment for lack of compliance. Luo (2011) argued that companies expecting to perform their social responsibilities are influenced by external institutions, such as other industrial companies, and are responding to social norms, rules and regulations. These companies understand that abiding by social norms will result in further value, because those companies that contribute to society via ethical behaviour will be regarded as trustworthy.

Jamili and Neville (2011) suggested that CSR activities are culturally defined; thus, as the context of this research is China, the unique perspectives of Chinese CSR are considered. Giddens (1995) stated that it is becoming increasingly significant that socially responsible companies exhibit ethical behaviour to achieve important global positions. Moreover, it is critical that companies in transitional economies develop an attitude of social responsibility and consciousness, even under current or potential prevalence and pressure of unethical activities by other institutions. According to the managers' responses in this thesis (5.1.1, 3. Motivations for conducting CSR activities), companies conduct CSR largely influenced by other companies and social trends. They are willing to follow the tide of society, but they do not correctly and fully adopt CSR.

This phenomenon and data results reflect the **decoupling** strategy introduced and explained via theories section (2.5.3 Institutional theory). Decoupling is a common strategy adopted by organisations to coordinate conflicting institutional requirements, aiding organisations in hiding the non-compliance behind the surface compliance and, to a certain extent, helping to alleviate the pressure caused by the external institutional environment; thus, the organisation can achieve both legitimacy and efficiency. In China's institutional environment, due to different interests, institutional influence and cultural and historical reasons, there are some

institutional phenomena, such as lack of government order, variation in execution, difficulty in coordination, frequent changes in government order, and prevalence of unwritten rules. This research found that most Chinese food companies are only formally participating in CSR activities, rather than fully understand all their responsibilities in various aspects.

According to the interview results, many Chinese food companies use a 'Greenwash' (also called 'Whitewash' in China) to repair their brand reputation and improve their company's public image by promoting their products and companies' aims or policies as environmentally friendly (Ramusand Montiel, 2016; Marquis and Qian, 2014; Laufer, 2003). The evidence indicating that companies are Greenwashing can be seen from the 'green' advertising rather than time or money spent on practical action. If CSR disclosure is compulsory, it could be set up to maximise the perception of legitimacy; the more details disclosed, the more practical activities are required. However, the results suggest that the incomplete and inefficient legal system and the absence of external supervision and verification lead to 'Greenwash' strategies among Chinese companies. Why Chinese food do companies 'Greenwash'? Because they are facing reputational risks, being criticised heavily by the public media (Seele and Gatti, 2017). A series of food scandals has given rise to government and consumer concerns; consequently, the food companies receive pressure and are eager to prove that they are responsible companies and produce healthy and safe food. However, regulations, laws, policies, and guides have not been set up completely, resulting in companies showing their philanthropic responsibilities by conducting charitable activities rather than spending large amounts of money on 'green' investments, such as investing in technologies to minimise environmental pollution or using better raw materials to produce high-quality food products. This happens because customers and the public rarely see technology investments, but charitable activities are apparent via the media, thus making companies look responsible. Therefore, it is an easy and quick way to

promote a company's image. However, it needs to be noticed that, when 'greenwashing' is revealed and exposed, related companies also suffer from greater scepticism and lowered public confidence. From this point, the Chinese government and related supervising bodies and lawmakers have a greater responsibility to establish complete and sufficient CSR regulations. This finding is also link with Scorecard result.

6.2 Conclusion

This sections includes five sub-sections. The first section contains policy recommendations that are considered in this chapter. The second section examines the managerial implications of this study. The third section discusses future studies and limitations regarding this study. The fourth section is a discussion of originality. The fifth section is the summary and conclusion of this research.

6.2.1 Policy Recommendations

Based on the above discussions of the current CSR disclosure situation in China's food industry and summaries of the problems existing in CSR reports, this section puts forward some reasonable suggestions for the CSR report disclosures in China's food industry. These are believed to have particular guiding significance for the further development of CSR in China.

1. To introduce mandatory disclosure requirements on food companies to disclose their CSR information

Interview results show that it is voluntary to disclose CSR information as a government requirement. This situation leads most food companies to evade the disclosure of social responsibility information and not actively disclose CSR reports. In this respect, the

government should strengthen its mandatory information disclosure requirements to all food companies. On the one hand, voluntary disclosure should be strongly advocated. On the other hand, a mandatory disclosure system could be gradually established, guaranteed by an external force. For example, some important information (e.g. food additives) that will affect consumers' interests (e.g. health) directly should be strictly implemented as mandatory information disclosure. Other information that might not directly affect consumers' interests can be encouraged to be voluntarily disclosed, and incentives (e.g. business tax concessions) could be considerable. In addition, it is suggested that food companies that have insufficient food safety and potential safety risks be required to disclose their CSR information by improving the current laws and regulations. By enhancing the authenticity of the disclosed CSR information and increasing the enthusiasm of public supervision, food companies can be made to disclose valuable CSR reports.

2. To perfect the content of CSR reports and disclosure methods for food companies

The information disclosed in CSR reports should be comprehensive and extensive, and should not be limited to one aspect, or deliberately conceal important information. It also should not be disclosed in a broad sense. The information disclosed should have the characteristics of its industry and build its own model. Food companies should not only disclose the same information as general industries, such as the protection of interests of shareholders and employees, the responsibility of consumers and community government and resource consumption, but also, in order to avoid the contents of the CSR reports from food companies being confused with other industries, it is suggested that an independent disclosure mechanism should be set up, and the report be published regularly (e.g. yearly). Therefore, the situation of information ambiguity can be changed, and the value and effectiveness of the CSR reports disclosed by the food industry can be improved in time. In view of the single information

disclosure method of China's food industry, companies should increase the disclosure of some digital information on the basis of the existing written description, which can make the report more scientific and convincing.

The research findings show the social responsibility accounting started relatively late in China, and relevant theories and practical operations are still in the exploratory stage. No consensus has been reached on basic issues related to social responsibility accounting, such as accounting subjects, accounting period, recognition principles, measurement form and methods, let alone the practical operating system. In the future, the Chinese government should strengthen social and material support to universities, research institutes/groups, and other theoretical research institutions to promote exchanges and cooperation among the various academic organisations, conduct in-depth research on the recognition principles, measurement standards and reporting forms of CSR matters, and promote the diversification and standardisation of contents and forms of CSR report disclosures.

3. To strengthen supervision on CSR information disclosure and set up a specialised food company CSR management agency in China

First of all, the Chinese government should learn lessons from the successful examples of Western countries and reform the current CSR disclosure system for food companies to make them realise the importance of disclosing the authenticity of the information.

Second, it is suggested that food companies set up an internal department to be in charge of their CSR development and activities from the inside to inspect the implementation of CSR, supervision and evaluation, to ensure that the food company itself fulfils its social obligations.

At the same time, this department can ensure the CSR information is regularly disclosed to the public. This not only improves the professionalism of information disclosure but also helps prevent cheating by other for-profit departments.

In addition, as well as internal guarantees, the government should set up relevant regulators to further verify the authenticity and effectiveness of the information disclosed by food companies. Once again, it is necessary to promote the establishment of a complete social responsibility auditing system as soon as possible, to increase the authenticity and effectiveness of the CSR reports produced by China's food companies. This is to enable consumers and relevant departments to evaluate the fulfilment of their social responsibilities better. KPMG (2015) states in its CSR research report: CSR reports should be guaranteed by independent verification (auditing and assurance). However, from the research results of the scorecard in Section C, it is clear that from the top 20 companies, only 22% of CSR reports have been reviewed by external assurance and 20% of CSR reports have been reviewed by internal assurance. The companies ranked from 21st to 50th and 51st to 100th had nearly no external assurance, and only 2% to 5% internal assurance. Independent third-party verification of CSR information has become a standard practice for large companies worldwide. According to the 2015 KPMG study, companies in the following countries/regions are most likely to independently verify their CSR reports: France (96%), South Korea (86%), Greece (70%), Taiwan (70%) and the UK (61%).

The interview results show that most food companies lack awareness of CSR and have a weak sense of autonomy, resulting in their cognition of CSR report disclosures still being in the initial stage. Most companies pay attention to their current interests but do not see the long-term impact of social responsibility performance, which makes them very likely to give up the

fulfilment of social responsibilities because of short-term economic interests. It seems that it is particularly important to establish a social responsibility management agency for food companies. The management here is not only about the supervision of information disclosure but also the promotion of the knowledge of the importance of conducting CSR practices and disclosing CSR information. It not only helps protect shareholders but also prevents consumers, employees, the government and the public interest from being harmed. It enables food companies to recognise and treat CSR as work and important business, which is beneficial for companies to truly incorporate the implementation of CSR into all aspects of daily business activities and ensure its implementation.

Finally, supervision should be strengthened by conducting regular inspections or checks. The inspection and enforcement departments should strictly punish food companies that fail to disclose CSR information or disclose inaccurate information. In recent years, the Accounting Law, Company Law, Securities Law and other laws and regulations have standardised the CSR disclosure from different perspectives. The Shenzhen Stock Exchange and Shanghai Stock Exchange also enacted The Guidelines on CSR Disclosure of Listed Companies and The Guidelines on Environmental Information Disclosure of Listed Companies, respectively, and other notices to encourage listed companies to disclose CSR information on a regular basis (Xu, 2016). However, the characteristics of the food industry in China, with its small scale, large number, high dispersion and weak capacity, have resulted in these regulations and norms and laws being limited to a very small number of listed companies, and most of their CSR reports are merely formal. At present, most food companies in China are short of practical and applicable regulations and laws to lead them to carry out CSR.

4. To strengthen education and raise awareness of CSR

Improving and developing citizens' (including children, students, young, middle-aged, employees and managers) awareness of CSR is a complicated systematic project. Only when all citizens have a higher awareness of CSR can a harmonious society be realised. Along with the perfection of CSR contents and the improvement of regulations/laws related to CSR, educating citizens to comply with CSR regulations/laws becomes a significant problem in CSR theory and practice.

Modern society and the market economy require subject consciousness, participation consciousness, right consciousness and supervisory consciousness. They require active participation in public life, the courage to fight for and defend rights. For example, in the interview with an interviewee who is a university lecturer (Case 15 – interviewee code is C8), they stated that:

I am a university lecturer, and one of the course I am teaching is Enterprise Engineering Ethics... as we may of know that in the European and American countries, for the enterprise engineer, that is to say, or they want to pass the engineer certificate, they must be under the education of engineering ethics. However, in China, there is no such requirement. From last year, the major universities in China began to carry out this education work. In other words, high education workers have the awareness that the education is important. Our students who might be future enterprise engineers should realise what they can bring to their companies and what role they are having for their companies, especially their roles of supervision on companies, as well as the CSR of individuals.

Therefore, education is an important part of improving CSR awareness in China. The current

social education should cultivate university students (not limited to) to have a kind of right consciousness. Only by cultivating ourselves as good citizens in a new era can we better transform society. When the consciousness of what is right increases, the awareness of CSR increases.

6.2.2 Managerial Implications

The content analysis provides China's food companies with information on how companies, government and the public evaluate their CSR performance. Using scorecard to self-assessment and monitor disclosure performance. It is important for China's food companies to improve their CSR performance by conducting various high-quality CSR practices while the Chinese government and the public are currently paying more attention, subject to increasing awareness and the pressure of the international situation. The scorecard is suggested to be used for the below purposes.

First, academic researchers can use the scorecard to assess CSR performance in their interested industries. By comparing the performance to identify advantages and disadvantages, they can generate appropriate recommendations to improve CSR performance. Furthermore, the scorecard can be used on a longitudinal basis, which means assessing their CSR performance after recommendations have been suggested. The purpose of this further action is to identify whether definite improvements have been made or whether customers' expectations have been reached. By employing the scorecard, it is helpful to identify the deficiency, then correct and improve.

Decision-makers in companies are also encouraged to use the scorecard to assess their own

performance. Referring to the increasingly fierce competition, both domestically and internationally, it is important for them to identify their weaknesses in order to make accurate decisions for their company's development.

As previously explained, the scorecard is designed based on G4 and CASS-CSR, which cannot be ignored. They are originally generated from Carroll's CSR Pyramid, which includes four parts: economic responsibilities, legal responsibilities, ethical responsibilities and philanthropic responsibilities. This pyramid model shows that companies not only need to create profits for shareholders but that they also need to comply with the law, ethical responsibilities, charitable responsibilities and ultimately become a good corporate citizen. Therefore, companies must bear in mind that good CSR performance requires the achievement of all these four aspects.

In-depth interviews can positively and comprehensively help academic researchers to understand the food industry. Participants who have the willingness to take part in the research are not only the people with the consciousness to contribute to the research but also those who are interested in the research area.

China's food industry should concentrate more not only on environmental or charitable activities but, particularly appropriate for large companies, aspects of governance and social issues (i.e. employment and human rights). One-sided CSR development cannot run for long and will result in other unexpected issues.

Also, China's food companies should carefully keep up with the social trends and target the demands of customers who genuinely wish to support companies that have better CSR performance. Food companies can benefit from costing on providing, for example, an excellent

working environment, high-quality products, social care activities, environmental protection and much more. Particularly for large companies, maintaining a good brand image and reputation can contribute to profitable long-term expectations.

In addition, the food companies should make more efforts to produce a positive environment in which the overall industry needs to develop CSR practice. Without an honest attempt to improve the CSR policies, China's food and other industries' efforts to improve their CSR performance will be ineffective.

Although the findings of this research are based on the Chinese context, these managerial implications may be suitable for other developing economies where CSR systems are not fully established. For example, Amaeshi et al. (2014) studied CSR in Nigeria and declared that institutional systems in Nigeria's companies are weak, and they should develop CSR in their firms to attain legitimacy. Also, Zhao (2012) stated that having studied CSR in Russia, both China and Russia show similar levels of uncertainty in their managerial systems.

6.2.3 Directions for further research

As a whole, further studies of this research topic are necessary. First of all, this study is for the food industry only; research instrument and findings are not suitable for other industries. For example, the oil industry or banking might have different results using the same research methods. Or the research methods used in this research might not apply to other industries.

The content analysis of this study also has future research needed. In the first place, this research decided to research only the top 100 food companies in China. Therefore, the research results may not apply to other groups of companies, such as small-medium companies, family

companies or small companies. The size of companies is determinant to the companies' perception of CSR performance, because of their limited knowledge, resources and what they could afford. Consequently, further research of CSR in China's food companies could expand to groups of different company sizes (large, medium or small) and different forms of companies (state-owned, private, family or listed). Also, a comparison of the above suggested groups would further enrich the understanding of CSR performance in China's food companies.

Secondly, the designed contents of the scorecard are not perfect. Although it is designed based on the GRI and CASS-CSR indexes, these two indexes are also updated and revised regularly. Hence, improving this scorecard for future or further research is necessary.

Furthermore, the data for scorecard was collected from selected top 100 companies on the basis of their 2011 annual turnover, brand influence and food safety status of market. However, this study did not divide the nature of companies (e.g. private/state-owned companies; listed/unlisted firms) to conduct a comparative analysis of their CSR performance results, since the regulations applied to different natures of companies are different and therefore the disclosures level and performance can result in different.

This study also generates ideas by conducting interviews with different groups of interviewees. In spite of high cost, there are below concerns discussed for future research.

Firstly, the interview bias. The participants may not tell the truth or may omit valuable information due to the position they hold (Maxwell, 2005; Kvale and Brinkmann, 2008; Chenail, 2011). The reasons for participants not always giving 'truthful' answers may be either intentional or unintentional (Gubrium and Holstein, 2003; Lincoln, 2005; Rubin and Rubin,

2006). With respect to the current research, the managers may have had intentional reasons for not wanting the researcher to know the actual answers because those responses make them feel uncomfortable, or perhaps even because the answer would damage their own position or their companies. In this case, they may have chosen to refuse to talk about certain things, to lie or to give inconsequential (meaningless) information. In addition, respondents may also be unintentional, because they really do not know it. This situation may result in their weak awareness of CSR.

Second are the difficulties of recording. An interview survey is voice communication between two parties. If the interviewees do not agree to use a live recording (such as by recording pen), there will be a high speed requirement on the writing down of the contents spoken by interviewees. However, interviewers who have no specialised shorthand training usually cannot record the conversation completely. A lot of information will tend to be left out by memorising and taking notes.

Finally, it is difficult to process data analysis. An interview survey has a flexible aspect, but it also increases the randomness of the survey process. Interviews respond differently and their answers varied from each other. This results in the challenge of processing and analysing the interview results. Hence, the quantitative analysis is regarded as difficult due to its low degree of standardisation.

6.2.4 Originality

The originality of this doctoral research is therefore employing mixed research methods, via quantitative and qualitative research to deeply study the CSR in China's food companies that has caused concern in China. The originalities of this research are in research topic, research

tool and data, discussed as below.

Originality in research topic

An extensive literature review method by viewing 554 articles (chapter 1.2) is employed to identify that there is no article about CSR in China's food industry from the top ten journals (see table 1.1). After the reform and opening-up, it can be seen that the China's food industry are developing rapidly. The development of China's food industry also contribute to the economic growth which is increasing year by year. However, as food companies are in large numbers, small scale, dispersed and less intensive, it is concerned that their quality and safety management ability is relatively low. The lack of ethical standards of merchants, the ineffective supervision from the government departments, the continuous food safety scandals happened in China, have resulted in the loss of public confidence in food companies, and damage of the international reputation in China's food industry. Therefore, the understanding, discussion, study, promotion and development of CSR in China's food industry are of great significance in terms of caring for people's well-being and rights, and the progress of society as a whole.

Originality in research instrument – Scorecard

This research employs a mixed-methods approach that includes quantitative and qualitative research methods to study the CSR in China's food companies. To perform quantitative research methods, a Scorecard is developed. The Scorecard is developed on the basis of the Guidelines on CSR reporting for Chinese Enterprises (CASS-CSR) and The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). This research instrument contained four sections. Section A recorded the company's name, while section B recorded the format of the CSR report format, i.e. stand-

alone CSR report, integrated report, web information only or no CSR information at all. Section C classified the auditing and assurance of the CSR information and included two items: ‘disclosure about internal assurance’ and ‘disclosure about external assurance’. Their variables were defined as 1 if they were explained and 0 if there was no discussion. Finally, section D captured the details of the CSR disclosure and included 10 subsections, each of which contained a different number of items.

This research instrument – Scorecard is a particular technique and is employed in a new area of China’s food industry to assess China’s food companies CSR performance by analysing their variables. This Scorecard can be updated regularly according to relatively CSR guidelines and applied in assessing CSR performance in the future.

Originality in data

In this research, there are two forms of data were collected: quantitative data generated from five-year CSR reports and qualitative data from semi-structured interviews. The quantitative data are then analysed using numerical comparisons and statistical inferences. In this study, the research instrument was designed to examine the CSR reports of selected food companies in China to explore the scale of the current level and situation of CSR and CSRD of China’s food industry. The qualitative data are collected through participant observation and interviews and then analysed by categorising patterns and reporting meaningful findings. In this research, semi-structured interviews were used to collect qualitative data regarding the motivation for and obstacles to CSR practice within these companies. By mixing both quantitative and qualitative research data, this research results are able to reach a better and broader understanding of the research objectives.

6.2.5 Executive summary

Under the general trend of accelerating the penetration of globalisation and deepening the concept of sustainable development, CSR has become the focus of academic and practical circles. More and more enterprises have incorporated CSR and business ethics into their strategic planning. To take the initiative to undertake social responsibilities is the requirement of social development for enterprises and entrepreneurs and the core strategy to promote sustainable development and the success of enterprises. Table 8.1 is a summary of research objectives and results.

Table 6.1 Summary of Research Objectives and Results

Research Objectives	Research Results
1. To explore the scale of the current level and situation of CSR and CSRD of China's food industry via desk research (content analysis – scorecard).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall CSR information disclosure level is very low; • CSR information disclosure is incomplete; • CSR knowledge is sufficient.
2. To identify motivations and challenges to conduct or disclose CSR information of food industry in China via in-depth interviews.	<p>Motivations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From the stakeholder aspect: to gain profits and be a good citizen; • From the legitimacy aspect: to comply with laws and regulations and the social contract; • From the institutional aspect: to gain social culture expectations and normative expectations of the professional community. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From the stakeholder aspect: insufficient knowledge from each aspect of stakeholders; • From the legitimacy aspect: incomplete and inefficient legal system; • From the institutional aspect: underdeveloped CSR system under the coercion, imitation and regulation.
3. To discuss improvement approaches to increase the knowledge and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce a mandatory disclosure requirement; • Perfect the content of CSR reports; • Strengthen supervision and increase the intensity of punishment;

China's food industry is growing rapidly, and its contribution to economic growth is increasing annually. However, due to the low entry requirements, the number of food enterprises is large, the scale is small, the distribution is scattered, the degree of intensification is not high and the quality and safety management ability is low. China's food safety problems continue. The public has lost confidence in food companies since food safety scandals happened. China's food industry's reputation in the world has also been severely damaged. Food safety problems have highlighted the lack of social responsibility of China's food companies. Therefore, it is of great significance to discuss and promote the CSR of China's food industry, whether from the perspective of people's rights and interests or the development of enterprises.

China's food industry not only provides safe and healthy food for consumers but also should protect the environment, save energy, reduce consumption, reduce emissions and provide employment opportunities for society. At the same time, it should also be willing to perform social responsibility from the ethical aspect, so that the concept of CSR can be gradually integrated into the mission of the industry, forming the social responsibility values with the characteristics of the food industry, and making sustainable development an internal requirement and driving force for the development of the industry.

Based on this background, the research combines the qualitative and quantitative analysis methods that are explained in Chapter 3. According to the definition of CSR, stakeholder theory, institutional theory, legitimacy theory and CASS-CSR and GRI indexes as references, Chapter 4 introduces the design of a scorecard, which is employed to assess the performance of China's

food companies' CSR. Chapter 5 explores valuable insights from four groups of participants by applying semi-structured in-depth interviews. Food companies' need a sound corporate culture and strive to provide employees with better conditions for labour, life and development. Human resource training and incentive systems are encouraged to be set up, and adequate training budgets encourage employees to further their studies to improve their working skills and social responsibility awareness.

In Chapter 4, the scorecard is applied for accessing the 5 years of disclosed CSR reports from China's top 100 food companies. The research findings showed or show that the company size effect is noticeable, which means larger companies produce more CSRDs than smaller companies. Furthermore, CSR report information from larger companies is of higher quality compared to the smaller companies. This finding comes from reading their CSR reports; some smaller companies' CSR reports show high similarities for each year. CSR reports hardly reflect updates except for the figures from them. From the disclosure category aspect, the environment index is the most widely disclosed category, while the least reported category is the social index. This finding reflects the overall degree of recognition of which area China's food companies pay attention to. This can be influenced by the social situation or government policies.

Another interesting finding is that liquor companies show a better CSR performance than other types of food companies in China. As for the legal theory and institutional theory influence, the survival of an organisation depends not just on its material resources, operation, technique and marketing, but also on the organisation's perceived legitimacy (Powell and DiMaggio, 1991). In addition, the liquor companies' good performance on their CSR can be useful for them to get public support and further help them to maintain or achieve the success of the

business operation.

In the national and local charity activities for disaster relief, we can see the kindness of China's food companies. In the event of natural disasters, such as earthquakes, snow disasters, drought, flood and debris flow, their products are the first relief materials that appear in the hands of the disaster victims. It shows that Confucianism has gone deep into Chinese people's heart, to be benevolent, philanthropic and humane.

The food industry cannot develop without the help of external stakeholders such as the Chinese government, consumers and suppliers. Companies in the whole industry not only obtain social resources to exercise production capacity and maximise the interests of shareholders but also perform in the interests of government departments, employees, suppliers, consumers and other stakeholders, as well as the interests of environmental protection and community harmony. It is necessary to continue to strengthen communication with stakeholders, listen to views and suggestions from all sectors of society, respond to stakeholders' concerns in a timely manner and fulfil their social responsibilities to related stakeholders.

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Appendix 2: Participant Letter of Invitation

Participant Letter of Invitation

Research Project Title	Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in China: Evidence from the Food Industry
Research Investigator	Yuxiao Zhou [Redacted] [Redacted] <div style="border: 1px solid red; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Personal details withheld.</div>

Dear Sir or Madam,

This is a letter of invitation to enquire if you would like to take part in a PhD research project regarding to the Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in China by the means of a face to face or telephone interview which would last 45 minutes to 1 hour to complete.

Before you decide if you would like to take part it is important for you to understand why the project is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to carefully read the **Participant Information Sheet** and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask me if there is anything that is not clear, or if you would like more information.

If you would like to take part, please complete and return the **Consent Form**.

Please do not hesitate to contact me if you have any questions.

Yours faithfully,

Yuxiao Zhou

参与者邀请信

研究课题	关于中国食品行业企业社会责任披露的现状
研究人员	姓名：周昱晓 [Redacted] [Redacted] Personal details withheld.

尊敬的先生/女士，

您好！我是留学英国西苏格兰大学商学院的博士研究生。为了进一步了解中国食品行业企业社会责任披露的现状，及提高和促进中国食品行业企业社会责任的披露水准，我诚挚的邀请您参与此项“*关于中国食品行业企业社会责任披露的现状*”课题研究的采访。此采访将通过面对面或者电话采访的方式进行，预计采访时长为 45 分钟到 1 个小时。

在您决定是否参与此研究的采访前，请您仔细阅读我所提供的 **参与者信息说明** (participant information sheet)。这对您了解此采访的意义，内容以及过程环节，有着很重要的作用。如果对于此采访的具体信息，有任何不清楚的地方，或者希望了解更多信息，欢迎与我联系。

如果您决定参与此采访，请签署并归还 **同意书** (consent form)。

如有任何疑问，欢迎随时与我联系。

敬礼

周昱晓

Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Research Project Title	Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in China: Evidence from the Food Industry
Research Investigator	Yuxiao Zhou <div style="background-color: black; width: 300px; height: 15px; margin: 5px 0;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid red; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Personal details withheld.</div> <div style="background-color: black; width: 300px; height: 15px; margin: 5px 0;"></div>

What is the purpose of this project?

The purpose of this research project is to study the current Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) disclosing level of China’s food industry and to improve and promote their CSR practice.

Following this, this research explores the scale of current level and situation of CSR and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure (CSR) of China’s food industry via desk search. Then to identify motivations for and obstacles to conduct or disclosure CSR of food industry in China via in-depth interview; Finally to discuss improvement approaches of increasing the knowledge and comprehension about CSR in China’s food industry.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because you are a related stakeholder and therefore we are interested in your opinion, reasoning and beliefs as to the appropriate and effective understanding of the current CSR condition in China. We are also interested in your opinion, reasoning and belief as to the contribution to improve and promote CSR practice in China.

What happens if I volunteer to take part in this project?

First, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part, you will be asked to complete and return the **Consent Form**. Then a face to face or telephone interview will be arranged. The recording will be conducted during the interview. You will be sent the transcript and given the opportunity to correct any factual errors.

Will I receive any financial reward or travel expenses for taking part?

No

Are there any other benefits of taking part?

You will be contributing and helping to improve and promote the CSR practice in food industry in China.

Will participation involve any physical discomfort or harm?

This research involves no physical discomfort or harm.

Will participation involve any embarrassment or other psychological stress?

This research should not cause any psychological stress or embarrassment.

How will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

The questions will not ask for any sensitive personal details. Also data analysis and write up will be anonymity.

How will my data be used?

The overall results will be fed back to research investigator Yuxiao Zhou. The data will also be able to be accessed by Director of Studies: Dr. Michael Xin Guo, Dr. Abeer Hassan and Professor Angus Duff.

Who has reviewed this study?

This research project has undergone full ethical scrutiny and all procedures have been risk assessed and approved by the Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland.

What if I am unhappy during my participation in the project?

You are free to withdraw from the project at any time. If you choose to withdraw from the interview, the recording will be deleted by the research investigator as soon as the interview has terminated. You do not have to give a reason for your withdrawal. Any personal information or data that you have provide (both paper and electronic) will be destroyed or deleted as soon as possible after your withdrawal. After you have completed the research you can still withdraw your personal information and data by contacting the research investigator.

How do I take part?

Contact the investigator using the contact details given below. She will answer any queries and explain how you can get involved.

Name: Yuxiao Zhou

Personal details withheld.

参与者信息说明

研究课题	关于中国食品行业企业社会责任披露的现状
研究人员	姓名：周昱晓 Personal details withheld.

此研究的目的是什么？

此课题研究的主要目的是去了解中国食品行业企业社会责任披露的现状和水准。并根据实际情况提供可行的意见来改进和提高中国食品行业在企业社会责任方面的具体实践方针。

为了达到此目的，此研究首先查阅并研究中国的食品公司所发表的企业社会责任报告。然后通过进行深入的采访来了解中国食品公司披露其企业社会责任信息的动机和阻碍。最后根据研究人员通过以上两种方式得出的结论结合本身的知识水准，提供可行的意见来改进和提高中国食品行业在企业社会责任方面的未来发展。

为什么我会被选中参与此研究？

您被选中参与此研究，是因为您是关于此课题紧密相关的利益者。您的观点对于此研究有着重要的价值，同时对于此研究课题的目的有着重要的指导作用。

如果我自愿参与此课题研究，将会发生什么？

首先，由您自主决定是否参与此课题研究。一旦您决定参与，请填写并交还参与者同意书。稍后，我们将会安排对您进行面对面，或者电话采访。采访过程将会采取全程录音。参访结束后，您将会收到关于您在此采访内容问答的文字记录。如有任何记录有误的地方，您将有机会进行修正。

如果参与此研究，我是否会收到金钱奖励或者差旅费补助？

很抱歉，参与此研究属自愿无偿性质。您将不会得到任何金钱方面的补偿。

与我而言，参与此项课题研究的意义是什么？

您的宝贵意见和想法，将会对真正得切合实际地帮助和提高中国食品行业在企业社会责任实践方面有着重大贡献。

参与此研究是否会造成任何身体上的不适或者伤害？

此研究不会造成任何身体上的不适或者伤害。

此研究是否会包含使人难堪或者心理压力的部分？

此研究不会涉及使人难堪或者引起心理压力的部分。

在此研究中，我的个人信息将是如何被进行保密的？

在此采访中，您不会被问及任何敏感的私人信息。在之后的数据分析和文章内容书写中，将会采用代号的方式来代表每一位受访人。

我所受访的内容将是如何被使用的？

受访的过程和数据分析将由研究人员周昱晓来进行。其指导老师 Dr. Michael Xin Guo, Dr. Abeer Hassan 还有 Professor Angus Duff 在需要的情况下，可以查阅其受访的具体内容。

谁审核和批准此项研究？

此项研究已经获得英国西苏格兰大学道德委员会审核和批准。

如果在参与采访的过程中，遇到不开心的或者改变受访意愿的情况下怎么办？

在您进行受访的过程中，随时有自由和权利决定终止此受访。在您决定终止受访后，并结束受访后，研究员将尽快删除关于您的一切信息和资料（纸质版及电子版）。您或许会被问及终止受访的理由，但您不必必须回答。即使在您完成了此次受访后，您依然有机会联系研究员来退出此次研究。

我如何参与此项研究？

请根据提供的联系方式，联系研究员。如有任何关于参与此受访的疑问，研究员将会一一解答。

研究员：周昱晓

邮箱

联系电话：

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 4: Interview Consent Form

Interview Consent Form

Research project title: Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in China: Evidence from the Food Industry

Research investigator: Yuxiao Zhou

Research participants name:

The interview will take 45 minutes to 60 minutes. We do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to stop the interview or withdraw from the research at any time.

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of the above research project. Ethical procedures for academic research undertaken from UK institutions require that interviewees explicitly agree to being interviewed and how the information contained in their interview will be used. This consent form is necessary for us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying **information sheet** and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following:

- the interview will be recorded and a transcript will be produced
- you will be sent the transcript and given the opportunity to correct any factual errors
- the transcript of the interview will be analysed by research investigator
- access to the interview transcript will be limited and academic colleagues and researchers with whom he might collaborate as part of the research process
- any summary interview content, or direct quotations from the interview, that are made available through academic publication or other academic outlets will be anonymized so that you cannot be identified, and care will be taken to ensure that other information in the interview that could identify yourself is not revealed
- any variation of the conditions above will only occur with your further explicit approval

Printed Name

Participants Signature

Date

Researchers Signature

Date

同意书

研究课题：关于中国食品行业企业社会责任披露的现状

研究人员：周昱晓

受访者：

此采访将预计持续 45 分钟至 1 个小时。在您的参与中，将不会发生造成个人风险的情况，但您依然有权利随时暂停或者退出本次受访。

首先非常感谢您对于本研究课题的积极参与。根据英国相关机构要求，任何一个学术研究课题在进行相关采访前，必须获得受访人的认可和同意，并且使受访人了解他们的受访内容将会如何被使用。此同意书可以使研究员确保您将明确了解参与此采访的相关信息。请您仔细阅读以下信息，如没有疑问并同意继续采访，请签字。

- 采访全程将会录音。随后采访内容将会编辑整理为文字版本。
- 您将会收到研究员整理编辑好的文字版本。并将有机会对其有出入的内容进行修正。
- 采访内容将由研究员本人分析。
- 只有研究员本人，以及研究员的指导老师有权利查阅采访内容的原本。
- 在随后的论文书写中，如有任何采访内容的称述部分，或者直接引用的原话，都将会对个人信息采取保密措施。将会确保您的个人信息不会泄漏。
- 如果以上情况发生任何变化，都将会在获得您本人的明确认可后进行。

受访者（签名）：

日期：

研究员（签名）：

日期：

Appendix 5: Interview Questions

Interview Questions – Consumers

Section 1: Introduction	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To introduce this research aim and significance; 2) To explain the importance of interviewees' participation; 3) To assure the confidentiality; 4) To assure the Interview Consent Form signed.
Section 2: Scale of current level and situation of CSR in China's food industry	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Are you aware of CSR concept? What does it mean to you? 2) What is the food companies' most important social responsibilities in your opinion? 3) What the current CSR information disclosure level in the overall China's food industry according to your knowledge?
Section 3: Motivations and obstacles	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Why are you concerned about the CSR in food companies? If you are not, please give reasons. If yes, please explain what cause your concern of CSR in China's food industry? 2) Why are you more willing to purchase a product with higher price but it is produced by a food company with higher CSR performance? 3) Why a food company do not or not completely disclose CSR information as you know?
Section 4: Improvement approaches	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) What do cause the food company to fail to perform its CSR? What are your suggestions to improve the current CSR practice of food companies in China? 2) What are your recommendations to develop future CSR policies/activities in China's food industry?
Section 5: Conclusion	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To discuss any unclear or incomplete points in the interview; 2) To seek any suggestions for future research.
Thank you for your participation and cooperation.	

采访问题 --- 消费者

1. 介绍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 介绍研究的目的是其重要性； 2) 解释受访者的参与对这项研究的重要性； 3) 解释并确认研究的保密性； 4) 请受访者签署相关同意书。
2. 中国食品行业的企业社会责任现状和水平	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 您是否了解企业社会责任这一理念？对您来说，企业社会责任意味着什么？ 2) 在您看来，作为一个食品企业，最重要的企业社会责任是什么？ 3) 据您所了解，中国食品企业在企业社会责任信息披露的现状是什么，以及整体水平如何？
3. 动机与阻碍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 是什么引起了你去关注中国食品行业的企业社会责任？如果您并不关注这个问题，请解释为什么不关注。如果您关注这个问题，请解释是什么因素引起了您的关注。 2) 您是否更加愿意购买一款更贵的但是具有良好企业社会责任的企业生产的食品？ 3) 在您看来，食品公司不披露或者没有完整披露企业社会责任信息的原因有什么？
4. 改善方法	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 您认为是什么原因导致了一个食品公司未能很好的开展和执行相关的企业社会责任？对此，您有什么改善的建议？ 2) 对于中国食品行业的企业社会责任未来的发展，您有什么建议？
5. 结束语	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 讨论在以上采访中不清楚的和未完成的内容； 2) 咨询对与未来研究的建议。
感谢您的参与与配合！	

Interview Questions – Employees

Section 1: Introduction	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5) To introduce this research aim and significance; 6) To explain the importance of interviewees' participation; 7) To assure the confidentiality; 8) To assure the Interview Consent Form signed.
Section 2: Scale of current level and situation of CSR in China's food industry	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4) What do the CSR policies/practices have in your company? How does your company disseminate its CSR policies and performance? 5) According to your knowledge, in what aspect of the CSR is the best performance in your company? And in what aspect of the CSR is lack of implementation and development? 6) What the current CSR information disclosure level of your company in your view to compare to the overall china's food industry? What the CSR information disclosure level of the overall china's food industry as you know?
Section 3: Motivations and obstacles	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) What motivates your company to develop CSR or engage in CSR activities? What are the objections? Any examples? 2) Does CSR help your company to attract employees?
Section 4: Improvement approaches	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) According to the point 2 in Section 2 you referred, what are your suggestions or recommendations to your company in developing CSR policies/activities?
Section 5: Conclusion	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To discuss any unclear or incomplete points in the interview; 2) To seek any suggestions for future research.
Thank you for your participation and cooperation.	

采访问题 ---员工

6. 介绍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 介绍研究的目的是其重要性； 2) 解释受访者的参与对这项研究的重要性； 3) 解释并确认研究的保密性； 4) 请受访者签署相关同意书。
7. 中国食品行业的企业社会责任现状和水准	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 您所在的公司有着什么样的关于企业社会责任的政策和活动？又是如何宣传这些政策？如何开展相关活动的？ 2) 据您了解，您所在公司在企业社会责任的那一方面表现的最好？又在哪些方面的实施和发展有所欠缺？ 3) 在您看来，相对与整个中国食品行业，您所在的公司对于企业社会责任信息的披露水准是什么？在您看来，整个中国食品行业关于企业社会责任信息的披露水准又是多少？
8. 动机与阻碍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 据您所知，是什么导致您所在的公司开展并且实施企业社会责任？或者有什么原因阻碍企业社会责任的发展？是否有实例说明？ 2) 开展并且实施企业社会责任是否有帮助您所在的公司更好的吸引员工？
9. 改善方法	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 根据您在采访第二部分的第二点所提及的内容，对于您所在的公司将来关于企业社会责任政策的开展和活动有什么样的建议？
10. 结束语	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 讨论在以上采访中不清楚的和未完成的内容； 2) 咨询对与未来研究的建议。
感谢您的参与与配合！	

Interview Questions – Government Staff

Section 1: Introduction	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 9) To introduce this research aim and significance; 10) To explain the importance of interviewees' participation; 11) To assure the confidentiality; 12) To assure the Interview Consent Form signed.
Section 2: Scale of current level and situation of CSR in China's food industry	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7) From the government's point of view, what the current level and situation of CSR in China's industry? 8) According to your knowledge, in what aspect of the CSR is the best performance in the overall china's food industry? And in what aspect of the CSR is lack of implementation and development? 9) How have government policies affected CSR policy and practice in China's food industry.
Section 3: Motivations and obstacles	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) What motivates the government to take action on the development of CSR policy? Any objections? 2) How would companies benefit from following government policies? What are the punishment if they do not abide by the policies?
Section 4: Improvement approaches	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) What are the flaws on the basis of current policies? Any suggestions to improve them? 2) What are the plan and future aim to develop CSR policies/practice in China according to the point 2 in section 2 you referred?
Section 5: Conclusion	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To discuss any unclear or incomplete points in the interview; 2) To seek any suggestions for future research.
Thank you for your participation and cooperation.	

采访问题 --- 政府工作人员

11. 介绍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 介绍研究的目的是和其重要性； 2) 解释受访者的参与对这项研究的重要性； 3) 解释并确认研究的保密性； 4) 请受访者签署相关同意书。
12. 中国食品行业的企业社会责任现状和水准	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 从政府角度，中国食品行业企业社会责任信息的披露现状和水准如何？ 2) 据您了解，现中国食品行业在企业社会责任的那一方面表现的最好？又在哪些方面的实施和发展有所欠缺？ 3) 政府相关政策是如何影响和指导中国食品行业的企业社会责任的实施和相关活动的开展？
13. 动机与阻碍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 是什么原因促使政府关注中国食品行业的企业社会责任，并制定相关的政策？又有着什么样的阻碍？ 2) 食品公司在遵从政府政策时有什么样的奖励政策？对于没有遵从的公司又有什么惩处？
14. 改善方法	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 在现阶段的关于食品行业的企业社会责任的相关政策有什么已知的缺陷？有什么建议进行改进？ 2) 针对于您在本采访第二部分第二点所提及的发展缺陷，对于中国食品行业未来的企业社会责任的政策和活动的开展实施有着什么样的计划，提议和目标？
15. 结束语	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 讨论在以上采访中不清楚的和未完成的内容； 2) 咨询对与未来研究的建议。
感谢您的参与与配合！	

Interview Questions – Managers

Section 1: Introduction	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 13) To introduce this research aim and significance; 14) To explain the importance of interviewees' participation; 15) To assure the confidentiality; 16) To assure the Interview Consent Form signed.
Section 2: Scale of current level and situation of CSR in China's food industry	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10) To look through the CSR in China's food industry, what the current level and situation of CSR in China's food industry in your view? 11) When does your company start to operate its CSR policy? What is the development history? 12) According to your knowledge, in what aspect of the CSR is the best performance in your company? And in what aspect of the CSR is lack of implementation and development? 13) With your understanding of this company, what is the current disclosing level of your company's CSR information?
Section 3: Motivations and obstacles	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) What motivates your company to develop CSR? What are the objections? 2) What motivates your company to engage in CSR activities? Any examples? 3) What challenges does your company have when implementing CSR policies or conducting CSR activities? Do these challenges motivate your company to continue CSR activities or obstruct your company? 4) How could your company benefit from conduct CSR activities? Does this motivate your company?
Section 4: Improvement approaches	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) According to the point 3 in section 2 you referred, what aspects do you think the company needs to improve to develop a CSR policy/activities? How to operate the improvement?
Section 5: Conclusion	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To discuss any unclear or incomplete points in the interview; 2) To seek any suggestions for future research.
Thank you for your participation and cooperation.	

采访问题 --- 经理管理人员

16. 介绍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 介绍研究的目的是和其重要性； 2) 解释受访者的参与对这项研究的重要性； 3) 解释并确认研究的保密性； 4) 请受访者签署相关同意书。
17. 中国食品行业的企业社会责任现状和水准	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 纵观整个中国食品行业，在您看来中国食品行业的企业社会责任的开展水准如何？ 2) 您所在公司从何时起开展企业社会责任政策的？有着什么样的发展历史？ 3) 据您了解，您所在公司在企业社会责任的那一方面表现的最好？又在哪些方面的实施和发展有所欠缺？ 4) 据您了解，您所在企业的企业社会责任水准如何？
18. 动机与阻碍	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 是什么原因促进了您所在企业实施企业社会责任的政策？又有着什么样的阻碍呢？ 2) 是什么原因促进了您所在企业开展相关企业社会责任活动？请举例阐述。 3) 在实施企业社会责任的政策和开展相关活动时，遇到什么样的挑战？这些挑战是激励了你们改善并继续开展，还是打击了你们的积极性？ 4) 您所在的公司是否有得益于相关开展的企业社会责任活动？这些益处是否激励本公司未来在企业社会责任的方面的发展？
19. 改善方法	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 根据您在本采访的第二部分的第三点所提及的内容，从您的角度来看，您对您所在公司关于企业社会责任的政策和未来活动的开展，有什么样的建议？您又有什么样的提议去进行这些改进？
20. 结束语	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 讨论在以上采访中不清楚的和未完成的内容； 2) 咨询对与未来研究的建议。
感谢您的参与与配合！	

